

Anion-driven enabled functional nanomaterials from metal and metal oxide nanoparticles

RESEARCH: Review

Yi Zhou ^a, Jun Li ^a, Long Liu ^a, Cuifang Wang ^b, Reilly P. Lynch ^c, Bing Bai ^{a,*}, Hsien-Yi Hsu ^{d,e}, Zongyou Yin ^f, Andreu Cabot ^{g,h,*}, Richard D. Robinson ^{c,*}, Ido Hadar ⁱ, Zongping Shao ^b, Mark A. Buntine ^k, Xuyong Yang ^{j,*}, Guohua Jia ^{k,*}

^a Key Lab for Special Functional Materials, Ministry of Education, National and Local Joint Engineering Research Center for High-Efficiency Display and Lighting Technology, School of Nanoscience and Materials Engineering, and Collaborative Innovation Center of Nano Functional Materials and Applications, Henan University, Kaifeng 475004, PR China

^b WA School of Mines: Minerals, Energy and Chemical Engineering (WASM-MECE), Curtin University, Perth, Western Australia, Australia

^c Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Cornell University, Ithaca, NY 14850, USA

^d School of Energy and Environment & Department of Materials Science and Engineering, City University of Hong Kong, Kowloon Tong, Hong Kong, China

^e Shenzhen Research Institute of City University of Hong Kong, Shenzhen, 518057, PR China

^f Research School of Chemistry, The Australian National University, ACT 2601, Australia

^g Catalonia Institute for Energy Research – IREC, Sant Adrià de Besòs, Barcelona 08930, Spain

^h ICREA, Pg. Lluís Companys 23, 08010 Barcelona, Catalonia, Spain

ⁱ Institute of Chemistry, and the Center for Nanoscience and Nanotechnology, The Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Jerusalem, 91904, Israel

^j Key Laboratory of Advanced Display and System Applications of Ministry of Education, Shanghai University, 149 Yanchang Road, Shanghai 200072, PR China

^k School of Molecular and Life Sciences, Curtin University, Perth, WA 6102, Australia

Despite significant progress in the synthesis of nanocrystals (NCs) by conventional wet-chemical synthetic approaches, producing nanostructures with complex architectures tailored to specific applications remains a formidable challenge. Recently, anion-driven synthesis, including oxidation, sulfidation, phosphorization, nitridation, selenization, telluridation, and chlorination have emerged as a versatile approach to produce novel nanostructured materials with tuned size, morphology, crystal structure, and composition from the chemical transformation of template NCs. This chemical conversion can be accompanied by the formation of new NCs architectures, overall modifying the surface chemistry and the mechanical, electronic, optical, and magnetic properties of the material. This strategy can be used to optimize the performance of the material in a range of applications, including energy conversion and storage, catalysis, bioimaging, drug delivery, and sensing. In this review, we first detail the possible anion-driven synthesis and discuss the related underlying mechanisms. Subsequently, we overview the unique nanostructure obtained by this strategy and summarize their functional properties and potential applications. Finally, we provide perspectives and discuss the remaining challenges and the new opportunities in this field.

Keywords: Anion-driven synthesis; Colloid nanocrystal; Hollow nanostructure; Kirkendall effect

* Corresponding authors.

E-mail addresses: Bai, B. (bingbai@henu.edu.cn), Cabot, A. (acabot@irec.cat), Robinson, R.D. (rdr82@cornell.edu), Yang, X. (yangxy@shu.edu.cn), Jia, G. (guohua.jia@curtin.edu.au).

Introduction

Over the past decades, a wide range of colloidal nanocrystals (NCs) developed by numerous synthetic routes underpin both fundamental research and technological applications [1–11]. Nowadays, such synthetic strategies are key tools to composite nanoarchitectures with precise size, shape, crystal phase, composition, and surface chemistry, leading to tailored mechanical, electronic, optical, and magnetic properties. The currently conventional wet-chemical synthetic approaches, such as coprecipitation, hot-injection, heating-up, and solvo(hydro)thermal methods, are capable of producing various types of NCs through the reaction of anionic and cationic precursors or the thermal-decomposition of single-source [12–21]. However, NCs with complex structures and metastable phases are not accessible through these direct synthesis methods [22–27]. For example, $\text{CoO}_x\text{S}_{0.18}$ NCs with a hollow structure [26] and Cu_xS [28,29] of metastable phase, can not only be used to adsorb and catalyze various molecules, but also have the ability to encapsulate and deliver specific molecules. Notably, these structures usually cannot be synthesized through direct methods but can form via the sulfidation of pre-synthesized metal oxide NCs. Another example is the synthesis of thermodynamically metastable spinel-type Ni_3Se_4 NCs, which are rarely accessible using conventional direct synthesis methods but can be obtained through the chemical conversion such as the cation exchange reaction of $\text{Cu}_{1.8}\text{Se}$ NCs with Ni^{2+} [30].

Chemical conversion of metal and metal compound NCs has emerged as a meaningful strategy to forge new NC architectures with special chemical and structural complexity that are inaccessible via direct conventional wet-chemical synthetic approaches [31–35]. Such chemical transformations, including cation exchange [24,27,28,36–55] and galvanic replacement reactions [31,56–66], benefit from the efficient and rapid atomic diffusion within nanometric structures. Additionally, these chemical transformation reactions are frequently accompanied by structural changes such as the formation of voids, underpinned by mechanisms such as the Kirkendall effect [31,57,67–71]. The novel nanostructures created can be advantageous in a wide spectrum of applications, including energy conversion and storage, catalysis, bioimaging, drug delivery, and sensing.

Cation exchange reactions have become a popular approach to obtaining NCs with metastable phases and complex heterogeneous compositions. Nevertheless, the significance of surface ligands has not been extensively investigated, and it is challenging to entirely eliminate the presence of residual ions and defects [27,44,51,72]. Galvanic exchange reactions are an effective approach for the synthesis of hollow nanostructures manifesting porous walls, controllable size, and tuned elemental composition. So far, the template NCs are generally made of a noble metal which acts as a reducing agent, but there are still numerous opportunities to utilize the electrochemical potential difference between the metals present in the template and the solution as the driving force to produce new nanostructured materials [59,61,63,64,73]. The Kirkendall effect is a classical phenomenon in metallurgy that has gained significant attention within the nanoscience and nanotechnology fields due to its fundamental role in the formation of hollow NCs during the chemical trans-

formation of solid template NCs [31,67,74]. However, adjusting the diffusion rate of the involved species to regulate the formation of voids and to prevent disruption, collapse and reconstruction of the nanostructures has proven challenging [75].

Anion-driven synthesis is a chemical transformation process encompassing the reaction of a metal or metal oxide with an anionic reagent, leading to the formation of a novel metal compound such as a metal chalcogenide, metal pnictide, or metal halide. The synthesis approaches within this field encompass both additive reactions, exemplified by the oxidation of metal NCs to yield metal oxide NCs, and anion exchange reactions, which involve only metal oxide NCs as the initial template. A prime example of the latter is the transformation of metal oxide NCs into metal chalcogenide NCs through reaction with a chalcogen source. In fact, colloidal metal NCs are susceptible to oxidation, a process that is often unavoidable for certain metals. Consequently, careful consideration must be given to their handling and storage. The conversion of metal oxides to metal sulfides, known as sulfidation, is a critical step in anion-driven synthesis [75–78]. This process involves replacing oxygen anions with sulfur anions, highlighting the importance of controlling oxidation reactions to achieve successful synthesis of metal sulfides with desired properties. Moreover, metal oxides, owing to their higher covalent nature, distinguish themselves from the more common perovskite compounds with weak covalent bonding [54,79–82]. Herein, we propose that metal oxides can serve as sacrificial templates in anion-driven synthesis owing to their unique chemical properties.

So far, a variety of anion-driven synthesis including oxidation, sulfidation, selenization, tellurization, nitridation, phosphorization and chlorination have been reported to synthesize NCs. Due to the fact that the process of anion-driven synthesis is determined by the (1) interaction of chemical substances in terms of their association and dissociation, and (2) the diffusion of atomic species, electrons (Cabrera-Mott theory) and holes throughout the nanoparticles (NPs) [83]. These anion-driven synthesis methods have demonstrated the ability to generate NCs with customizable properties that are not accessible through conventional wet-chemical synthesis. It is widely acknowledged that the radius of monatomic anions is generally much larger than that of cations, and the anions often serve as the framework for metal compound NCs, which may determine the morphology of the NCs. Additionally, anions can alter the surface energy of NCs. For instance, halides are preferentially adsorbed on certain facets to stabilize gold surface and promote specific crystal orientations, resulting in anisotropic growth [84]. Moreover, anions impact the kinetics of ion incorporation into the crystal lattices and their charges and sizes influence how quickly ions from the solution attachment to the surface of the NCs affecting the growth rate and morphology of NCs, while softer anions may facilitate the growth of NCs compared to harder ones [85]. The type and concentration of anions also influence the defect formation during the crystallization, which can act as nucleation sites for further growth, thereby affecting the stability and morphology [86].

Therefore, during anion-driven synthesis, the entire crystal structure of a template is in a state of framework-collapse. By

adjusting the mobility of metal cations (from metal or metal oxide template) and anions (from anionic reagent) before reaching the final equilibrium state, a more thermodynamically or kinetically favorable morphology can be achieved [22,25,87–89]. Hence, this framework-collapse state in anion-driven synthesis can provide an opportunity to obtain nanostructures with special architectures and even entirely new ionic frameworks [27,28,33].

In this review, we categorize materials based on the preservation or alteration of the template morphology/architecture during anion-driven synthesis into the following categories:

- (1) Nanostructures with altered architecture, such as yolk-shell (core–void–shell), hollow, nanonecklaces [90,91] (assembled from hollow or solid NPs), nanocages, nanopipes, and others, which exhibit distinct modifications to their initial templates.
- (2) Nanostructures with conserved template architectures, such as nanospheres, nanorods, nanoplatelets, and so forth, which maintain a close resemblance to their original template morphologies [28,45,75,77,87,92].

Anion-driven synthesis typically transforms the structural and chemical composition of template NCs, thereby altering their physical properties [37,47,93,94]. In some cases, this alteration can be adjusted by tuning the extent of anion-driven synthesis of the initial NPs [89]. Moreover, the ability to modify the template architecture through anion-driven synthesis is particularly noteworthy, as it enables the production of nanostructures with special morphologies and functional properties that have the potential to optimize performance in specific application fields [31,74,95–106]. In recent decades, with the continuous development of the anion-driven synthesis, numerous new nanostructures have been prepared and employed in a wide range of applications and devices, including catalysis, [26,95,97,98,107–110] biomedical [111], gas sensing [112], lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) [112–115], supercapacitors [116–118], and solar cells [38]. For instance, several works have recently reported on the enhancement of the catalytic performance of NPs through anion-driven synthesis. The enhancement of the catalytic performance has been related to several different mechanisms, including:

- (1) An increase in activity due to the enlarged surface area of the produced NPs (e.g., transformation from solid to hollow or multi-shell structures).
- (2) An improvement in selectivity resulting from the differential diffusivity of reactants, intermediates, and products through the porous structures.
- (3) The generation of internal electric fields at hetero-junction interfaces.
- (4) The introduction of dopant heteroatoms, such as nitrogen (N), into specific nanomaterials, [117,119,120] which will be discussed in Section ‘Nitridation’.

This work discusses anion-driven synthesis on metal and metal oxide templates. First, the reaction mechanisms underpinning these chemical transformations are overviewed. Subse-

quently, various examples are discussed with special emphasis on the unique nanostructure obtained by this strategy, summarizing their functional properties and potential applications. Finally, the remaining challenges and the new opportunities in this field are elaborated.

Reaction mechanisms

As previously defined, anion-driven synthesis refers to a chemical transformation process where a template NC undergoes a compositional change by reacting with an anion source (Scheme 1). This process involves two primary reaction types: metal NP as template ($M + X \rightarrow MX$, where M represents a metal and X represents an anion) and metal oxide NP as template ($MO + X \rightarrow MX + O^{2-}$, where MO is a metal oxide and O^{2-} usually combine with H^+ or other species in colloidal system). From a perspective in NC synthesis, to the best of our knowledge, there is no existing comprehensive review that systematically discusses the underlying reaction mechanisms of anion-driven synthesis in detail. Notably, anion-driven synthesis is more different with ion exchange, which includes both cation exchange and anion exchange. Firstly, metal NCs are used as a template for anion-driven synthesis. Besides, the cationic lattice is generally considered stable in ion exchange reactions, while in anion-driven synthesis, the metal cations can reorganize and diffuse through the evolving shell to react with the precursor anions. This can result in the formation of completely different crystal lattices and NCs morphologies [89,121,122].

Thus, while ion exchange reactions have been extensively examined and reviewed, [44] anion-driven synthesis deserves to be comprehensively introduced to better understand their mechanisms, potentials and limitations to produce novel structures. In this section, we will initially discuss the thermodynamics and kinetics of the anion-driven synthesis with providing some representative examples.

Thermodynamics

Two types of anion-driven syntheses must be differentiated as described above: (1) The formation of MX by reacting M NCs with X^{n-} anions; (2) The formation of MX by reacting MO NCs with X^{n-} anions. Although several anionic sources are not present as ions but as molecules (N_2 , O_2 , S_8), potentially solids/liquids (Se, Te) or in more complex forms (NH_3 , Na_2S) can be converted into free anions and eventually participate in the anion-driven synthesis as anions.

These two processes can be written as:

Two approximations are generally considered to study these systems: (1) While anion-driven synthesis can take place between heterovalent anions, only monovalent anions will be considered. For instance, $n = m = 1$, because the entropy change (ΔS) of heterovalent ions can be neglected according to a recent report by Manna et al. [44]; (2) The specific crystallographic

SCHEME 1

Different Chemical Transformation Methods for Anion-driven Synthesis.

phases of the template and produced NCs play a minor role in the overall free energy [44]; (3) The effects of solution and ligand are equivalent for both the template and product NCs.

Under these approximations and following the work from Rivest et al. [41] on ion exchange reactions, Type 1 anion-driven synthesis involves three steps: (i) M-M dissociation; (ii) M-X association; and (iii) X^- desolvation/dissociation. It is important to note that the anionic reagent can manifest in various forms, e.g. ions in solution, molecular gas, crystalline solid, *etc.* A representative example of a type 1 anion-driven synthesis is a metal oxidation process wherein molecular oxygen is consumed and no other anions come out from starting materials. To estimate if a type 1 anion-driven synthesis is thermodynamically favored, one just needs to calculate the enthalpy of M-M dissociation and M-X association because the entropy change (ΔS) is always negative and it plays a minor role in determining the overall free energy of the reaction [44]. Type 2 anion-driven synthesis can be divided into four ideal steps: (i) M-O dissociation, (ii) M-X association, (iii) X^- desolvation/dissociation, and (iv) O^{2-} solvation/association. Similarly, the anionic reagent and released anions also can take different forms as in type 1 anion-driven synthesis, including solvated ions in solution, gas molecules, solids, *etc.* A representative example of a type 2 anion-driven synthesis is the reaction of a metal oxide with sulfur to produce a metal sulfide, wherein sulfur is consumed and oxygen is released into the atmosphere. Therefore, to ascertain the spontaneity of the anion-driven synthesis, it is essential to calculate the Gibbs free energy change (ΔG) of each individual

step. The ΔG of the first two steps of the anion-driven synthesis can be accurately assessed by considering the standard molar reaction Gibbs free energy ($\Delta_r G^\ominus_m$) of MO dissociation and MX formation. It is worth noting that, to accurately calculate the free energy change (ΔG) for the initial two steps in anion-driven NC synthesis which is different from the chemical transformation of bulk materials, it is necessary to account for the surface energy contributions of MO and MX NCs. Furthermore, the ΔG for the subsequent steps of solvation and desolvation can be determined by considering the anions' affinity for the solvent and the ligands employed in the anion-driven synthesis [41,44,51,123–129]. Since no other ions (besides O^{2-} and X^-) are lost or gained in the anion-driven synthesis, the entropic contribution (ΔS) of the anions in solution to the overall ΔG can be disregarded. Consequently, more detailed numerical calculations in the examples will be provided below.

Here, the first key parameter to estimate the reaction feasibility is the standard molar reaction Gibbs free energy of the formed oxide or sulfide (Table 1), which can be used to predict the spontaneity of anion-driven synthesis directly. For example, $3Fe(s) + 2O_2(g) \rightarrow Fe_3O_4(s)$, $\Delta_r G^\ominus_m = -1015.4$ kJ/mol; $Cu(s) + S(s) \rightarrow CuS(s)$, $\Delta_r G^\ominus_m = -53.6$ kJ/mol.

A comprehensive understanding of the thermodynamic parameters is pivotal in assessing the feasibility and predicting the outcome of such reactions. Specifically, the free energy variations during the initial stages of anion-driven synthesis are crucial indicators of the reaction pathways and product formation. However, relying solely on Gibbs free energy may be insufficient,

TABLE 1

Thermodynamics data at normal temperature–pressure (NTP) of various materials potentially obtained from an anion-driven synthesis. $\Delta_r H^\ominus_m$ = standard molar reaction enthalpy change; S^\ominus_m = standard molar reaction entropy change; $\Delta_r G^\ominus_m$ = standard molar reaction Gibbs free energy. (P = 10⁵ Pa, T = 298 K).

Substance	$\Delta_r H^\ominus_m$ [kJ/mol]	S^\ominus_m [J/(mol·K)]	$\Delta_r G^\ominus_m$ [kJ/mol]
Fe ₃ O ₄	−1118.4	146.3	−1015.4
ZnS	−205.98	57.7	−201.29
ZnO	−348.28	43.64	−318.3
H ₂ O(g)	−241.818	188.825	−228.572
H ₂ O(l)	−285.83	69.91	−273.192
MnO	−385.2	59.7	−362.9
MnS	−214.2	78.2	−218.4
CoO	−237.9	53	−214.2
CoS	−82.8	/	/
CuO	−157.3	42.6	−129.7
CuS	−53.1	66.5	−53.6
Cu ₂ O	−168.6	93.1	−146
Cu ₂ S	−79.5	120.9	−86.2
NaOH(aq)	−470.114	48.1	−419.15
NaS	−364.8	83.7	−349.8
H ₂ S(g)	−20.63	205.79	−33.56

given the complexity of anion-driven reactions. Hence, in the following discussion, we delve deeper into the thermodynamic aspects of anion-driven synthesis, including the contributions of anionic reagent state and temperature, as well as other crucial parameters that influence the reaction mechanism.

For instance, to work out the standard molar reaction Gibbs free energy variation of anion-driven synthesis, either the desolvation or dissociation energy of ions in solution or stable elementary substance (N₂, O₂, S, Se, Te, P, etc.) which acts as the anionic reagent is required. When the anionic reagent is not a stable elementary substance, such as NH₃, Na₂S, H₂S, the Gibbs free energy of anion-driven synthesis is difficult to calculate.

However, if the actual Gibbs free energy change of the products is produced by unstable elementary substance, [28,75] it can be calculated by a thermodynamic formula ($\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S$), which is based on the specific experimental conditions in some examples (Table 2). Specifically, the values of $\Delta_r H^\ominus_m$ [kJ/mol] and $\Delta_r G^\ominus_m$ [kJ/mol] of anion-driven synthesis in Table 2 can be calculated by using a particular temperature in combination with the thermodynamic data from Table 1. For instance, MnO + H₂S → MnS + H₂O, $\Delta_r G^\ominus_m = \Delta_r G^\ominus_m(\text{MnS}) + \Delta_r G^\ominus_m(\text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{g}) - \Delta_r G^\ominus_m(\text{MnO}) - \Delta_r G^\ominus_m(\text{H}_2\text{S}, \text{g}) = -218.4 \text{ kJ/mol} - 228.572 \text{ kJ/mol} + 362.9 \text{ kJ/mol} + 33.56 \text{ kJ/mol} = -50.512 \text{ kJ/mol}$. Similarly, if this process proceeds at different temperature, $\Delta_r H^\ominus_m = -214.2 \text{ kJ/mol} - 241.818 \text{ kJ/mol} + 385.2 \text{ kJ/mol} + 20.63 \text{ kJ/mol} = -50.188 \text{ kJ/mol}$, $\Delta S^\ominus_m = 78.2 \text{ J/(mol·K)} + 188.825 \text{ J/(mol·K)} - 59.7 \text{ J/(mol·K)} - 205.79 \text{ J/(mol·K)} = 1.535 \text{ J/(mol·K)}$. At 160 °C, $\Delta_r G_m(433 \text{ K}) = \Delta_r H^\ominus_m - T\Delta S^\ominus_m = -50.188 \text{ kJ/mol} - 1.535 \text{ J/(mol·K)} \times 433 \text{ K} = -$

50.188 kJ/mol − 0.664655 kJ/mol × 433 K ≈ −50.85 kJ/mol. Notably, as discussed above, the entropy contribution to the total free energy is negligible.

As we progress in our examination of NC synthesis strategies, a particular focus must be placed on the thermodynamic aspects of anion-driven reactions. These reactions are pivotal in determining the properties and quality of the resulting NCs. To elucidate the feasibility and control of such reactions, a thorough analysis of the enthalpy and entropy changes during the initial stages is essential. Moreover, it is important to note that the spontaneity of some anion-driven synthesis reactions cannot be skimpily judged by Gibbs free energy change, because the dissociation or solution energy of anions in a colloidal solution generally represents the primary driving force. Therefore, a comprehensive evaluation encompassing parameters such as ligand-modulated hardness, solvation energy, and solubility constants [44] is necessary to gain a deeper understanding of the anion-driven synthesis process and its control.

Association and dissociation energies

To assess the feasibility of anion-driven synthesis reactions, a key consideration lies in estimating the enthalpy change. While accurate enthalpy values for reacting species may not be readily available, the association and dissociation energies involved in the initial stages of such reactions can provide valuable insights. In the context of anion-driven synthesis, these energies are particularly relevant as they govern the stability and reactivity of the involved highly reactive intermediates, such as radical anions. The intermediates play crucial roles in facilitating the transfer of electrons or holes, promoting specific reaction pathways, and ultimately leading to the formation of the desired NC products. The lattice enthalpy (ΔH_{latt}), commonly referred to as lattice energy, quantifies the energy required to disassemble a crystalline compound into its constituent isolated atoms or ions under standard conditions [130]. This energy can be experimentally determined using the “Bohr-Haber cycle,” a thermochemical cycle that relies on experimentally measured quantities such as heats of formation, sublimation, dissociation, ionization, and electron affinity. By estimating the association and dissociation energies of the initial steps in anion-driven synthesis and utilizing the Bohr-Haber cycle to calculate the lattice enthalpy, we can gain a theoretical understanding of the energetic feasibility of the reaction. This approach not only aids in the design of NC synthesis protocols but also sheds light on the mechanistic nuances of the reaction pathway.

Continuing from our previous discussion, the lattice enthalpy serves as a crucial parameter for assessing lattice stability [130,131]. The higher the lattice energy is, the greater the energy consumed to melt or dissolve the compound, indicating a more stable lattice structure. This parameter, ΔH_{latt} is used to explain/predict several physical and chemical properties of crystals. For

TABLE 2

Enthalpy and Gibbs free energy change of some anion-driven synthesis.

Starting NCs	Anionic reagent	Temp	Final NCs	Morphology	$\Delta_r H^\ominus_m$ [kJ/mol]	$\Delta_r G^\ominus_m$ [kJ/mol]
MnO	H ₂ S	160	MnS	solid sphere	−50.188	−50.9
ZnO	H ₂ S	160	ZnS	solid tetrapod	−78.888	−77.6
Cu ₂ O	Na ₂ S	RT	Cu _{2-x} S	polyhedral cage	−200.498	−155.5

instance, metal compounds with a high value of ΔH_{latt} tend to have high melting and boiling points due to the increased energy barrier for overcoming the strong chemical bonds. Consequently, ΔH_{latt} can serve as a valuable reference in adjusting the reaction temperature or predicting the stability of NCs during an anion-driven synthesis [25,32,132–134]. Moreover, according to the energy conservation law and the second law of thermodynamics, the larger the lattice energy, the stronger the chemical bond and the more stable the crystal [23,135,136]. Hence, the lattice enthalpy also provides a measure of the strength of the chemical bonds among ions within a compound. Generally, the lattice energy can be calculated from the crystal model by considering the Coulomb attraction and repulsion among ions in the lattice. ΔH_{latt} is influenced not only by the charge and radius of the ions but also by the ionic ordering and the specific crystal structure:

$$\Delta H_{latt} = \frac{N_A M Z_+ Z_- e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0\gamma_0} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right) \quad (3)$$

where N_A is the Avogadro constant, Z is the ion valence, r_0 is the average distance between a pair of ions, M is the Madron constant (related to the lattice type), ϵ_0 is the vacuum capacitance rate ($8.85419 \times 10^{-12} \text{ C}^{-2} \cdot \text{N}^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$) and n is the Bohr constant (its desirable value is 5–12). Taking a sodium chloride crystal as an example, $Z_+ = Z_- = 1$, $r_0 = 2.814 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}$, $M = 1.7476$, $n = 8$, and thus $\Delta H_{latt} = 755 \text{ kJ/mol}$. The lattice energies (ΔH_{latt}) of some common materials are displayed in Table 1 [137].

Notably, the absolute value of ΔH_{latt} of high-valent compounds (III–V) is generally much larger than that of low-valent ionic compounds (II–VI). This may be the reason why the synthesis of III–V compound NCs generally requires harsher conditions, including longer reaction time, higher temperature, and more reactive precursors, than for the synthesis of II–VI NCs [138]. Additionally, the absolute value of ΔH_{latt} of metal chalcogenides generally decreases as the ionic radius of the chalcogen increases. For instance, the lattice energy values of $M_x\text{Te}_y$ (M means metal) are lower than the corresponding $M_x\text{Se}_y$, and the same trend is seen when comparing $M_x\text{Se}_y$ with $M_x\text{S}_y$ or comparing $M_x\text{S}_y$ with $M_x\text{O}_y$. Therefore, we can roughly conclude that metal oxides spontaneously transform into metal chalcogenides via anion-driven synthesis, because the absolute value of ΔH_{latt} of metal chalcogenides is generally lower than that of the metal oxide.

However, two primary challenges arise when predicting the anion-driven synthesis from ΔH_{latt} : (1) Difficulty in obtaining accurate lattice energy values, particularly for crystals with polymorphic structures (allotropes); (2) Complexity of the resulting nanostructures in anion-driven synthesis (hollow, yolk-shell, nanocages, multi-shell and so on), which typically lack of any fixed ion ordering and fixed Madron constant. To overcome the limitations of ΔH_{latt} in predicting anion-driven synthesis resulting in complex materials, the bond dissociation energies (BDEs) is considered as an alternative metric. BDEs offer a way to estimate the association and disassociation energies, as well as the relative stabilities of template and product NPs [44,125,139,140]. Specifically, the BDE of a generic MX compound is commonly defined as the standard enthalpy of the process of dissociation of a diatomic molecule, regardless of the ions ordering:

In contrast to ΔH_{latt} , BDEs are not inherently tied to a specific crystal structure, making them applicable to materials with complex physical and chemical architectures. BDEs have been shown to be useful in comparing the relative stabilities of compounds, often yielding consistent results with those obtained from ΔH_{latt} . For instance, the bond dissociation energies (BDEs) of Zn–O and Zn–S bonds are 360 kJ/mol and 427 kJ/mol, respectively, which could be utilized as metrics to assess the feasibility of the sulfidation process of ZnO NCs [75,141]. Furthermore, BDEs can be obtained through both thermochemical and spectroscopy methods. However, it is crucial to emphasize that bond dissociation energies primarily represent the relative change in free energy between two chemical states of a substance. They do not fully encapsulate the totality of ΔG that determine the reaction spontaneity of a material. Therefore, in order to obtain a rigorous and comprehensive understanding of the anion-driven synthesis process, it is imperative to consider BDEs in conjunction with other relevant parameters and experimental data.

While lattice energies have hitherto been the primary focus, it is crucial to recognize that NCs possess a significant fraction of atoms located on their surface. Furthermore, anion-driven synthesis usually alters the NP architecture, thereby modifying the surface-to-bulk atomic ratio. Therefore, the surface energy component must be taken into account when considering anion-driven synthesis. Unfortunately, a rough estimation of the surface energy contribution of the anion-driven synthesis remains extremely challenging, because the surface area of NPs in anion-driven synthesis depends on many variables, such as the types of ligands decorating the NC surfaces and the chemical and structural nature of the NP facets. Therefore, to enhance our understanding of the thermodynamic mechanisms of anion-driven synthesis and improve predictions including surface energy and the solvation/desolvation energy, we endeavor to consider additional factors in the subsequent sections, such as the hard and soft acids and bases (HSAB) theory and solubility product constants.

Hard and soft acids and bases theory

As previously emphasized, the total free energy of anion-driven synthesis cannot be merely determined by the energy of association and dissociation of the product and template NCs. In fact, the solvation and desolvation energies can serve as significant driving forces of anion-driven synthesis in a colloidal system. Therefore, a prudent selection of ligands and solvents is crucial for controlling the anion-driven synthesis. Specifically, adjusting the solubility of the outgoing anions (facilitating their release from the anionic reagent into the template NCs) and the ingoing anions (captured by the ligands or dissolved in the solvents) can be achieved through a careful choice of ligands and solvents.

Here, the qualitative concept of hard and soft acids and bases (HSAB), which relies on the concept of chemical hardness and softness of Lewis acids (A) and bases (B) plays the most important role in the solution and desolvation processes of anion-driven synthesis [142–147]. The word “hardness” refers to the resistance to deformation or change, and this parameter is primarily determined by the electronic configuration and electronegativity of

the donor/acceptor atom. Specifically, Lewis bases are generally divided into two categories, hard and soft bases. Soft bases manifest a donor atom of high polarizability and low electronegativity that can be easily oxidized (such as I^- , SCN^- , CN^- , CO , H^- , $S_2O_3^{2-}$, C_2H_4 , RS^- and S^{2-}). In contrast, hard bases have donor atoms of low polarizability and high electronegativity that can be easily reduced (such as F^- , OH^- , H_2O , NH_3 , O^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} , SO_4^{2-} , CO_3^{2-} and ROH). Similarly, Lewis acids can also be divided into soft acids that having acceptor atoms of low positive charge and large size (Ti^{4+} , Fe^{3+} and Cr^{3+}), and hard acids with acceptor atoms having high positive charge and small size (Cu^+ , Ag^+ , Hg^{2+} and Pt^{2+}).

To better understand the HSAB theory, Parr and Pearson introduced the concept of absolute hardness (η) in 1983 [142]. Here, η is normally designed to quantitatively compare the hardness of acids and bases. When analyzing Lewis bases (Table 3), two features for anion-driven synthesis can be inferred from the listed η values:

- (1) In general, molecules with high electronegativity, such as F, O or N, tend to exhibit stronger hardness due to their negative electron affinity. This indicates their resistance to electronic deformation and polarization;
- (2) In contrast, molecules with donor atoms, such as Cl, S and P, have larger atomic size and reduced hardness.

The hardness of a species is also a quantitative indicator for evaluating the affinity between metal cations and solvents or ligands. This affinity can serve as a powerful tool to predict and optimize anion-driven synthesis processes. The HSAB theory encompasses four fundamental principles:

- (1) Hard acids prefer to associate with hard bases to form ionic complexes [44]. This interaction is characterized by the electrostatic attraction between the positively charged hard acid and the negatively charged hard base.

TABLE 3

Experimental absolute hardness, η , of typical cations and ligands or bases that can be used in anion-driven synthesis (from [153]).

Acid	η	Base	η
Al^{3+}	45.77	H_2O	9.5
Ga^{3+}	17	CH_3F	9.4
In^{3+}	13	NH_3	8.2
Fe^{3+}	12.08	$(CH_3)_2O$	8
Zn^{2+}	10.88	CH_3Cl	7.5
Cd^{2+}	10.29	CH_3CN	7.5
Ge^{2+}	9.15	HCO_2CH_3	6.4
Mn^{2+}	9.02	$(CH_3)_3N$	6.3
Co^{3+}	8.9	$HCONH_2$	6.2
Pb^{2+}	8.46	CH_2O	6.2
Au^{3+}	8.4	$(CH_3)_2S$	6
Cu^{2+}	8.27	PH_3	6
Co^{2+}	8.22	$(CH_3)_3P$	5.9
Pt^{2+}	8	DMF	5.8
Sn^{2+}	7.94	CH_3CHO	5.7
Hg^{2+}	7.7	CH_3COCH_3	5.6
Fe^{2+}	7.24	C_5H_5N	5
Ag^+	6.96	C_6H_5OH	4.8
Pd^{2+}	6.75	C_6H_5SH	4.6
Cu^+	6.28	$C_6H_5NH_2$	4.4

- (2) Soft acids prefer to bind to soft bases to form more covalent complexes. Upon interaction between soft acids and soft bases, their orbitals undergo overlap, leading to the formation of stable bonds characterized by lower energy. This phenomenon can be attributed to the diffuse nature of the orbitals associated with soft acids and soft bases, facilitating their effective overlap.
- (3) Chemical transformation in anion-driven synthesis tend to favor the formation of compounds composed of hard-hard or soft-soft pairs.
- (4) Hard solvents favor the dissolution of hard solutes, while soft solvents favor the dissolution of soft solutes. For instance, many organic compounds are not soluble in water because water is a hard base.

Overall, the HSAB theory is a very helpful tool to rationalize the selection of specific anionic reagents, solvents, and ligands in anion-driven synthesis. In the context of NC synthesis, this theory aids in predicting and optimizing interactions between reactants to favor desired product formation. For instance, if the template NCs contain hard Lewis base anions like O^{2-} , and soft acid cations such as Cu^+ , Pb^{2+} , Ag^+ , or Fe^{2+} , they will be easily reacted with anions such as S, Se, Te, P, and N that are soft bases [49,75,148]. According to the HSAB principle, these soft base anions will tend to form stronger bonds with the soft acid cations in the template NCs, resulting in their substitution for the original hard base anions. Conversely, when hard acids are employed as cation sources, anions acting as soft bases are spontaneously exchanged with anions exhibiting harder base characteristics. This exchangeability is governed by the relative hardness/softness of the acids and bases involved, thus facilitating the synthesis of NCs with tailored compositions and properties [149,150].

Furthermore, the HSAB theory is instrumental in estimating and fine-tuning the conditions for anion-driven NC synthesis. For instance, (1) Dichlorobenzene and oleylamine can be utilized to immobilize the cations and restrict their diffusion rates, thereby favoring anion-driven growth mechanisms. By modulating the cation diffusion, these solvents and ligands enable a more controlled synthesis process; [151,152] (2) Poly(vinylpyrrolidone) (PVP) can be combined with Cu_2O NCs to slow down the diffusion of sulfur dianions (S^{2-}) to the Cu_2O surface [49]. This diffusion control is crucial for achieving NCs with desired morphologies and properties. Table 3 provides an overview of the relative hardness of various metal cations, ligands, and solvents that are commonly employed in anion-driven NC synthesis. This information serves as a guide for selecting appropriate reactants and conditions based on the HSAB principle.

Additionally, hardness [153] is a guideline for rationally selecting the ligands and solvents, toward optimizing the targeted chemical transformation as reported by Cheon et al., [92] Manna et al. [44] and Ha et al. [154].

Solubility product constants

Different from HSAB theory, the solubility product constants (K_{sp}) provide a quantitative approach to predict the anion-driven synthesis direction of colloidal NCs [151–155]. The K_{sp} value reflects the extent to which a solid compound can dissolve

in a solvent at equilibrium, determined by the concentration of the dissolved ions [43,155]. This equilibrium constant is critical in understanding the relative stability of various metal chalcogenides and metal oxides during the synthesis process. As shown in Table 4, the K_{sp} values of selected metal chalcogenides and metal oxides can be used to guide the design of synthesis conditions, favoring the formation of desired NCs.

For anion-driven synthesis of NCs, the value of K_{sp} serves as a critical parameter for predicting the aqueous solubility of crystals under various conditions. Specifically, K_{sp} quantifies the thermodynamic equilibrium between the solid phase and its dissolved ions in a solution. Additionally, the concept of solubility product constants is similar to solubility, both of which can indicate the solubility of electrolytes. For instance, when water is used as a solvent in the reaction, the K_{sp} value of the template NCs and the expected products can predict the thermodynamic feasibility [43,155]. However, it is important to note that there are distinctions between the K_{sp} and solubility:

- (1) K_{sp} is the product of the ion concentration for the insoluble solid phase when the corresponding ions reach equilibrium that depends only on temperature. It is an intrinsic property of the solid.
- (2) Solubility, on the other hand, is influenced by a broader range of factors, including but not limited to temperature, system composition, pH changes, and the formation of complexes.

Here, K_{sp} of NCs can be determined experimentally by directly measuring the concentrations of the constituent ions. Alternatively, it can also be calculated from the standard Gibbs energies ($\Delta_f G^\circ$) of the various species involved [44]. Specifically, we define $K_{sp} = [M^+][X^-]$ (as mentioned previously, a product of ion concentration powers, the power of each ion concentration is equal to the stoichiometric number of the chemical formula) as the equilibrium constant for the reaction:

TABLE 4

Solubility product constants (K_{sp}) at 25 °C of various metal oxides and chalcogenides that can be used in anion-driven synthesis (from reference [156]).

Compound	E = O (K_{sp})	E = S (K_{sp})	E = Se (K_{sp})
Ag ₂ E	2.0×10^{-8}	6.3×10^{-50}	2×10^{-64}
ZnE	1.2×10^{-17}	1.6×10^{-24}	3.6×10^{-26}
CoE	5.92×10^{-15}	1.6×10^{-23}	N.A.
HgE	$2.0 \times 10^{-23.7}$	1.6×10^{-52}	4×10^{-59}
SnE	1.4×10^{-28}	1×10^{-25}	5×10^{-34}
Bi ₂ E ₃	$4.0 \times 10^{-30.4}$	1×10^{-97}	1×10^{-130}
Cu ₂ E	5×10^{-8}	2.5×10^{-48}	1.58×10^{-61}
SbE	1.6×10^{-14}	2×10^{-26}	N.A.
NiE	2.0×10^{-16}	3.2×10^{-19}	2×10^{-26}
In ₂ E ₃	1.3×10^{-29}	5.7×10^{-74}	N.A.
CuE	2.2×10^{-19}	6.3×10^{-36}	2×10^{-40}
CdE	2.5×10^{-14}	8×10^{-27}	4×10^{-35}
PbE	1.6×10^{-15}	8×10^{-28}	1×10^{-37}
PtE	1.0×10^{-67}	9.9×10^{-74}	N.A.
FeE	1.6×10^{-15}	6.3×10^{-18}	N.A.

Here, MX is the soluble NC, M^+ and X^- are the cation and anion produced in the solution by the dissociation of MX NCs. The Gibbs energy change of each ion at their standard states can be written as

$$\Delta_f G^\circ = \Delta_f G^\circ(M^+, aq) + \Delta_f G^\circ(X^-, aq) - \Delta_f G^\circ(MX, s) \quad (6)$$

The solubility product constant and Gibbs energy change can be converted from the equation:

$$\ln K_{sp} = \Delta_f G^\circ / RT \quad (7)$$

A rough judgment of the thermodynamic feasibility of anion-driven synthesis can be obtained by comparing the K_{sp} values of the starting and final materials. From this comparison, it follows that NCs with a relatively high K_{sp} can spontaneously transform into NCs with a lower K_{sp} [43,47,49,157–160]. For instance, Xia et al. demonstrated the possibility of producing CoS and NiS via a facile sulfidation reaction using metal oxide template NCs and Na₂S as sulfur source. Herein the K_{sp} values for Co₃O₄, Co(OH)₂, NiO, Ni(OH)₂, CoS and NiS are about 3.1×10^{-18} , 5.9×10^{-15} , 1.5×10^{-17} , 5.5×10^{-16} , 3×10^{-26} and 1.3×10^{-25} , respectively [160–162]. The possible involved reactions can be expressed as follows.

Hence, the Co(OH)₂, NiO and Ni(OH)₂ NCs can spontaneously transform into CoS and NiS NCs with a lower K_{sp} via sulfidation reaction.

In parallel, Xiong et al. reported that colloidal spherical Cu₂O NCs can be used as template NCs to synthesize multi-shelled Cu₂S hollow nanosphere via successive sulfurating reactions. This anion-driven synthesis is thermodynamically favorable because the K_{sp} of Cu₂S is much smaller (2.5×10^{-48} , 18 °C) than that of Cu₂O (2.0×10^{-15} , 25 °C) [49]. Meanwhile, Jiao et al. reported that Cu₂O NPs suspended in a Na₂S solution could be immediately converted into Cu₂O/Cu₂S core-shell structures because of the very small K_{sp} of Cu₂S (10^{-48}) [29]. This anion-driven synthesis can be formulated as shown in reactions (13) and (14):

Similarly, Cao et al. reported that Cu_{2-x}Se NPs could be formed when Se²⁻ ions were added to the mixture containing Cu₂O NP by a dissolution process because the Cu_{2-x}Se has much lower solubility than Cu₂O in aqueous alkaline solutions [34].

Here, it is crucial to highlight that the solubility data of metallic compounds in common polar solvents is often lacking in the literature. Specifically, K_{sp} values of numerous metallic compound crystals, including metal selenides, most metal tellurides, and particularly ternary materials like NiCo₂O₄, MnFe₂O₄, and

FePtCo, are not readily accessible. In the absence of such data, Trizio et al. have made inferences regarding the solubility of these compounds based on the ionic radii and lattice enthalpies [44]. For instance, they inferred that the metal tellurides have lower K_{sp} values than the corresponding selenides (and sulfides) by considering that $r_{S^{2-}}^2 < r_{Se^{2-}}^2 < r_{Te^{2-}}^2$, and $\Delta H_{latt}(M_xS_y) > \Delta H_{latt}(M_xSe_y) > \Delta H_{latt}(M_xTe_y)$ [156].

To promote the anion-driven synthesis, [49,163] Moon et al. have reported strategies for adjusting the actual solubility of materials [163,164]. These strategies involve several factors:

- (1) Addition of a common ion of reactant. This can influence the equilibrium and solubility of the desired product.
- (2) Selective addition of product ions and non-common salts. This aims to selectively increase the solubility of the template anions, thereby promoting the desired chemical transformation.
- (3) Temperature modulation. By changing the temperature, one can selectively alter the solubility of different components, favoring specific reactions.
- (4) Complexation of ligands and ions. This can effectively alter the thermodynamics of a reaction, converting an unfavorable one into a favorable one. For instance, the selective increase in the solubility of the product salt can facilitate the chemical reactions, [49,163] as it shifts the equilibrium in favor of the desired product. By employing these strategies, more control over the synthesis process can be accessed and therefore desired NC structures and compositions can be achieved.

Reaction kinetics

Thermodynamics alone does not fully determine the feasibility of anion-driven synthesis. Instead, kinetic factors, such as ions diffusivity and activation energy barriers, also play a key role in determining the process viability and the nature of the final products, including size, shape, composition, and structure. Recently, notable progress in the understanding of the reaction kinetics of NC anion-driven synthesis has been reported [89,165–168]. However, several aspects remain to be elucidated and predicted in the context of the processes taking place, when a template NC is exposed to a solution that contains potential guest anions:

- (1) Anion diffusion mechanisms. Anions can diffuse inside the lattices of the template NC either via an interstitial- or a vacancy-assisted mechanism. While the latter is the main anion diffusion route owing to their relatively large size, the exact diffusion mechanisms are still unclear in many cases [75,101,169].
- (2) Penetration depth of anions. When diffusing, anions can either penetrate the whole template NC or just the surface layers, which is potentially dependent on the relative solubility of the template and reacting anions [28,75,151]. This dependence requires further investigation.
- (3) Controllable morphology creation. The question of how to controllably create hollow or solid morphologies through modulation of anion-driven synthesis kinetics remains an open challenge. Further research is needed to address this issue.

In most cases, the fast replacement of anions from metal compound NCs (type 2 anion-driven synthesis) or the entry of anions on metal template NCs (type 1 anion-driven synthesis) can rapidly nucleate the product phase. During this initial step, the template anions (type 2) or some metal cations (type 1) are expelled from the template NCs through an out-diffusion mechanism, then solvated by the ligand molecules [44]. The region zone where the anion-driven synthesis occurs, can include the whole surface of the NC or mere a fraction of the NCs. (1) When the transformation region covers the entire surface of the NCs, the resulting nanostructure is typically categorized as a yolk-shell, solid, urchin or hollow nanostructure. The specific nanostructure attained is primarily dictated by the completion status of the reaction, which may be influenced by kinetic or thermodynamic limitations, or by a limited supply of reactant. Additionally, the diffusivity of the template and reacting ions, as well as the volume change associated with the anion-driven synthesis, play crucial roles in determining the final nanostructure [170]. (2) When the transformation region is confined to specific sites on the NCs surface, various heterostructured NPs (e.g., heterodimer) or asymmetric NPs can be prepared via anion-driven synthesis [171–175]. Once the initial reaction zone is established, the subsequent synthesis process, driven by anions, progresses towards the as-yet unreacted areas of the template NC via solid-state ion diffusion. This mechanism will be further elaborated in the subsequent section. It should be noted that anions coming in and out of the crystal framework tend to destroy the lattice structure, potentially resulting in products with reduced crystallinity or significant morphological changes [31,40,45,50,68,176]. In both cases, the diversity of ions transfer rate can significantly influence the resulting NP geometries. This diversity in transfer rates, which can be attributed to various factors such as ion species, concentration gradients, and surface energetics, leads to variations in the growth of the NPs. The impact of these diverse transfer rates on NP geometries will be further analyzed and discussed in detail in Section ‘**Unique nanostructures**’.

Solid-state diffusion and the Kirkendall effect

In most cases, solid-state diffusion is the rate-limiting process in anion-driven synthesis and strongly influences the product morphology and composition [49,68,83,97,149,177–179]. Typically, the solid-state diffusion involved in the anion-driven synthesis comprises both the inward diffusion of new anions and the outward diffusion of template cations. The diffusion rate of anions and cations are influenced by the presence of defects such as vacancies (even on the surface), impurities, dislocations, stacking faults, and possible grain boundaries inside the NCs [180–183]. Furthermore, the relative concentration of anions and cations plays a crucial role in determining the solid-state-diffusion process [67,83].

During anion-driven synthesis, the relative diffusion rates of anions and cations determine the formation of distinct NP geometries. A noteworthy scenario arises when the reaction zone encompasses the entire NC surface, and the diffusion of template ions through the growing shell surpasses the diffusion of the reactant ions. In such a case, the anion-driven synthesis occurs predominantly at the interphase between the NCs and the solvent, resulting in the formation of yolk-shell or hollow NCs, depending whether the reaction is kinetically limited. This

observed phenomenon is related to the Kirkendall effect, which was originally described by E. Kirkendall in 1947 for macroscopic systems and refers to the phenomenon of diffusion-induced void formation [184]. In 2004, Yin et al. reported that this effect is a specific mechanism to produce hollow NPs, and exemplified it with the formation of hollow CoSe NPs from the selenization of Co NPs [68]. Since this seminal work, this mechanism has been extensively explored and reported in numerous studies for the production of a wide variety of hollow NPs [22,31,34,35,67,68,70,71,83,97,101,133,149,151,185–188].

The Kirkendall effect specifically refers to the differential diffusion rates of species in a compound, leading to the formation of voids, while solid-state diffusion can occur without such phenomena. As shown in Fig. 1a, Wang et al. [67] schematizes the Kirkendall effect between two phases (A and B). Herein, the solid-state diffusion of A into B (J_A) through the growing AB is faster than that of B into A (J_B) through the growing AB, simultaneously, the unequal material flow is accompanied by the diffusion of vacancy (J_V). As shown in Fig. 1b, a layer of AB compound forms when an anion source (in the gas or solution phase) reacts with phase A (template NCs). However, this compound layer can

hinder the conversion of the core material (A) into the shell (AB). Fortunately, as the temperature increases, the ions or atoms passing through the interface continuously can promote further anion-driven synthesis. Notably, the condensation of vacancies can generate a void or gaps on the side of the phase with faster diffusion (corresponding to component A in Fig. 1b) [185]. These gaps generally act as the nuclei for further coagulation of the supersaturated vacancies, leading to the emergence and expansion of void near the interface. During the evolution of the voids, as shown in Fig. 1c, bridges between the shell and core can form (Fig. 1c, e) when the diffusion rate of core material is faster than that of shell material ($J_{\text{core}} > J_{\text{shell}}$). Under these conditions, the outward diffusion of atoms or ions can be transferred from the core material to the shell-liquid interface through the shell material, and the chemical composition of bridge is same as the core material. The bridges will persist until the core is completely consumed and a hollow structure finally forms (Fig. 1c, f). Here, we present a typical example of the formation of a hollow structure through anion-driven synthesis utilizing the Kirkendall effect: the oxidation, sulfation, or selenization of metal cobalt (Co) NPs (Fig. 1c–f) [68,83]. Furthermore, this anion-driven synthesis

FIG. 1

The Kirkendall effect. (a,b) Schematic illustration of a nonequilibrium lattice diffusion at the interface in bulk phase by Kirkendall effect. (c) Schematic illustration of nanoscale Kirkendall effect for the formation of hollow NCs. Reproduced with permission [67]. Copyright 2012, American Chemical Society. (d–f) The evolution of CoSe hollow shells. Reproduced with permission [68]. Copyright 2004 American Association for the Advancement of Science. (g) HRTEM and SPED of SC-Ag NP, SC-Ag₂Se NPs with hollow core; and schematic diagram of different atom diffusion paths (middle). Reproduced with permission [105]. Copyright 2007, Nature Publishing Group. (i) Proposed indirect exchange mechanism of O diffusion in the ϵ -Co phase takes place over three steps. (j) TEM and HRTEM images of ϵ -Co, CoO, Co₃O₄ NP. Reproduced with permission [101]. Copyright 2013, American Chemical Society.

approach, driven by Kirkendall effect, can be extended to prepare hollow structures composed of various components, such as metal oxides, sulfides, selenides, tellurides, nitrides, phosphides, etc.

This versatility demonstrates the broad applicability of this technique in the synthesis of complex nanostructures. Moreover, from the reaction of Cd NCs with different chalcogenide precursor types and concentrations, Cabot et al. observed that the mere differential diffusivity of core (A) and reactant ions (B) through the growing shell (AB) is not the sole parameter determining the formation of hollow or solid NPs. Instead, the final morphology of the AB NCs obtained through anion-driven synthesis of A with B depends on these three main parameters: [170].

- (1) The different self-diffusion rates of A and B through the AB shell.
- (2) The reaction probabilities between A and B at each interface.
- (3) The frequency of interaction between B ions and the NCs, which is determined by the concentration and diffusivity of B in the reaction solution.

Furthermore, the various combinations of these parameters lead to four distinct shell growth regimes:

- (1) The self-diffusion limited regime, where hollow AB NCs form only when the self-diffusion rate of A is higher than that of B in the AB shell. This phenomenon was observed in the reaction of Cd with higher concentrations of DCB:S.
- (2) The preferential reaction regime, resulting in solid NCs when the reaction probability at the A/AB interface is higher than that at the AB/solution interface. This is the case for the reaction of Cd with TOP = S (TOP: Tri-n-octylphosphine).
- (3) The reaction-rate-limited regime, where low reaction probabilities allow the ions to diffuse through the shell and react simultaneously at both interfaces to produce solid NCs. This scenario was observed in the reaction of Cd with low concentrations of TOP = Se.
- (4) The collision-limited regime, where low interaction frequencies but high reaction probabilities allow A ions to diffuse and accumulate at the AB/solution interface, preventing B ions to diffuse inside.

Moreover, to further explore the mechanism of the formation of products' structure by solid-state diffusion, Tang et al. analyzed the relationship between the ion diffusion and the final morphology by changing the crystallinity of A (template NCs) [105]. Specifically, the single-crystal (CS) Ag NCs can form hollow (H) Ag₂Se NCs by the Kirkendall effect (Fig. 1g). During this anion-driven synthesis, the silver atoms diffuse faster than the selenium atoms, resulting in vacancy formation and condensation into holes. Nevertheless, since the diffusion of atoms along the defects (in multiple twinned NC) allows selenium to diffuse into silver (as shown in Fig. 1h), the multiply twinned (MT) Ag NCs can transform into solid homogeneous (CS) Ag₂Se NCs by anion-driven synthesis.

Similarly, Robinson et al. suggested that the single-crystalline ϵ -Co NPs could transform into polycrystalline CoO (Fig. 1j) NPs

via Kirkendall hollowing [101]. The first step of the hollowing process is an indirect exchange mechanism of O through interstitial O and vacancies of type I Co sites of the ϵ -Co phase, which has a lower energy barrier than a vacancy-mediated diffusion of O. Specifically: (1) O atom in a vacant type I site diffuses to an adjacent interstitial site; (2) Neighboring type I Co atom diffuses to site vacated by O; (3) O hops back into the empty type I site (Fig. 1i). Then, the hollow NP could be formed due to the CoO phase being established and the rate of Co diffusing outward is faster than that of O diffusing inward. Moreover, it is worth noting that the morphology and structure of CoO to Co₃O₄ NPs does not change significantly during the further oxidation (Fig. 1j) because the diffusion of O ions is easier than in the initial oxidation.

Additional studies detailing the mechanism of the nanoscale Kirkendall effect have been reported. For instance, Fan et al. proposed that the initial nucleation and formation of interior pores are induced by the Kirkendall effect, and the surface diffusion of the core atoms (the fast-diffusing species) along the pore surface might be the main mechanism of the enlargement of the interior pores [189]. Furthermore, different from the diffusivity difference which could influence the product architecture, Tracy et al. reported that the size of the core material could also influence the architecture of NPs prepared by anion-driven synthesis via the Kirkendall effect. When the size is large, the self-diffusion will not be fast enough to cause the voids or vacancies to combine into a single void [133].

These investigations revealed some important aspects of the Kirkendall effect to promote the understanding of solid-state diffusion in anion-driven synthesis. While metal NCs (type 1 anion-driven synthesis) have been extensively studied, it is known that the anion-driven synthesis of metal oxide NCs (type 2 anion-driven synthesis) can also yield hollow structures through the Kirkendall effect [43,45,75,77,78,141,190–192]. However, the precise mechanism of ion diffusion and structure evolution based on the nanoscale Kirkendall effect remain poorly understood in these systems. To address this gap, the combination of multiple experimental characterization techniques is anticipated to provide a more comprehensive and detailed understanding of this anion-driven synthesis process. Moreover, the combination of experimental methods with computational simulations has the potential to offer deeper insights into the phenomena, and predict the NP architectures obtained through type 2 anion-driven synthesis involving the Kirkendall effect.

Unlike the oxidation of Co, Cu or Al, Nakamura et al. reported that the oxidation of Pb NPs only forms solid PbO NPs, [193] as the diffusivity difference ($D_{\text{Pb}} < D_{\text{O}}$) in PbO does not permit the formation of vacancy clusters. Specifically, the fast inward oxygen diffusion through the oxide layer is the rate-limiting process. As a further example, Lim et al. reported on the sulfidation of metal oxide NCs to produce solid metal sulfide NPs, and demonstrated the Non-Kirkendall effect [75]. Interestingly, to avoid (or circumvent) the Kirkendall effect during anion-driven synthesis, (Z)-N-trimethylsilyloctadec-9-en-1-amine (TMS-ODA) was utilized as an oxygen-extracting reagent to preserve the original nanostructure and morphology of metal oxide. In this process, the amine group in TMS-ODA facilitates nitrogen to coordinate with Fe^{2+/3+}, as the Si–N bond (355 kJ/mol) is weaker than the

Si—O bond (452 kJ/mol). Additionally, the TMS group binds to O^{2-} on the NC surface [75,194]. As TMS-ODA is added, oxygen atoms on the NC surface is activated and eliminated with the formation of bis- (trimethylsilyl) oxide (TMS_2O), leaving oxygen vacancies (V_O) (Fig. 2a,b). Specifically, the mechanism of this process involves four steps: (1) The amine group in TMS-ODA coordinates to $Fe^{2+/3+}$ with Si—O bond formation via chelation-assisted σ -bond metathesis (Fig. 2b(i,ii)) [75,195,196]; (2) Upon the coordination of another TMS-ODA to an adjacent $Fe^{2+/3+}$, TMS_2O is formed and eliminated with the generation of V_O (Fig. 2b(iii,iv)); (3) The addition of H_2S to V_O generates Fe—S bond (Fig. 2c(i,ii)); (4) The formation of the Fe—S bond and the elimination of oleylamine (Fig. 2c(iii,iv)).

Herein, the diffusion kinetics of (incoming) S^{2-} from the NCs surface to the NCs inside (via interstitials) can be simulated by using finite element calculations (a transport model in which the S^{2-} diffusivity (D_S) is assumed as a constant) [197]. The concentration of S^{2-} (C_S) in NCs was estimated using Fick's second law: (Fig. 2d):

$$\frac{\partial C_S}{\partial t} = D_S \frac{\partial^2 C_S}{\partial r^2} \quad (15)$$

Here, C_S is the concentration of incoming S^{2-} (mol/m³), D_S is the S^{2-} diffusivity (cm²/s), t is the time (s), and r is radius of NCs (6.5×10^{-9} m). It is worth noting that the simulated D_S (2.0×10^{-16} cm²/s) is close to the typical cation-diffusivity for iron (Fe^{2+}) oxides [198–200] and matches well with the experimental results (Fig. 2(e,f)). Typically, in Kirkendall-based anion-driven synthesis, the calculated thickness of the inward growing shell (in cross-section profiles of S^{2-} concentration distributions with D_S of 1.3×10^{-18} cm²/s) is consistent with the shell thickness of products. The E_a (activation energy) for S^{2-} diffusion is 294 ± 15 kJ/mol in the absence of (Z)-N-trimethylsilyloctadec-9-en-1-amine TMS-ODA, which is similar to the typical anion-diffusion E_a of 295 kJ/mol for iron oxides [201–203] (Fig. 2g, blue).

In contrast, in the presence of TMS-ODA, E_a (S^{2-} diffusion) is 188 ± 12 kJ/mol (Fig. 2g, red), which is close to the cation-diffusion activation energy (135 kJ/mol) of iron oxide [202,204]. In addition, these two observations also agree with the calculated values: (1) The decrease in the volume of starting NCs is directly proportional to the $t^{3/2}$; (2) The starting NCs of Fe_3O_4 converted to 70 % of Fe_3S_4 only within 2 min. (Fig. 2h).

This is an example of a tuned anion-driven synthesis to produce solid metal oxide NCs avoiding the Kirkendall void formation. This mechanism may provide insights for engineering other solid NCs via anion-driven synthesis. Additionally, Bothe et al. proposed a model to illustrate the diffusion of cations exclusively mediated by interstitial lattice sites based on a kick-out mechanism to remove individual ions from lattice sites without the formation of vacancies [205]. Numerous anion-driven synthesis reactions are inherently accompanied by the Kirkendall effect, which is often challenging to mitigate. Therefore, to achieve precise control over the morphology and structure of the resulting NCs, including the deliberate fabrication of solid and hollow NPs, a thorough understanding of the mechanisms

governing solid-state diffusion and the Kirkendall effect is crucial [75,105].

Cabrera-Mott theory of anion-driven synthesis

In our exploration of solid-state diffusion and the Kirkendall effect, we have observed deviations from these theories in certain cases, particularly in metal oxidation where the existence of a critical oxide size plays a crucial role. Specifically, in the case of the oxidation of small Al and Zn NPs (Al NPs < 8 nm, Zn NPs < 20 nm), generally at the initial oxidation stage, the rapid outward diffusion of metal cations leads to the formation of amorphous hollow NPs. However, larger hollow Al_2O_3 NPs (>100 nm) could not be prepared by thermal oxidation because the further growth of the oxide layer usually stops after the formation of an initial oxide layer. Most importantly, it is worth noting that the oxide shells formed on different sizes of starting NP (such as larger Al or Zn NPs) generally have the same thickness. These phenomena are related to the following aspects:

- (1) The onset of oxidation kinetics does not depend on the NP size;
- (2) The Zn or Al cations with low mobility in their oxide layer can prevent the further growth of ZnO or Al_2O_3 on the larger Zn or Al NPs [67].

Moreover, the very rapid initial oxidation reaction at low temperatures cannot be explained by thermal-activated solid-state diffusion in most cases. For instance, the hollowing of Zn or Al NPs perhaps should be explained by other theories.

Given these considerations, a physical picture to illustrate the diffusion of metal ions and oxygen during the initial stage of the low-temperature oxidation process was provided by Cabrera and Mott, [31,67,121,206–212] which was later generalized by Fromhold and Cook [165,166]. The Cabrera-Mott model deals with the kinetics of metal oxidation and it was initially developed to investigate the oxidation of flat metal layers rather than NPs [213]. The model was later modified to be applied to metal NCs by Kasemo [214]. The Cabrera-Mott theory assumes that oxygen atoms are firstly adsorbed on the oxide surface, subsequently, electrons can rapidly pass through the oxide layer by tunnelling, generating a built-in electric field within the thin metal oxide layer (Fig. 3a). Then, the resulting electric potential between the metal and the adsorbed oxygen can drive the diffusion of metal cations and the flow of oxygen through the oxide layer [89,121,122]. For further growth of the oxide shells, once an initial oxide layer of a certain thickness has formed, thermal activation of ion diffusion may become a necessity. Importantly, the Cabrera-Mott theory assumes that the rate-determining step in this process is the diffusion of metal cations from the core-shell interface to the exterior oxide surface, whereas the Kirkendall effect involves differential diffusion rates leading to the void formation. The crucial aspect of this theory is the hypothesis that metal electrons traverse through the thin oxide shell via tunnel effect, or come into the conductive band of oxide by thermionic emission. This conductive band is often equal to the O 2p energy level, and locates between the Fermi level of the metal and the valence level of the oxide [215]. Then, the absorbed atoms of oxygen can be ion-

FIG. 2

(a) Schematic illustrations of OER-assisted anion-driven synthesis with O^{2-} extraction followed by S^{2-} incorporation upon treatment with TMS-ODA and H_2S . (b) Reaction pathways for O^{2-} extraction by TMS-ODA. (c) S^{2-} incorporation via V_o . (d) Time-dependent HRTEM images of intermediates from $sc-Fe_3O_4$ to $amor-Fe_3S_4$. (e-f) Simulated spatial and temporal variability of the S^{2-} concentration distributions with $D_5 = 2.0 \times 10^{-16}$ cm²/s in cross-section and line profiles. (g) Plots of $\ln D_5$ vs $1000/T$ for the determination of E_a for incoming S^{2-} diffusion. (h) Changes in volume of Fe_3O_4 NCs. Reproduced with permission [75] Copyright 2020, American Chemical Society.

FIG. 3

(a) Oxidation of a metal NCs in an oxidizing environment. Dependence of the In_2O_3 thickness on NCs size (Schematic illustration of the Cabrera-Mott (CM) model). (b) Oxide thickness predicted to form on surface of spherical Al NPs. Reproduced with permission [121]. Copyright 2011, Elsevier. (c) Experimental In_2O_3 thickness and indium core diameter determined from TEM measurements. (d) Dependence of the In_2O_3 thickness on indium NCs size for room temperature oxidation, calculated using a modified Mott-Cabrera model for spherical NPs. Reproduced with permission [122]. Copyright 2012, American Chemical Society. (e) Schematic illustration of the proposed growth mechanism of Au NPs. Surface-oxidized Au NPs resulted in graphene shells. Reproduced with permission [210]. Copyright 2012, American Chemical Society. (f) Relative concentration of Ga^{3+} vs. total Ga as a function of time and thiolating species based on quantification of the Ga 3d peak. Reproduced with permission [215]. Copyright 2018, American Chemical Society.

ized by connecting with electrons, thus reducing the energetic barrier of metal ions diffusion toward the oxide-oxidizer interface and accelerating the anion-driven synthesis (Fig. 3a).

The equations describing the formation of a spherical oxide shell according to the Cabrera-Mott mechanism were presented by Dreizin and Ermoline [121]. Specifically, the rate of growth of the oxide thickness (L), according to the Cabrera-Mott model [121,206], is given by Eq. (16):

$$\frac{dL}{dt} = \Omega_{\text{ox}} n \nu \exp\left(-\frac{W}{kT}\right) \exp\left(\frac{qaE}{kT}\right) \quad (16)$$

Here, Ω_{ox} is the volume of oxide formed per diffusing ion, n is the number of ions per unit area in the position to jump over the rate-limiting energy barrier W , ν is the ionic attempt frequency of the jump, a is the distance between the energy barrier maximum and adjacent minimum, and E is the electric field in the oxide film ($E = \frac{\Phi_M}{L}$, Φ_M is the Mott potential).

However, these equations do not explicitly take into account the difference in the radius of core and oxide shell of NP when the shell thickness is not negligible compared to the core size. Specifically, the electric field in the spherical oxide layer cannot be accurately described solely by Eq. (17), as it is influenced by the ratio of the shell (r_2) to the core radius (r_1). Therefore, the equations should be modified to account for this ratio, as shown in the revised formulation Eq. (18):

$$\left(E = \frac{\Phi_M}{L}\right). \quad (17)$$

$$E = -\frac{\Phi_M}{L} \frac{r_2}{r_1}. \quad (18)$$

Taking into account the electric field correction, the following equation for the rate of oxide growth was obtained in Ref [214]:

$$\frac{dL}{dT} = u \exp\left(-\frac{qa\Phi_M}{kT} \frac{r_2}{r_1 L}\right) \quad (19)$$

where u is the rate of oxide growth in the absence of an electric field. As shown in Fig. 3a, diffusing ions originate from the core at radius r_1 (and move toward r_2), and this equation provides the rate of oxide thickness growth [121]. Furthermore, a more comprehensive equation considering both the electric field correction and the diffusion coefficients of the ions in the core and shell regions is given by Eq. (20):

$$\frac{dL}{dT} = [(\Omega_1 + \Omega_2) \frac{r_2}{r_1 L} - \Omega_1] n \nu \exp\left(-\frac{W}{kT}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{qa\Phi_M}{kT} \frac{r_2}{r_1 L}\right) \quad (20)$$

where Ω_1 and Ω_2 are the diffusion coefficients in the core and shell regions, respectively.

As shown in Fig. 3b, the Al NPs were considered to be oxidized at 500 K and the oxidation kinetics parameters considered in calculations were from Refs [121,216,217]: $n = 10 \text{ nm}^{-2}$, $\nu = 10^{12} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $a = 0.12 \text{ nm}$, $\Phi_M = 1.6 \text{ V}$, $W = 2.6 \text{ eV}$, $q = 3e$, $\Omega_2 = 0.023 \text{ nm}^3$ and $\Omega_1 = -0.0166 \text{ nm}^3$. Based on these parameters, we draw the following conclusions:

- (1) For small NCs, where the NCs radius becomes comparable to oxide shell thickness, the result calculation using Eq. (17) with the correction for electric field in the exponent Eq. (19) is significantly different from using Eq. (20).
- (2) In the case of larger NCs, about 10 nm or above, this discrepancy diminishes.
- (3) For very large NPs, exceeding than 100 nm, there is almost no difference between the oxide layer thicknesses calculated using Eq. (19) and the calculation using Eq. (17).

An earlier study has shown that the initial thickness of Fe NPs with different larger sizes generally can form an oxide shell with similar thickness (about 3 nm) under ambient conditions [218]. Here, the Cabrera-Mott theory is a useful tool to explain and predict the initial oxidation stage of NP at low temperatures. For instance, Sutter et al. reported that the size-dependent room-temperature oxidation of indium NPs aligns well with predictions for the Mott-Cabrera model by using TEM [122]. As given in Fig. 3c, the diameters of NCs significantly influence the structure of the resulting NCs. Specifically:

- (1) NPs with diameters less than 12 nm undergo completely oxidation (without a metal indium core) after being exposed to air.
- (2) Indium core diameter greater than 12 nm exhibit a core-shell structure, comprising c-In₂O₃ shell. As the NCs diameter increases, the indium core size also increases (Fig. 3c, orange), while the oxide thickness decreases slightly (Fig. 3c, brown)).
- (3) For NPs with diameters exceeding 12 nm, the thickness of oxide shell decreases to a uniform value of 3.5 to 4 nm, which is consistent with previous experiments on In films and large NCs [219,220].

Furthermore, the accelerated oxidation kinetics of NPs with high-curvature (small size) can be directly demonstrated [122]. For instance, the thickness of the oxide shell can be calculated by using the Cabrera-Mott model for various oxidation times (1000 min (green), 10000 min (red), 50000 min (blue)), as shown in Fig. 3d. The curves indicate that the oxidation of small NPs is still a continuous process even after a long time, which typically leads to an increase in oxide thickness. Most importantly, although this theory would predict a continuous increase in the critical size, the underlying assumptions are eventually no longer valid for large NCs.

Similar to In NPs, the thickness of the gold oxide shell formed by oxidation for Au NPs also follows the Cabrera-Mott model, and the thickness is independent of the stoichiometry of AuO_x [210]. As shown in Fig. 3e, the experimental shell thickness is extremely consistent with the Cabrera-Mott theory in the linear region between 15 min and 45 min, indicating the applicability of this theory to oxidized Au NPs within this duration range. Notably, the slope of this linear region represents the oxidation rate constant (Ω_{ox}), which allows for the theoretical calculation of the oxide shell thickness (a) using Eq (17.) [210,221]. Furthermore, the Cabrera-Mott theory holds significant value for metal alloys [215] or liquid metals [215,222–224] at room temperature. For instance, Farrell et al. utilized this model to develop a method for controlling the growth of oxide shells via using the sulfura-

tion of eutectic gallium–indium alloy (EGaIn, a room temperature liquid metal) NPs with sulfurated molecules [215]. As shown in Fig. 3f, the absorbed molecules such as 1-dodecanethiol (DDT), thiophenol (TP) and pentafluorothiophenol (FTP) could decrease the thickness of the oxide shell. Because the absorbed molecules being utilized to change the dynamic of O₂ absorption by occupying the surface site.

While metal oxidation may eventually advantageous to engineer more complex nanostructures, it often needs to be mitigated or completely avoided to fully exploit the intrinsic properties of pure metal NPs. From a NC synthesis mechanism perspective, it is crucial to control the oxidation process. To this end, Buonsanti et al. reported a thorough investigation into the oxidation behavior of Ga NPs, utilizing the well-established Cabrera-Mott theory as a theoretical framework. They found that certain ligands such as DDT and TOP, were the most suitable ligands to hinder the growth of gallium oxide [224]. The selection of these ligands was based on their ability to occupy surface sites on Ga NPs, thus reducing the availability of reactive sites for oxygen adsorption and subsequent oxidation.

However, in the cases of the thickness of the oxide shells is larger than 3 nm or when the react is conducted at sufficiently high temperatures, the Cabrera-Mott theory needs to be modified and updated due to the rapid electron tunneling and the diminished electric field as the shell grows [121]. To tackle these challenges, Fromhold et al. proposed a model for describing the oxidation process of spherical metal NPs in the low electric field, where the thickness of the oxide shell is relatively large (but below 100 nm) [165,166]. Furthermore, Valensi et al. developed a shrinking core model, which results in a more accurate rate law for oxidation at relatively high temperatures [31,225–228]. This model accounts for the changing dimensions of the metal core as oxidation progresses, leading to more precise predictions. In the presence of gaseous oxygen, the existence of an electrostatic potential has been experimentally investigated by measuring changes in the work function. Nevertheless, Ramírez et al. demonstrated that the work function measurements are insufficient to validate the Cabrera-Mott model. Instead, attention should be directed towards structural characteristics of the oxide band, such as the surface dipole energy barrier and band bending [229]. Another limitation of the Cabrera-Mott theory is that it does not consider the formation of grain boundaries in the product, and the defect concentration is assumed to remain constant throughout the oxidation process. This oversimplification may hinder its predictive capabilities for more complex oxidation phenomena. Therefore, there is still some room for a comprehensive modification of the model to overcome these limitations and potentially use this mechanism as a useful tool for predicting and interpreting the product of the initial stages of oxidation processes.

Anion-driven synthesis

Several strategies have been employed to forge colloidal NCs via anion-driven synthesis. Typically, these processes rely on the reaction between template metal or metal oxide NCs and anionic reagents to form new metal compound NCs, such as metal chalcogenide, metal pnictide, or metal halide. Although various

classification schemes are conceivable, for the purposes of this discussion, we will categorize anion-driven synthesis according to the anionic species used in the reaction (e.g., oxygen, sulfur, selenium, *etc.*). This classification allows for a systematic understanding of the underlying synthetic mechanisms and product properties (Table 5).

Oxidation

Oxidation processes are a common anion-driven synthesis wherein a metal NP undergoes a reaction with oxygen or oxygen-containing precursors, resulting in the formation of a metal oxide NP [230,241,295]. Although oxidation reactions of metallic NCs are often undesired due to their potential to deteriorate the structure and properties (such as plasmon resonance, optical, and magnetic properties), they offer a unique opportunity to produce metal oxide NCs with special structures (hollow, yolk-shell, *etc.*) tailored for various potential applications, such as (photo)catalysis and biological imaging [248,249,296,297]. As mentioned, some metal NCs are prone to oxidation even at low temperatures [22,87,90,91,101,133,151,223,224,231, 242,296–299]. To gain a comprehensive understanding of the oxidation mechanism, *in-situ* detection methods are commonly employed to monitor the oxidizing reaction of metal NPs [169,223,245,247,300,301]. Furthermore, the quest for uniformly sized NPs has garnered immense interest in both technological and scientific communities. This pursuit is driven by the fact that NPs with precise size and shape control exhibit superior properties compared to their polydisperse counterparts. Such NPs are crucial for applications that require high performance and reliability, such as catalysis, sensing, and imaging [302–304]. Notably, the synthesis of monodisperse NPs remains a challenge, especially when compared to solid-state processes. Solid-state methods, though widely used, often lack the precision required to produce NPs with uniform size and geometry. In contrast, the oxidation of colloidal metal NPs presents an effective route to overcome these limitations and fabricate metal oxide NPs with remarkable uniformity. During the oxidation process, the colloidal metal NPs undergo a controlled reaction with oxygen or oxygen-containing species, resulting in the formation of metal oxide NPs. The key advantage of this approach lies in the ability to fine-tune the reaction conditions, such as temperature, reactant concentration, and reaction time, to achieve precise control over the size, shape, and structure of the resulting oxide NPs.

In summary, the oxidation of colloidal metal NPs offers a promising route to synthesize monodisperse metal oxide NPs with precise size and shape control. However, the quality of the initial metal NPs remains a critical factor that must be carefully considered during the synthesis process. To optimize oxidation reactions, three important aspects need to be considered:

- (1) Although the oxidation of metals is kinetically facilitated, the reaction process typically involves a negative entropy change (ΔS) due to the consumption of gaseous oxygen.
- (2) Elevating the reaction temperature can promote oxidation.
- (3) Completely or partially hollow metal oxide structures are frequently obtained due to the difference of the diffusion rate between metal cations and O^{2-} anions.

Hollow oxide NPs are an important class of nanostructured materials, where the interior void and shell thickness can be precisely adjusted to produce multishell, yolk-shell, or fully hollow nanostructures. The synthesis of such hollow structures often relies on intricate chemical and physical processes that occur at the nanoscale. For instance, a colloidal solution of monodisperse CoO hollow NPs was prepared by bubbling air through the solution at 100 °C for 28 h, in which the colloidal cobalt NPs were fully oxidized [12]. Furthermore, Peng and Cabot [67,207] reported that the uniform-sized Fe_3O_4 hollow NPs can be synthesized by using an oxygen-transfer reagent, trimethylamine N-oxide (Me_3NO). Alternatively, they achieved a similar result by flowing a dry mixture of 20 % oxygen in argon at a rate of 20 mL/min through the colloidal solution. These approaches leverage the nanoscale Kirkendall effect, a well-known phenomenon in materials science, which refers to the different diffusion rates of species in a solid solution. As previously mentioned in Section 'Reaction kinetics', numerous examples of hollow nanostructures synthesized using the nanoscale Kirkendall effect have been extensively reported [67,68,70,97,133,187,260,264,305].

Herein, we will focus on two significant examples of the synthesis of iron oxide NPs to illustrate the oxidizing reaction process (Fig. 4a,j). Initially, it is well known that the first thin oxide layer will rapidly form on the iron surface upon exposure to oxygen. Consequently, the preparation of Fe NPs must be carried out under strictly air-free conditions. Additionally, the subsequent oxidation is substantially slow even if the Fe NPs are exposed to the atmosphere. Based on the Cabrera-Mott models (Section 'Cabrera-Mott theory of anion-driven synthesis'), it is estimated [218] that 600 years are required to grow a 4 nm thick oxide layer in an iron film [22,165,166,206]. These sequential stages of the oxidation process can be seen clearly in Fig. 4c-g. Specifically, Peng [88] and Cabot [22] reported that there are three steps in the Fe oxidation process:

- (1) In the initial stage, a thin and low-density region forms between the outer oxide layer and the initial iron NCs, as shown in Fig. 4a. Here, the coalescence of voids at the interface indicates an initial net outward material flow, consistent with the faster outward diffusion of iron cations compared to the inward flow of oxygen anions through the growing iron oxide shell [218];
- (2) As the oxidation reaction progresses, the oxide shell grows thicker, accompanied by the continuous appearance of iron atoms on the outermost surface through the amorphous oxide shell. These iron atoms then react with oxygen to facilitate oxidation;
- (3) As iron atoms diffuse outward sequentially, the vacancies that left by the cations will coalesce into a single central cavity. Eventually, for sufficiently small NCs, the spherical iron core that located in the center of the hollow NCs will disappear completely (Fig. 4i).

In fact, the phenomenon of vacancies left behind by the nanoscale Kirkendall effect is a clear signature of the outward diffusing of iron through the initial oxide shell [68,83]. As a result, we can conclude that the thickness of an initial oxide shell can

TABLE 5

Starting material, reactant, reaction temperature, final product composition, and architecture of different anion-driven synthesis.

Anion-driven synthesis	Starting material	Anionic reagent	Temperature	Product	Architecture
Oxidation	Cu	air	R.T., 150 °C	Cu ₂ O,[169,230]Cu-Cu ₂ O[193,231]	solid sphere, core-shell
		air	R.T., 200 °C	Cu-Cu ₂ O,[232,233]Cu ₂ O[232]	solid, core-shell, hollow
	Fe	air	R.T., 160 °C	Cu-Cu ₂ O,[234–236]Cu ₂ O[234]	core-shell, hollow
		air	50–300 °C	Cu ₂ O[237,238]	hollow, solid
		air	R.T.	Fe-FeO,[89]	core-shell, hollow
	Fe-Fe ₃ O ₄	O ₂ /Ar(1:4)	200–400 °C	Fe ₂ O ₃ ,[89]Fe ₃ O ₄ [218]	hollow, nanotube
			80 °C, 350 °C	Fe ₃ O ₄ ,[239]Fe ₂ O ₃ [239]	yolk-shell, hollow
		air	200 °C	Fe-Fe ₃ O ₄ ,[22]Fe ₃ O ₄ [22]	hollow
	Co	(CH ₃) ₃ NO	130 °C	γ-Fe ₂ O ₃ [240]	solid sphere
		(CH ₃) ₃ NO	210 °C	γ-Fe ₂ O ₃ [241]	yolk-shell, hollow
	ε-Co	air	400 °C	Fe-Fe ₃ O ₄ ,[88]Fe ₃ O ₄ [88]	nanowires, core-shell
			300 °C	Co ₃ O ₄ [91]	hollow
		O ₂	200 °C, 30 °C	CoO[242]	core-shell, hollow
		O ₂ /Ar(1:4)	182 °C	Co-CoO,[243]CoO[243,244]	hollow
		air	200 °C	CoO[68]	hollow
	Ni	air	300–400 °C	CoO,[101]Co ₃ O ₄ [101]	hollow
	Ag	air	300 °C	NiO[245,246]	yolk-shell
			plasma, X-ray beam	NiO[133]	nanoporous, nanotube
	Au-Co	air	400 °C,185 °C	Ag ₂ O[188,247]	nanowires, core-shell
				Au-Co ₃ O ₄ [90,248]	heterodimer
			Au _{0.83} Cu _{0.17} -Cu ₂ O [174]	core-shell	
Au _{0.46} Cu _{0.54}	air	1100 °C	AuCu-CuO [249]	core-shell, heterodimer	
		250 °C	Au-CuO [175]	hollow	
		250–600 °C		hollow	
FeCo	S = ODE, air	180–290 °C	Co _{1-x} Fe _x ⁽²⁺⁾ Fe ₂ ⁽³⁺⁾ O ₄ [250]	core-shell, heterodimer	
		R.T., 160 °C	In-In ₂ O ₃ [122,219]	core-shell, heterodimer	
Zn	air	110–150 °C	ZnO [251]	core-shell	
Pb	air	150 °C	PbO [193], Pb-PbO [177,252]	solid sphere, core-shell	
				core-shell, hollow	
Al	air	150 °C	Al-Al ₂ O ₃ , Al ₂ O ₃ [193]	solid sphere	
Cd	O ₂	200–300 °C	CdO [151]	hollow	
Bi	air	180–200 °C	Bi ₂ O ₃ [223]	core-shell	
Ga	air	R.T.	Ga-GaO _x [224]	core-shell	
MnO-SiO ₂ /M (M = none, Pt, Pd, and Ni)	air	500–800 °C	Mn ₃ O ₄ -SiO ₂ , Mn ₃ O ₄ -SiO ₂ /MO (M = Pt and Pd), and NiMn ₂ O ₄ -SiO ₂ [25]	core-shell	
CoO	air	240 °C	Co ₃ O ₄ [101]	hollow	
	Oleylamine	290 °C, 270 °C	Co [253]	nanoparallelepipeds	
Sulfuration	Fe ₃ O ₄	air	200 °C	γ-Fe ₂ O ₃ [240]	solid sphere
		S	182 °C	Co ₃ S ₄ [68,83],Co ₉ S ₈ [68,83]	hollow
	Co	S	450 °C	CoS ₂ [254]	nanosheet array
			297 °C	FePt-CoS ₂ [255]	core-shell
	FePt-Co	S	160 °C	NiS [256]	hollow
	SiO ₂ -Ni	Na ₂ S	R.T.	Au-Ag ₂ S _x [257]	core-shell
	Au-Ag	S	172 °C	Au-Ag ₂ S _{1-x} Se _x [257]	heterodimers
	AuCu	thioacetamide	280 °C, 220 °C	Au-Cu ₂ S[171]	heterodimers
			220 °C	Au-Cu _{1.8} S,[172] Au-CuS[172]	
	Pb	S, H ₂ S	300 °C, 145 °C	Pb-PbS [148,177]	core-shell
			CS(NH ₂) ₂	20, 35, 55 °C	PbS [258]
	Cd	S	200–300 °C	CdS [151,259]	solid sphere, hollow
			H ₂ S	280–300 °C	CdS [260]
	NiCo	CH ₃ CSNH ₂	160 °C	NiCo ₂ S ₄ [179]	ball-in-ball hollow
					spheres
	CoO _x	(NH ₄) ₂ S	100 °C, 70 °C	CoO _x S _{0.18} [26], CoO _x S _{1.03} [26,39]	hollow
Cu ₂ O	CH ₄ N ₂ S	190–230 °C	Cu ₂ O-Cu _x S,[28,29,77]	multi-shell	

(continued on next page)

TABLE 5 (CONTINUED)

Anion-driven synthesis	Starting material	Anionic reagent	Temperature	Product	Architecture	
Selenization	Au-Cu ₂ O Fe ₃ O ₄ ZnO	Na ₂ S	0 °C	Cu _x S[28,29,77]	core-shell, nanocages	
		CH ₄ N ₂ S	R.T.	Cu ₂ O-Cu ₂ S[46], Cu ₂ S[46]	yolk-shell, hollow	
			172 °C	Cu ₂ S[78]	hollow	
			0 °C	Au-Cu _{2-x} S[261]	core-shell	
		H ₂ S	160–200 °C	Fe ₃ S ₄ [75]	solid/hollow sphere/platelets	
			H ₂ S	160–200 °C	ZnS[75]	solid/hollow tetrapods
		[(CH ₃) ₃ Si] ₂ S		235 °C, 130 °C	ZnO-ZnS,[141]ZnS[45,141]	core-shell, hollow
		CH ₄ N ₂ S		160 °C	ZnS [262]	solid sphere
		MnO	H ₂ S	160–200 °C	MnS [75]	solid/hollow sphere
		CdO	[(CH ₃) ₃ Si] ₂ S	130 °C	CdS [45]	hollow
	WO ₂	CS ₂	300 °C	WS ₂ [76]	nanosheet	
	NiCo ₂ O ₄	NaHS	R.T.	NiCo ₂ S ₄ [48]	thin film	
	NiCoMnO ₄	TAA	180 °C	NiCo ₂ S ₄ [263]	multi-shell	
		CH ₄ N ₂ S	180 °C	NiCoMnS ₄ [190]	solid sphere	
		Fe	Se	800 °C	FeSe [96]	solid sphere
			Se	182 °C	CoSe [68]	hollow
		Co	Se	182 °C	CoSe ₂ [264]	nanonecklace
			Se	45 °C	Ag ₂ Se [105]	solid/hollow sphere
		Ag	Na ₂ Se	180 °C	Ag ₂ Se [265]	thin-film
			CSe ₂	254-nm lamp	Ag-Ag ₂ Se, [99,266]	core-shell, hollow, dendrites
Au-Ag ₂ S		Se	R.T.	Au-Ag ₂ S _{1-x} Se _x [257]	core-shell	
Pb		(TMS) ₂ Se	155 °C	Pb-PbSe [177]	core-shell	
Cd	Se	200–300 °C	CdSe [151]	hollow		
Pd, Ag-Pd	Se	260 °C	Pd ₁₇ Se ₁₅ [267], Ag-Pd ₁₇ Se ₁₅ [267]	cuboids, hollow		
Cu ₂ O	Se	R.T.	Cu ₂ O-Cu ₂ Se [34], Cu ₂ Se [34]	core-shell, nanocages		
Phosphorization	ZnO	Se	160 °C	ZnSe [262]	solid sphere	
	In ₂ O ₃ -CoO _x	Se	400 °C, 450 °C	In ₂ Se ₃ -CoSe ₂ [268]	nanorods	
		Au-Cd	Se = TOP	250 °C	Au-CdSe [269]	core-shell
		AuCu	selenourea	200 °C, 240 °C	Au-Cu _{1.8} Se, Au-CuSe [172]	heterodimers
	Cu	TOP	320 °C	Cu ₃ P [33]	solid sphere	
		TOPO, TOP	350 °C	Cu-Cu ₃ P [270]	heterodimers	
	Fe	TOP	350 °C	FeP ₂ [271] FeP [33,271]	nanorod, solid/ hollow sphere	
		Co	NaH ₂ PO ₂	450 °C, 300 °C	CoP [95,109,116,272,273]	solid sphere
	red P		700 °C, 500 °C	CoP [274], CoP ₂ [275]	solid sphere	
	Ni	TOP	320 °C, 300 °C	Ni ₂ P [33,70,276]	hollow, yolk-shell	
		Ag	TOP	350 °C	Ni ₂ P, [152]Ni ₁₂ P ₅ [152,277]	solid/hollow sphere
	P ₄		220 °C	Ni ₂ P-Ni [278]	core-shell	
	TOP	370 °C	AgP ₂ [33]	solid sphere		
	Au	TOP	360 °C	Au ₂ P ₃ [33,276]	solid sphere	
	Pt	TOP	370 °C	PtP ₂ [33,276]	solid sphere	
Rh	TOP	360 °C	RhP ₂ [33,276]	solid sphere		
Pd	TOP	250 °C,	PdP ₂ [97,276], Pd ₅ P ₂ [33]	hollow		
	TOP	360 °C, 300 °C	Pd ₅ P ₂ [279], PdP ₂ [279]	solid sphere		
NiCo	NaH ₂ PO ₂	300 °C	NiCoP [134]	hollow		
Co ₃ O ₄	NaH ₂ PO ₂	350 °C, 320 °C	CoP [108,120,280,281]	solid sphere, nanocages		
	NaH ₂ PO ₂	300 °C	CoP [282]	solid sphere		
CoO _x	NaH ₂ PO ₂	300 °C	CoP [282]	solid sphere		
Fe ₃ O ₄	TOPO	300 °C	Fe ₃ O ₄ P _x [191]	yolk-shell, hollow		
α-Fe ₂ O ₃	TOPO	300 °C	Fe ₂ O ₃ P _x [191]	yolk-shell, hollow nanocubes		

TABLE 5 (CONTINUED)

Anion-driven synthesis	Starting material	Anionic reagent	Temperature	Product	Architecture
	MnFe ₂ O ₄	TOPO	300 °C	MnFe ₂ O ₄ P _x [191]	yolk-shell, hollow
	MnO	TOPO	200 °C	MnOP _x [191]	yolk-shell, hollow dumbbell
	In ₂ O ₃	TOPO	230–320 °C	InP [283]	wires, hyperbranched sphere
Nitridation	Al	NH ₃ /N ₂	900 °C	AlN [284]	nanotube
		NH ₃	1000 °C	AlN [285,286]	hollow
	Al ₂ O ₃	NH ₃	900 °C	AlN [285,287]	solid sphere
	TiO ₂	Mg ₃ N ₂	1000 °C	TiN [288,289]	solid sphere
		NH ₃	600–800 °C	Ti(N,O) [117]	mesoporous nanowires
	ZrO ₂	NH ₃	700–900 °C	TiN [118,290]	hollow
		Mg ₃ N ₂	1000 °C	ZrN [288,289]	solid sphere
Mg ₃ N ₂		1000 °C	HfN [288,289]	solid sphere	
MoO ₂	NH ₃	650 °C	MoN [291]	porous nano-octahedrons.	
Tellurization	Na ₂ MoO ₄	NH ₃	950 °C	MoN [292]	nanosheet
	Cu	TOP-Te	250 °C	Cu-Cu _{2-x} Te, Cu _{2-x} Te [149]	core-shell, hollow
	Au-Ag	Te	R.T., 30 °C	Au-Ag ₂ Te [257,293,294]	core-shell, nanorods
Chlorination	Cd	Te	200–300 °C	CdTe [151]	hollow
	Ag	HCl	100 °C	AgCl [58]	core-shell

The anionic reagent of S is the S powder, similar with Se, and Te.

be tuned within a specific range by precisely adjusting the reaction temperature and oxidation time. Furthermore, it is worth noting that Peng et al. first used Fe-Fe₃O₄ core-shell NPs to react with trimethylamine N-oxide (Me₃NO), for the controlled preparation of hollow Fe₃O₄ NPs. This is different from the aforementioned studies that used the oxygen mixture in argon or air for iron oxide synthesis [88,295]. Additionally, it is found that the TEM electron beam can also effectively accelerate the oxidation of metal NPs in the absence of an oxidant, leading to the formation of metal oxide NCs, such as from Co to CoO and from Fe to Fe₂O₃ [306]. The selection of oxidizing reagents plays a crucial role in the synthesis of NCs, as it directly impacts the subsequent oxidation processes.

The selection of different anionic reagents often creates a certain range of options for the reaction temperature. In fact, because the alkyl ligands on the surface of metal NCs generally hinder the interaction between the oxidizing agent and the metal, the oxidation reactions of colloidal metal NCs typically occur at elevated temperatures. Although recent advancements in studying the oxidation mechanisms under high-temperature conditions, it remains a challenge to ascertain the applicability of kinetic modelling at the nanoscale and to elucidate how variations in NP size influence the underlying oxidation mechanisms. In 2022, Zhu et al. *in-situ* studied the thermal oxidation process of pristine Ni NPs (size ranging from 4 to 50 nm) in 1 bar 1 % O₂/N₂ at 600 °C using a gas-cell environmental TEM [245]. They studied from the early oxide nucleation to the diffusion-balanced oxide thickening in the process of formation of both solid and hollow NiO NCs, and reported an unexpected surface refactoring of NP before oxidation (Fig. 4j). Specifically, in an in-depth study of the oxidation mechanism of nickel

NPs, they have uncovered the pivotal role of dynamic surface restructuring during the oxidation process. It was observed that before the formation of NiO, the surface of nickel NPs underwent dynamic reconfiguration, resulting in transient surface corner sites that served as preferred sites for oxidation. The investigation identified a two-stage oxidation process for nickel NPs (Fig. 4j): The initial stage entails the formation of NiO nuclei, adhering to the Avrami-Erofeev (AE) model [307] (a model of oxidation process), along with the initial thickening of the oxide layer. Subsequently, the second stage is characterized by the thickening of the NiO shell, which is balanced by Wagner diffusion, as described by the Wagner model [308].

This first-stage oxidation is characterized by the inward retraction of the original nickel surface, defining a critical thickness beyond which the dominant transport mechanism shifts from oxygen surface diffusion to the Kirkendall diffusion mechanism. For nickel NPs with radii smaller than the critical thickness under the given oxidation conditions, their oxidation process terminates at the first stage, halting before the formation of Kirkendall voids, resulting in the production of homogeneous spherical NiO NPs (Fig. 4k). Conversely, for larger nickel NPs, whose initial radii exceed the critical thickness, the oxidation process proceeds to the second stage, leading to the formation of hollow NiO shells. The subsequent thickening of the NiO shell in the second stage was primarily driven by the Wagner diffusion of Ni²⁺ through the NiO grain boundaries, serving as “short-circuit” diffusion paths. This mechanism was validated by the experimentally determined parabolic rate constants and the observation of direction-dependent NiO thickening.

In addition to the influence of NPs size on the resulting morphology during the oxidation, the crystallinity also plays a signif-

FIG. 4

(a) Scheme of synthesis of core-shell-void Fe-Fe₃O₄ and hollow Fe₃O₄ NPs via using Fe-Fe₃O₄ NP as templet. Reproduced with permission [88]. Copyright 2007, Wiley-VCH. TEM micrographs of iron/iron oxide NPs exposed to dry 20 % oxygen: (b) <1 min at room temperature; (c) 1 h at 80 °C; (d) 12 h at 80 °C; (e) 5 min at 150 °C; (f) 1 h at 150 °C; (g) 1 h at 350 °C on a substrate; (h-i) High-resolution TEM images of partial and full oxidized iron NPs. Low- and high-resolution scale bars correspond to 100 and 6 nm, respectively. Reproduced with permission [22]. Copyright 2007, American Chemical Society. (j) Schematic representation of the three types of Ni NP oxidation as a function of time. (k) Schematic comparison between the diffusion balanced and unbalanced scenarios for successive NiO thickening until full oxidation. Reproduced with permission [245]. Copyright 2022, American Chemical Society.

icant role in determining the final structure. Specifically, polycrystalline NPs undergo oxidation to form core-shell (Co/CoO) NPs (Fig. 5a-c) [31,243], primarily because the crystallinity of the Co NPs leads to a reduced oxygen diffusion rate when they interlock. Conversely, hollow CoO NPs can be synthesized from single-domain hexagonal close-packed (hcp) NPs based on the well-known nanoscale Kirkendall effect (Fig. 5d,e). During the formation of these single-domain NCs, the final product becomes hollow because Co atoms diffuse outward through the oxide layer faster than the inward diffusion of oxygen. It is also possible that the polycrystalline structure suppresses the diffusion of ions, while the single crystal structure accelerates the diffusion of oxygen or metal ions.

As mentioned above, we have considered the oxidation mechanism and morphology control of metal NPs from the perspectives of the selection of oxidizing agents, the size and the crystallinity of the templet. However, these reaction processes are typically unidirectional. To further emphasize the controllability of metal oxidation reactions, Ha et al. transformed MnO-SiO₂ hollow sphere NPs (HSNP) into Mn₃O₄-SiO₂ core-shell NPs by a reversible oxidizing reaction [25]. The solid-to-hollow-to-solid transformation can be successfully cycled many times,

which can be achieved via simply repeating the oxidation and reduction processes by switching the flowing gas between air and hydrogen (Fig. 5f-g). From the X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of MnO-SiO₂/Pt, Pt-HSNP, Pt, PtO, MnO, Mn₃O₄ and Mn₂-SiO₄ (Fig. 5h), the transformation mechanism of hollow Mn₃O₄-SiO₂/PtO can be illustrated. Specifically, the process contains three successive steps: (1) Oxidation of Pt NCs to form PtO, (2) Pt-catalyzed reduction of the Mn₃O₄ phase to the MnO phase, and (3) Outward diffusion of the reduced MnO species into the silicate phase. Typically, three steps involve the cyclical oxidation process:

- (1) The annealing of MnO-SiO₂ core-shell nanospheres in a reducing gas (H₂) at 500 °C could transform the MnO-SiO₂ NPs into MnO-SiO₂ HSNPs because the outward diffusion of MnO species convert into the thermodynamically more stable silicate phase;
- (2) Subsequently, the MnO-SiO₂ HSNP hollow spheres can be transformed into Mn₃O₄-SiO₂ core-shell NPs through annealing in air at temperatures ranging from 500 to 800 °C, the interior cavities were refilled with a Mn₃O₄ phase segregated from the SiO₂ phase;

FIG. 5

(a) Schematic illustration of oxidation behavior of 2D hexagonally ordered Co NPs differing by their crystallinity. (b,c) HAADF-STEM images of 2D-organized Co polycrystals after oxidation. (d,e) HAADF-STEM images of 2D-organized hcp Co single-domain crystals after oxidation. Reproduced with permission [243]. Copyright 2013, American Chemical Society. (f). TEM images showing the cyclical transformation between hollow MnO-SiO₂/Pt (i) and Pt-HSNP solid. (g) Interior structure during the successive annealing at 500 °C with repeatedly switching the flowing gas between air and hydrogen. (h) Their XRD patterns. Reproduced with permission [25]. Copyright 2013, American Chemical Society. (i) Formation mechanism of dipolar PS-AuCo NPs and Au-Co₃O₄ nanowires. TEM images of ferromagnetic, (j) Core-shell PS-AuCo NPs ($D = 22 \pm 4$ nm, $D_{\text{core}} = 13 \pm 3$ nm), and (k) PS Au-Co_xO_y nanowires ($D = 31 \pm 4$ nm). Reproduced with permission [90]. Copyright 2010, American Chemical Society.

- (3) The Mn₃O₄-SiO₂ core-shell NPs can also be used to form MnO-SiO₂ HSNP hollow sphere NPs by annealing in H₂ at the same temperature as in step (2).

Besides silica coating, organic ligands such as common amines and carboxylic acids are more commonly used to stabilize NCs in colloidal systems [215,222,224]. Johans et al. reported the oxidation of Co metal NPs with amines and carboxylic acids as ligands [244], in which O₂ was introduced into the autoclave as anionic reagent and the oxygen consumption was tracked with a pressure meter. They observed the kinetics of the oxidation process and the structure of the products can be altered by changing the ligands. Specifically, a 0.8 nm thick oxide shell on Co NPs (8 nm, 22 nm, and 36 nm) could be obtained after 50 min oxidation when tridodecylamine was used as ligands to improve the stability of NCs. When tridodecylamine was replaced by long-chain carboxylic acids via ligand exchange, the thickness of the oxide shell was enlarged to 1.2 nm. Moreover, no matter what ligand (tridodecylamine or carboxylic acid) was used, the Co/CoO core-shell NPs could be used to form hollow CoO NPs by extending the oxidizing reaction time to half a year under the same reaction conditions. Interestingly, the carboxylic acid ligands could convert into carboxylate anions on the NP surface (carboxylic acid could offer O²⁻), which enhances the electric field according to the Cabrera-Mott theory and drive the oxidation process by promoting the rate of outward diffusion of cations.

Chen et al. reported that oleylamine ligands promote the oxidized metal to form soluble metal complexes [309]. In a related study, Chen et al. reported that hollow Pt₃Ni nanoframes con-

sisting of 24 edges with a width ~ 2 nm can be synthesized by the selective oxidation of Ni from the oleylamine-capped PtNi₃ NCs (Ni rich, rhombic dodecahedron) in non-polar solvents under ambient conditions for 2 weeks using dissolved oxygen as oxidant [296]. They found that the oxidized Ni can readily form soluble metal complexes with the oleylamine ligands. To investigate the impact of capping ligands on the metal NPs, in 2022, Castilla-Amorós et al. reported that amines and carboxylic acids can increase the thickness of metal oxide shells while thiols and phosphines can hinder the oxide growth [245].

While selective ligand chemistry can avoid the aggregation of NCs and adjust the oxidation process, ligands can simultaneously assist in the assembly of NPs into one-dimensional (1-D) nanomaterials [310–313]. In 2009, Kim et al. used polystyrene (PS) coated ferromagnetic Co NPs and combined these dipolar NP assemblies with an oxidation solution to transform them into cobalt oxide nanowires by bubbling O₂ in 1,2-dichlorobenzene at 175 °C [91]. Furthermore, to enhance the electrochemical performance of cobalt oxide NCs, they further prepared Au-Co₃O₄ heterostructured nanowires [90]. Herein, ferromagnetic AuCo NPs were first synthesized by using oleylamine-capped Au NPs as seeds. Then, polycrystalline Au-Co₃O₄ nanowires without perturbing morphology were prepared through further oxidation of PS Au-Co_xO_y films at 400 °C in air to remove the organic PS shell (Fig. 5i). Here, the effective diameter of the AuCo NPs is determined by considering the diameter of the Au NPs core ($D = 13 \pm 3$ nm) and the thickness of the metallic cobalt shell (~ 4 – 5 nm), which encapsulates the Au core (Fig. 5j). Under further oxidation conditions, PS Au-Co_xO_y nano-

wires with a diameter of 31 ± 4 nm were formed by the self-assembly of Au-Co_xO_y yolk-shell NCs, which correspond to the dimensional expansion of the Co shell based on the nanoscale Kirkendall effect (Fig. 5k).

While many complex metal oxide nanostructures have been prepared, adjusting the oxidation process to control the synthesis of NCs with solid, hollow, or other unique nanostructures remains challenging. Therefore, further understanding of the mechanisms of these typical oxidizing reactions is needed to gain insights into the controlled synthesis of metal oxide NCs. In this direction, *in-situ* studies of the reaction processes using modern characterization methods may facilitate the understanding of the reaction mechanism of anion-driven synthesis. For instance, Niu et al. reported the synthesis of Bi oxide hollow NPs in a liquid cell at 180–200 °C. Using the *in-situ* TEM analysis, they revealed that the diffusion of reactive species is influenced by defects, temperature, and the size of the NPs [223]. Thus all of these factors can be used to modify the kinetics of the hollowing process. Similarly, in an *in-situ* study of the oxidation process, in 2016, Yu et al. calculated that in the process of morphological transformation from solid Ag nanowires to Ag₂O nanotubes, the diffusion coefficient of Ag in its oxide shell is 1.2×10^{-13} cm²/s [247].

Beyond the oxidation of elemental metal NCs, in 2018, Zhang et al. report that Fe-Co magnetic alloy NPs can be used to prepare Co_{1-x}Fe_x^{II}Fe₂^{III}O₄ NCs by the nanoscale Kirkendall effect. The oxidation process is accompanied by the conversion from solid to core-shell and then to hollow nanostructures [250]. The use of an alloy NPs as the starting material in an oxidizing reaction was also reported by Koga et al., who prepared epitaxially coherent Au_{0.83}Cu_{0.17}-Cu₂O biphasic NPs by oxidizing Au_{0.46}Cu_{0.54} alloy NPs at a temperature above their melting point in gaseous oxygen [174]. Bauer et al. reported that heating AuCu alloy NPs in an O₂ atmosphere between 150 °C to 240 °C can form Au-CuO_x heterostructures, while heating the Au-CuO_x heterostructures in H₂ at 300 °C can reduce them into alloyed AuCu heterostructures [314]. Here, the oxygenated copper species in the heterostructure formed by the anion-driven synthesis can provide O₂ storage and release capacity for application in the field of catalysis [315]. Later, in 2017, Zhan et al. demonstrated that the composition of core materials of the AuCu alloy NPs can be properly adjusted. For example, compared with face-centered tetragonal (fct) AuCu alloy NPs, the Cu component in face centered cubic (fcc) AuCu alloy NPs is more easily segregated on the alloy surface. Therefore, the fcc and fct AuCu alloy NPs can be phase transferred into Au/CuO and AuCu/CuO core-shell structures, respectively. Furthermore, to prepare Au/CuO NPs with core-shell or heterodimer architecture, Jeon et al. reported that the Au/CuO can be generated as a major product only either at low temperatures ($T \leq 250$ °C) or with very low Cu contents. However, the Au/CuO heterodimer can be obtained at relatively high heat treatment (>250 °C) in most cases [249].

Additionally, as previously discussed in Section '**Cabrera-Mott theory of anion-driven synthesis**', when an initial oxidation occurs between the dissociative adsorption of oxygen and the surface iron, electron transport takes place in this interface allowing the oxidation to proceed. Actually, electron transport is usually considered as the first step in the oxidation of

iron surfaces, [316,317] as illustrated by the Cabrera-Mott theory [206]. Some background of this theory has been described previously (Section '**Cabrera-Mott theory of anion-driven synthesis**'). Here, we mainly review the details of the oxidation process from the perspective of the Cabrera-Mott theory in some cases. Once initial oxide is formed, the diffusion of the ions can be driven by a strong electric field, [22,165–168,316–318] which is formed by the contact potential of the chemisorbed oxygen. It is worth noting that the electron tunneling is operative only up to a thickness of 1–3 nm at temperatures below 150 °C [89,163,167,168,316–318]. Nakamura et al. provided insights into the mechanism of the critical diameter in NP oxidation at low temperatures [193]. They concluded that the single void was formed through the Kirkendall effect in the completely oxidized product when the size of the NPs was smaller than the critical diameter. For instance, Al NPs had a critical diameter of 8 nm, and the Al₂O₃ shell thickness was 1.5 nm. In another study by Nakamura et al. [251] Zn NPs exhibited a critical diameter of 20 nm and the critical diameter for Cu NPs is in the range of 10–40 nm. However, when the thickness of oxide layers is up to 10 nm, the additional source of electron supply is provided by the thermal excitation of electrons from the metal into the oxide conduction band, which allows the oxide growth to proceed further. However, when temperatures are lower or equal to 250 °C, only iron NCs smaller than 8 nm could be completely converted into hollow oxide NPs. Nevertheless, if the oxide shell is thicker than 2.0 nm at this temperature, the oxidation process will extremely slow down [163]. Meantime, when heating the NPs in solution at a higher temperature of 250–300 °C, cracks will form on the oxide shells. Here, high-temperature annealing and collapse of metal oxide NCs, such as Fe₃O₄, NiO, and CuO nanotubes under air were also reported [239,319]. Therefore, understanding the mechanisms of oxidation, such as nanoscale Kirkendall effect or Cabrera-Mott theory are beneficial to rationally control the size and shape of NC through regulating the oxidation process.

Sulfidation

Sulfidation is another widely used method to prepare functional nanostructures from metal and metal oxide NCs through the chemical transformation, especially those that are not accessible by conventional wet-chemical approaches [29,68,71,75,151]. Just like the reaction with O²⁻ anions, the reaction of S²⁻ with metal or metal oxide NPs also generated a variety of new NCs with unique nanostructures, such as Co or CoO to hollow Co sulfide (Co₃S₄, Co₉S₈, CoO_xS_{0.18-1.27}), [26,68,83] FePt-Co to core-shell FePt-Co₂S, [255] Cd or CdO to hollow CdS, [39,45,141,151] Cd nanowire to CdS nanowire, [260] ZnO to ZnO/ZnS core-shell NPs or ZnS hollow tetrapods, [45,75,141] Au/Ag or Au/Cu₂O to core-shell Au/AgS [257] or Au/Cu₂S, [46,261] AuCu NPs to Au-Cu₂S heterodimers, [171] Cu₂O to Cu₂S nanocages [28,29] or multi-shelled Cu₂S hollow spheres, [49] NiCo₂O₄ to NiCo₂S₄, [48] NiCoMnO₄ to NiCoMnS₄, [190] W₁₈O₄₉ nanorod to WS₂ nanosheet [76] and Fe₃O₄ to Fe₃S₄ [75].

To demonstrate the universality of nanostructures obtained by anion-driven synthesis, one of the challenges of sulfidation reactions is to control, eventually retain, the shape and phase of the starting NCs because anion-driven synthesis are generally accompanied by the formation of voids and a major restructura-

tion of the crystal structure. A proper anion-driven synthesis control can be demonstrated by adjusting the synthesis of either solid or hollow NCs via regulating the reaction conditions. For instance, in 2020, Lim et al. employed a morphology-conserving method to synthesize metal sulfide NPs through the utilization of an oxygen-extracting reagent to facilitate the sulfidation process [75]. To compare the preparation of the metal sulfide through the typical Kirkendall-based anion-driven synthesis and non-Kirkendall-based anion-driven synthesis, two different sulfidation processes have been proposed: (1) One process is choosing single crystalline Fe_3O_4 NPs (13 nm with the inverse spinel structure) as a sulfurating starting material to prepare 17 nm hollow Fe_3S_4 with a 7 nm void in 1-octadecene at 160 °C by using H_2S as sulfurating agent (Fig. 6a (i) and b,c); (2) The other process is using TMS-ODA as oxygen extracting reagent to assist the anion-driven synthesis of H_2S with solid Fe_3O_4 (Fig. 6a (ii), c and d). Finally, a spherical solid (void-free) sc- Fe_3S_4 with a diameter of 14.7 nm can be obtained with non-Kirkendall effect (Fig. 6d and e). In this case, the formation of solid structures is based on the non-Kirkendall effect and the specific mechanism is illustrated as follows.

Typically, due to the oxophilicity [320–322] of the trimethylsilyl (TMS) group and the nucleophilicity of the amine group of ODA, the amine group in TMS-ODA allows nitrogen to coordinate with $\text{Fe}^{2+/3+}$ while the TMS group binds O^{2-} on the surface of NCs [75,194,323]. Hence, during the reaction with TMS-ODA, the oxygen atoms on the surface of NCs can be acti-

vated and eliminated with the formation of bis-(trimethylsilyl) oxide (TMS_2O), producing oxygen vacancies (V_O). Then, adding H_2S to V_O could generate Fe-S bond and eliminate oleylamine. Finally, the generation of V_O promotes outgoing O^{2-} and incoming S^{2-} through a vacancy-mediated diffusion process [75,105]. More details relating to this were already discussed in Section ‘Cabrera-Mott theory of anion-driven synthesis’.

This work provided a special approach to achieving the controllable synthesis of nanostructures while avoiding void formation. Furthermore, regardless of the shape and crystal structure of the starting materials, such as MnO spheres, ZnO tetrapods and Fe_3O_4 , the controllable preparation of metal sulfide NCs with solid or hollow nanostructures can be achieved. Additionally, since the formation of the void in the sulfidation process has been prevented, the metal sulfide NPs with core-shell nanostructures can also be prepared. For instance, Zhang et al. reported the preparation of an amorphous structure shell of Ag_2S from Au-Ag NCs with core-shell structure. They found that the Ag_2S shell provides a crucial platform for the next chemical transformation stage, which can be used to compose monocrystalline nanoscale semiconductor core-shell structure and heterostructure [257]. Most importantly, they reported that compared with other metal cations (Zn^{2+} , Pb^{2+} and Cd^{2+}), the silver cations generally behave as a soft acid (2.1.2 hardness). Hence, Ag^+ can easily share their *d* electrons, and coordinate with various soft bases by back-donating π bonds to form a rich family of organometallic complexes. Then, the high acid softness can provide a synthetic pro-

FIG. 6

(a) Formation mechanism of hollow Fe_3S_4 NPs by Kirkendall-based sulfidation (i) Solid Fe_3S_4 NPs by OER-assisted sulfidation. (ii) TEM images of transformed hollow Fe_3S_4 NPs. (b) Template solid Fe_3O_4 NPs. (c) Transformed solid Fe_3S_4 NPs. (d) Transformed solid Fe_3S_4 NPs. (e) Changes in XRD patterns during OER-assisted sulfidation. (red, Fe_3O_4 (PDF no. 01-071-6336); yellow, Fe_3S_4 (PDF no. 01-089-1998)). Reproduced with permission [75]. Copyright 2020, American Chemical Society. Scheme (right) and TEM micrographs (left) of the reaction of Cd NCs with (f) Molecular sulfur in solution ($[\text{S}]/[\text{Cd}] = 8$). (g) TOP = S. Reproduced with permission [151]. Copyright 2011, American Chemical Society.

cess with a wide thermodynamic control. Furthermore, the electronegativity of silver is similar to some common anions X, such as P, As and chalcogenides [257,324]. Therefore, the silver shells can be transformed into silver sulfide shells under certain conditions including appropriate temperature and anion molecular complexes. In addition, the anion-driven synthesis of Ag NPs with iodine and phenylisothiocyanate (PhNCS) can also be used to fabricate the γ -AgI and Ag₂S (core-shell and hollow) nanostructures [99].

Meantime, the metal Pb NPs also could be used as starting materials to synthesize Pb-PbS core-shell NPs [148,177]. Furthermore, for core-shell to core-shell nanostructure by anion-driven synthesis, except that the Au-Ag core-shell NPs could act as the starting materials to prepare core-shell sulfide nanostructure, FePt-Co and Au-Cu₂O core-shell NPs can also be used to prepare FePt-CoS₂ and Au-Cu_{2-x}S core-shell NPs [255,261]. Importantly, regardless of the size of starting NPs, the core-shell (or yolk-shell) is usually an intermediate state in the transformation process of the nanostructure from solid to hollow or nanocages in the process of sulfidation, which is similar to the yolk-shell nanostructures in the oxidizing reaction [28,29,77,141]. However, unlike the general sulfidation process where the reaction is quenched by the formation of a shell, the sulfidation of ZnO NPs proceeds primarily through a dissolution and reprecipitation mechanism. Specifically, ZnO NPs (20 nm) initially dissolves in an environment containing Na₂S, and subsequently, Zn ions combine with sulfide ions to form ZnS, which then reprecipitates as ZnS NPs smaller than 5 nm. Given sufficient addition of Na₂S, a conversion being close to 100 % can be achieved in 5 days [325].

As discussed above, the initial size of the starting NPs that used for sulfidation to prepare metal sulfide NPs based on a non-Kirkendall effect usually is small (less than 20 nm). The morphology of the produced metal sulfide NPs can be preserved nicely in this anion-driven synthesis because the diffusion of ions and vacancies can be managed admirably. However, in most cases, it is very difficult to avoid the formation of voids and fabricate products with solid morphology when the starting materials have large sizes. For instance, when the sulfidation of metal oxide NPs with large size (> 200 nm) occurs, pseudomorphic nanocages can be obtained generally. In 2006, Jiao et al. prepared copper sulfide nanocages with single-crystalline shells by using Cu₂O sphere NPs (size > 200 nm) as sacrificial starting materials in Na₂S aqueous solution, and the composition of nanocages can be tuned from Cu₂S to Cu_{1.75}S by control of the ratio of N₂ to air atmosphere [29]. However, the nanocages obtained through this sulfidation process contain many pores and fractured walls, thus, these nanocages are not suitable for some applications, like drug delivery. Here, in order to prepare nanocages with well-defined ultrathin walls, Kuo et al. report that the Cu₂S nanocages and Au-Cu₂S core-nanocage can be synthesized in a Na₂S solution by using cubic Cu₂O NCs and octahedral Au-Cu₂O core-shell NCs (size > 50 nm) as starting materials [77]. Most importantly, after the surface of the NPs converted into metal sulfides, HCl was used to etch away Cu₂O from the wall of the Cu₂S nanocages. As revealed by TEM measurements, the obtained hollow Cu₂S nanocages manifest crystalline walls with a thickness ranging from 10 to 20 nm and ultrasmall pores with sizes of 1 nm or

less. Interestingly, the small pores and well-defined ultra-thin walls allow the transport of anthracene and pyrene (fluorescence molecules) from the solution into the cages. Furthermore, fluorescence molecules can be adsorbed on the surfaces of the core (the encapsulated gold NPs) in the inside of the nanocage, which can be proved by their enhanced fluorescence quenching (the fluorescent molecules are inside the nanocage, so the detected fluorescence is weak). To further design unprecedented nanostructure with pores and ultra-thin walls via anion-driven synthesis for molecule trapping and delivery application, in 2016, Wu et al. used Cu₂O NCs (with different shapes but identical crystal structures, and size > 200 nm) as a starting material to prepare pseudomorphic copper sulfide nanocages with different crystal structures in ambient conditions [28]. Here, the crystalline phase of Cu₂S nanocages was determined by the anion sublattice and packing pattern of the surface of the Cu₂O NPs. For example, the body-centered cubic lattice can be abnormally converted into the face-centered cubic or a hexagonally close-packed lattice, which formed multiply twinned nanostructures. Additionally, this unusual crystallographic structure can be used as a starting material to prepare CdS or ZnS nanocages by sequential cation exchange reactions.

As a matter of fact, it is well known that the size of starting NPs can partly determine the produced nanostructures. When the starting NCs are larger than 200 nm, hollow nanocages with hollow centrality generally can be obtained by the anion-driven synthesis, [28,29,77] which have been reviewed previously for their synthesis mechanism and biomedical applications [326]. In order to show the universality of sulfidation, many studies have reported that the solid or hollow NPs both can be prepared by the sulfidation process of template NCs smaller than 20 nm. Furthermore, the hollow structures are the most common nanostructure of products synthesized by anion-driven synthesis no matter the size of the starting materials. In fact, since the earlier work on the reactions of Co or CoO NPs with sulfur to prepare hollow cobalt sulfide NPs by Yin et al. et al. in 2004 and 2006, [68,83] there have been many reports on the synthesis of metal sulfide hollow nanostructures (by Kirkendall effects) in the most recent decades. For instance, Wang et al. explored a method to prepare PbS hollow NPs, [148] by using spherical colloids Pb NPs as their chemical starting materials to react with sulfur powder. Here, Pb cores could be completely converted into hollow PbS nanospheres. Being different from the spherical hollow nanostructure of PbS, Román-Zamorano et al. reported a hydrothermal method to synthesize Pb sulfide NPs with two phases such as galena PbS and tetragonal β -PbS₂ [258].

Furthermore, to prepare hollow metal sulfide NCs, Cabot et al. reported that Cd NCs with a relatively large size of 350 nm can be used as a starting material to prepare metal sulfide NCs. They found that the diffusion rate of Cd is much faster than that of S, which leads to the accumulation of vacancies at the metal/sulfide interface (the region of reaction in which Cd reacts with S) in this sulfidation process. In addition, they demonstrated that the NCs architecture can be controlled by adjusting the reaction time, reaction temperature and Cd/S ratio [259]. Ibañez et al. further studied the means and limits of control of hollow CdS NPs prepared using Cd NPs as starting materials (Fig. 6f, g) [151]. They concluded that the shell thickness and crystallinity of the

products could be tuned by adjusting the relative concentrations of the precursor and its reactivity. Specifically, a large excess amount of sulfur in dichlorobenzene (DCB:S) could produce hollow CdS NPs with high inner/outer radius ratios R_i/R_o (Fig. 6f, h), while smaller amounts of DCB:S or the use of the less reactive TOP:S can drive the formation of solid CdS NPs or hollow CdS NPs with low R_i/R_o radius ratios (Fig. 6g, i). Importantly, large amounts of DCB:S gave small NCs sizes and a large R_i/R_o radius ratio, which is close to the theoretical limit of nearly complete CdS shell growth at the shell/solution interface [151]. Under these reaction conditions, outward Cd diffusion is much faster than inward S diffusion. As a matter of fact, the reaction rate is limited by the diffusivity of Cd through the shell. Using X-ray diffraction quantitatively tracking the emergence of CdS and metal Cd at the same time decreasing changes over time, they conclude that the NCs with small size results in the fast nucleation of CdS NPs on the CdS shell/solution interface. On the other hand, different from excessive sulfur reagent in solution, a smaller amount of DCB:S generally reduces the rate of CdS nucleation, further yielding larger NCs sizes and a small R_i/R_o radius ratio. Most importantly, the final structure was determined by the competition of conversion of the inner Cd/CdS core-shell interface and the outer CdS shell/solution interface [151]. In other words, with high DCB:S concentrations, conversion can occur preferentially at the CdS shell/solution interface while diffusion is limited. However, with lower DCB:S concentrations, the reaction at the inner Cd/CdS core-shell interface becomes significant and conversion is limited. Hence, low DCB:S concentrations promoted CdS growth at both the core-shell and shell/solution interfaces. In the meantime, the extent of void formation of final structure can also be controlled by adjusting the precursor reactivity. For instance, hollow CdS NPs with a smaller inner diameter were also obtained when using trioctylphosphine TOP:S to place of a small amount of DCB:S because TOP:S is less reactive than DCB:S. Overall, the concentration and precursor reactivity in this synthesis system allows precise control of CdS shell thickness.

To expand the possibilities of anion-driven synthesis to prepare unique nanostructures, the use of hollow NPs as starting material materials has been also explored. For instance, Zhang et al. prepared hollow cobalt sulfide amorphous nanospheres via a simple sulfidation process using hollow crystalline CoO NPs (prepared by oxidizing reaction in Section 'Oxidation') to react with $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}$ at a low temperature (70 °C) [39]. Due to the faster outward diffusion of Co^{2+} and O^{2-} than the incoming S^{2-} , the significant expansion of the initial NPs voids can be found during the sulfidation process. Additionally, the crystallinity of hollow Co_3S_4 NPs can be improved by annealing cobalt sulfide amorphous nanospheres at high temperatures in an organic solution [26,39]. Similarly, in 2016, Nelson et al. used $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}$ as the sulfur source to react with cobalt oxide NPs at 100 °C to forge hollow $\text{CoO}_x\text{S}_{0.18}$ nanospheres with a controlled degree of sulfidation (Fig. 7a) [26]. The stability of cobalt oxysulfides can be improved via annealing the product at 200 °C under N_2 for 1 h. Here, the CoO_x NPs with a diameter of 13.0 ± 1.5 nm obtained by oxidation are hollow and polycrystalline (Fig. 7b). The oxysulfide $\text{CoO}_x\text{S}_{0.18}$ NPs with a metastable, distorted S-substituted CoO phase, created from the $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}$: Co ratio of

3:10, has a morphology almost identical to the CoO_x NPs (diameter 12.9 ± 1.4 nm) (Fig. 7c). For higher degrees of anion-driven synthesis, the $\text{CoO}_x\text{S}_{1.03}$ NPs with a diameter of 15.0 ± 1.7 nm (Fig. 7d) and $\text{CoO}_x\text{S}_{1.27}$ NPs with a diameter of 14.5 ± 1.6 nm (Fig. 7e) were obtained. The diameter increase follows the growth of the cavity within the NPs due to the nanoscale Kirkendall effect. As shown in Fig. 7f, CoO_x and $\text{CoO}_x\text{S}_{0.18}$ NPs exhibit a rock-salt structure with broad diffraction from the (111), (200), and (200) planes. Interestingly, as shown by the vertical dashed line in Fig. 7f, the SAED pattern of $\text{CoO}_x\text{S}_{0.18}$ show a small shift to lower scattering angles. This phenomenon indicates the expansion of the unit cell, which may be caused by the larger S anion with a large radius occupying the O^{2-} lattice. However, this shift is an order of magnitude smaller than expected based on the extrapolations of the Co-O/Co-S bond lengths from the Shannon radii [26,327]. Therefore, it is anticipated that the S concentration at the surface may be higher than in the bulk. At the high driving forces for S incorporation by using higher $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}$: Co ratios (1: 1 and 1: 3), the $\text{CoO}_x\text{S}_{1.03}$ exhibit weak peaks that could correspond to smaller grains of CoO. With higher S concentrations, the primary rocksalt CoO reflections become very weak in $\text{CoO}_x\text{S}_{1.27}$. Finally, compared with the unannealed NP, the annealed NPs with higher sulfur content show less significant expansion relative to the CoO NP.

However, the configuration of most available hollow nanostructures appears relatively simple, such as one composition of a single-shelled hollow sphere [179]. According to the above sulfidation rules, we believe that nanostructures can be intentionally fabricated via strategic control of the reaction conditions. For instance, Cu_2O NPs with large sizes (300–500 nm) can be used to design hollow multi-shelled Cu_2S . Xiong et al. explored an effective pathway using a mesocrystalline precursor of Cu_2O as the starting material to fabricate the multi-shelled hollow structures (Fig. 7g) [49]. Here, the fine nanostructures were enabled by sulfidation successfully through the control of the parameters of this anion-driven synthesis such as reactant concentration, reaction temperature, and the amount of capping ligands [49]. Specifically, these four main stages during this process perhaps can be used to illustrate the mechanism of the formation of multi-shell nanostructure: (1) Colloidal Cu_2O NPs were synthesized to form inorganic-organic hybrids with the assistance of PVP (Fig. 7g, step1); (2) Interestingly, the presence of PVP can slow down the rates of both the movement of S^{2-} ions from solution to the Cu_2O surface and the formation of Cu_2S surface clusters (step 2) during the sulfidation. With a continuous supply of sulfur dianions for further sulfur reaction, the Cu_2S shell presents steady growth because the mobility rate of O^{2-} is faster than that of sulfur, [141] thus, the persistent mass relocation of Cu_2O crystallites from inside to outside can be promoted. Moreover, the as-synthesized crystalline Cu_2S shell is much more compact compared to the porous starting material Cu_2O NPs, due to the recrystallization during the Ostwald ripening process. (3) Furthermore, the formation of vacant space (between the growing Cu_xS shell and depleting Cu_2O core) (step 3) contains two main processes: Out-diffusion of Cu_2O crystalline and the conversion of denser crystalline Cu_xS shell by the anion-driven synthesis of mesocrystalline Cu_2O , which are closely related to the anion-driven synthesis. (4) Different from

FIG. 7

(a) Schematic of the synthesis of cobalt oxysulfides via partial and full sulfidation. TEM images of structural transformations of CoO_xS_y NPs during anion exchange (a) of O^{2-} with S^{2-} ((b–e), scale bar 25 nm). The NCs morphology and crystal structure of the CoO_x NCs (b) are retained at low S^{2-} doping levels (c), but at higher doping levels the NCs swell and become less crystalline (d and e). Reference lines are given in (f) for CoO ; the dashed vertical line identifies the (220) reflection. Reproduced with permission [26]. Copyright 2016, Royal Society of Chemistry. (g) Formation process of multi-shelled Cu_2S hollow spheres. Multi-shelled Cu_2S hollow spheres: (h) Largely in double shelled Cu_2S (210/220 °C); (i–k) Mainly in triple-shelled Cu_2S (220/220 °C). $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2/\text{CH}_4\text{N}_2\text{S} = 2:1$. Reproduced with permission [49]. Copyright 2012, Wiley-VCH. (l) Schematic of the synthesis of NiCo sulfide ball in ball nanostructures via sulfidation. (m–o) TEM images of NiCo-glycerate products obtained after sulfidation at 160 °C for different durations: (m) 0.5 h; (n) 2 h; (o) 6 h. Scale bars, 200 nm. Reproduced with permission [179]. Copyright 2015, Nature Publishing Group.

yolk-shell and hollow nanostructure, when copper is generated, S^{2-} ions need simultaneously enter the Cu_2O core in the process of ripening and compaction in order to form multi-shell nanostructures. Hence, maintaining the continuous and stable supply of S^{2-} and PVP reduces the mobility of S^{2-} and further slows down the sulfation rate, all of which play an important role in promoting the roundness of Cu_xS shells and preparing multi-shell nanostructures. The second, third, and fourth shells of Cu_xS can be formed by repeating these reaction processes (steps 4 and 5, 6 and 7, and 8 and 9, sequentially). Among them, the shell defect must allow the penetration of S^{2-} anions to the internal copper oxide.

To prepare multi-shell structures, different from using metal oxide NPs as starting materials, Shen et al. reported that NiCo_2S_4 ball-in-ball hollow spheres can be prepared by using NiCo NPs as starting materials to react with thioacetamide (TAA) (Fig. 7l) [179]. In this sulfidation process, the NPs undergo a transformation from a solid structure to a core-shell structure, then to a yolk-shell structure, and finally to a ball-in-ball hollow structure (Fig. 7m–o). Importantly, the interiors of the as-prepared NiCo_2S_4 hollow sphere could be adjusted by tuning the reaction temperature because the temperature not only influences the decomposition rate of TAA, but also affect the diffusion rate of ions. Here, the following three examples may help us to specifically understand the influence of the reaction temperature on the formation of nanostructures: (1) After sulfidation at 120 °C for 6 h, only core-shell structures can be prepared; (2) Then prolonging the reaction time to 12 h, ball-in-ball hollow spheres (with less space between the two shell) can be obtained; (3) Moreover, after sulfidation at 200 °C for 6 h, only hollow structures (with a single shell) can be formed due to the fast diffusion

of ions before the formation of the inner metal sulfide layer (on the interior core).

The production of two-dimensional (2D) nanostructures using anion-driven synthesis is another formidable challenge. It is particularly challenging to fabricate 2D nanostructures from one-dimensional (1D) nanostructures as recently accomplished by Seo et al. [76]. Specifically, Seo et al. developed a novel shape-transformation concept that proceeds by rolling out the 1D $\text{W}_{18}\text{O}_{49}$ nanorods to fabricate laterally confined (less than 100 nm) 2D WS_2 nanosheets (Fig. 8a–f). This sulfidation process was accompanied by the presence of carbon disulfide as anionic reagent in a hot hexadecylamine solution (Fig. 8a) [76].

Different from the preparation of nanosheet structures by the sulfidation of nanorods directly, the metal sulfide NCs attaching to nanosheets (e.g. graphene) may offer a convenient approach to forge metal sulfide 2D structures. For instance, Pendashteh et al. synthesized quaternary metal sulfide NPs (attach to the nitrogen-doped reduced graphene oxide) ($\text{NiCoMnS}_4/\text{N-rGO}$) by using $\text{NiCoMnO}_4/\text{N-rGO}$ hybrid as a starting material to react with $\text{CH}_4\text{N}_2\text{S}$ (Fig. 8g–k) [190]. Here, the morphology can also be retained during the sulfidation process. Additionally, the sulfide and oxide compounds exhibit distinct physical and chemical properties, such as density, magnetic susceptibility, and surface chemistry. These differences can be leveraged to significantly enhance separation efficiency compared to liquid-liquid methods. The study provides sulfidation process conditions for 56 elements, with practical demonstrations conducted for 15 of them [328].

Phosphorization

In recent years, tremendous efforts have been devoted to preparing phosphide NPs through a variety of synthetic methods. In

FIG. 8

(a) Schematic diagram of the synthesis of 2D WS_2 nanosheets. (b) TEM image of $\text{W}_{18}\text{O}_{49}$ nanorod precursors. (c-e) TEM images of 2D WS_2 obtained with the reaction times 10 min (c), 30 min (d), and 1 h (e) after the CS_2 injection. (f) XRD analyses of the WS_2 single (top) and stacked (bottom) nanosheets (red lines: JCPDS reference card no. 08-0237). Reproduced with permission [76]. Copyright 2007, Wiley-VCH. (g) Schematic illustration of the synthesis procedure for (h) $\text{NiCoMnS}_4/\text{N-rGO}$ nanocomposites, which including (i) inward growth and (j) outward growth with Kirkendall effect. (k) TEM micrograph of the $\text{NiCoMnS}_4/\text{N-rGO}$ hybrid showing anchored crystalline sulfide NPs on thin rGO layers. Reproduced with permission [190]. Copyright 2019, Elsevier.

this scenario, phosphorization reactions have attracted lots of interest. Phosphorization is a common anion-driven synthesis method to controllably prepare metal phosphide NPs with unique morphologies. The available transition-metal phosphides are promising candidates for emerging applications because of their excellent electrical conductivity, stability, diverse compositions and crystal structures [132,329,330]. For example, many transition-metal phosphides (such as CoP , Ni_2P , FeP , Cu_3P , MoP , and WP , etc.) with different components and morphologies have been explored as cathodic materials for hydrogen evolution reactions [132,331–336].

Phosphorization reactions generally involve the reaction of metal or metal oxide NPs with active P-containing species, such as *n*-trioctylphosphine TOP, [271,276,337] TOPO, [191] white phosphorous P_4 [338] and $(\text{Me}_2\text{N})_3\text{P}$ [52]. In most cases, the phosphorization process generally involves the migration of different ions, and the vacancies inside the NCs can coalesce when the diffusion rate of the ions is unbalanced. Hence, there are two common approaches to prepare the products with desired nanostructures: (1) Controlling the void formation by optimizing reaction conditions such as temperature, reaction time, reagent types and reactant concentrations, and

(2) Adjusting the behaviors of nucleation and growth of NPs. Furthermore, metal phosphide NPs can serve as a typical model system to understand the anion-driven synthesis. Herein, we mainly reviewed the recent advances in metal phosphide NPs formed by phosphorization reactions to elucidate the nanostructural transformation process. Simultaneously, we also discuss the possible mechanisms behind to synthesis of specific metal phosphide NPs with controlled size and structure.

Metals can cause the cleavage of the P-C bond, thus, leading to phosphorous diffusion into the metal [33]. In this regard, the use of TOP as a P source to convert metal NPs into metal phosphides NPs is a common strategy. For example, Khanna et al. reported that InP NCs can be formed by the reaction of bulk-scale indium powder and TOP [339]. Chiang et al. explored the reactivity of Ni NPs with the TOP to form Ni_2P hollow nanosphere [70]. Besides common nickel phosphorization, Henkes et al. described a robust strategy for synthesizing many transition metal phosphide NPs via solution-mediated reaction with TOP based on the Kirkendall effect [33,276]. They reported that some transition metal phosphide NPs, including Ni_2P , PtP_2 , Rh_2P , Au_2P_3 , Pd_5P_2 , and PdP_2 , can be formed using metal NPs or other

metal compound NPs as starting materials to react with TOP. Furthermore, they show that, in some case, the bulk-scale metal powder can also be converted into metal phosphide NPs by simple solution-mediated reaction with hot TOP [33]. Some of the obtained metal phosphide NPs usually exhibit a variety of interesting properties, including magnetism, catalysis, superconductivity, superparamagnetism, magnetothermal effect, and magnetoresistance [271,340–343].

As aforementioned, extensive efforts have been devoted to promoting the Kirkendall effect in obtaining hollow nanostructures of various morphologies and compositions. For the preparation of hollow nanostructure by the phosphorization process, Hyeon et al. synthesized hollow phosphide NPs with various shapes, sizes, and compositions [191]. Herein, the final NPs contain oxygen, phosphorus, and metal. Interestingly, they showed MnO and iron oxide NCs both can be used as the initial reaction starting material for anion-driven synthesis, and the phosphorization reagent is TOPO, which is also the solvent in the phosphorization process [191]. The formation of hollow phosphide NPs is also accompanied by the Kirkendall effect due to the different rates of inward diffusion of phosphorus and outward diffusion of metal cations within the phosphide NCs shell. Interestingly, these hollow NPs exhibited paramagnetic properties at room temperature and exhibited spin relaxation enhancement effect when dispersed in water. Furthermore, Heyon et al. showed these excellent properties have the potential of hollow metal phosphide NPs for multifunctional biomedical applications, such as drug delivery vehicles and as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) contrast agents, which are similar to hollow iron oxide nanocapsules [297]. In order to control the nanostructures of metal phosphite NCs, Muthuswamy et al. reported that both Fe₂P nanorods and FeP hollow NPs can be prepared by a series of reactions of Fe NPs with TOP [271]. The phase of Fe phosphide can be controlled by adjusting the phosphorization temperature and time, and even concentrations of Fe. Specifically, sufficiently high concentrations of Fe, low reaction temperatures, and short reaction time can enable the production of phase-pure Fe₂P (iron-rich) NCs. Furthermore, Fe₂P solid nanorods occasionally with hollow characteristics of the Kirkendall effect can transform to FeP (phosphorus-rich) NPs with a hollow spherical morphology by increasing the phosphorization time and temperature properly. Unfortunately, due to some unknown kinetic barriers (obstacles), it is challenging to completely convert Fe₂P NPs into FeP NPs. They speculated that the emergence of this phenomenon perhaps because the ion mobility of inward diffusion of P and outward diffusion of Fe were decreased as the FeP shell thickness increases [271].

Besides the Fe-P system, some previous studies have demonstrated the synthesis of nickel phosphide NPs. In 2009, Wang et al. reported a method to obtain hollow Ni_xP_y NPs via the reaction of Ni NPs with TOP through the Kirkendall effect at 300 °C [277]. At a high P: Ni molar ratio (> 8.6), the reaction at 240 °C produced amorphous Ni_xP_y NPs while crystalline Ni_xP_y NPs were obtained at 300 °C. Then, the mixed solid and hollow Ni_xP_y NPs can be prepared via the control of the precursor molar ratio (P: Ni = 6) at 240–300 °C. At a low P: Ni molar ratio (0.9–2.8), the crystalline Ni NPs can be synthesized at 240 °C, and the crystalline hollow Ni_xP_y NPs can be synthesized at 300 °C.

To further understand how the synthetic conditions influence the phase, size, morphology, and composition of Ni_xP_y NPs during the phosphorization process, Muthuswamy et al. [152] studied the process of formation of nickel phosphide NPs. Here, similar to Fe₂P nanorods and Fe₂P hollow sphere, phase-pure products of hollow Ni₁₂P₅ NPs (~30 nm) and solid Ni₂P NPs (~10 nm) can be controllably fabricated by tuning several key parameters, such as the P: Ni precursor ratio, oleylamine content, reaction temperature and time (Fig. 9a). First of all, the P: Ni ratio impacts the phase and structure of the sample at the precursor synthesis temperature (200–230 °C) (Fig. 9 a,b). At a low P: Ni ratio, hollow metal-rich Ni₁₂P₅ NPs with a large size (~30 nm) can be generated while at a high P: Ni ratio, solid Ni₂P NPs with a small size (~10 nm) can be formed. Then, increasing temperature and time can also promote the formation of solid Ni₂P NPs since it could generate more reactive P to form the thermodynamic product. Moreover, at the crystallization temperature range of 300–350 °C (Fig. 9c,d), the chemical composition of the product phase will be changed when more of the P is added. This enables the formation of hollow Ni₂P NPs. Finally, by increasing the oleylamine concentration, Ni₁₂P₅ can be achieved even with high P: Ni precursor ratios. This is because a lower oleylamine concentration at low P: Ni ratios lead to smaller void sizes in the formed Ni₁₂P₅ NCs, resulting in Ni₁₂P₅ NPs with reduced hollowness (Fig. 9c,d). Besides TOP, tributylphosphine (TBP) or triphenylphosphine (TPP) can also be used to synthesize Ni phosphide NPs. Greenwood et al. reported that the nickel phosphide compounds formed by phosphorization have at least 8 phases/compositions, which include Ni₃P, Ni₅P₂, Ni₁₂P₅, Ni₂P, Ni₅P₄, NiP, NiP₂, and NiP₃ [344].

Similar to the use of TOP as a phosphorization reagent, Andrea et al. successfully employed TOP to directly produce Janus-shaped Cu-Cu₃P NPs and hexagonal Cu₃P NPs at a temperature of 350 °C (Fig. 9e,l). By precisely controlling the reaction temperature and time, the phosphorization process between the Cu and phosphorus sources proceeds, resulting in Janus NPs with distinct Cu and Cu₃P domains. Specifically, when using less than 2 mL of TOP (for instance, 1 mL, which corresponds to a TOP:Cu ratio of 5.6:1), Cu NPs were first formed. This was likely due to the reduction of Cu⁺ by the alkylamines present. As time passed, these Cu particles reacted with TOP to form Janus-shaped Cu-Cu₃P NPs, and gradually transformed into Cu₃P NPs (Fig. 9f-i). Notably, different from the formation of hollow Ni₂P NPs during the phosphorization process of metal Ni NPs, the occurrence of the Kirkendall effect has never been observed in the case of Cu₃P NPs, which are prepared by phosphorizing initial metallic Cu particles. Through detailed HRTEM analysis of Cu-Cu₃P heterostructures (Fig. 9j,k), two distinct epitaxial growth processes of Cu₃P on Cu during phosphorization were identified. Both processes exhibited alignment of Cu₃P (300) lattice planes with Cu (111) planes along epitaxial interfaces, following specific crystallographic relationships. The lattice mismatch between Cu₃P (300) and Cu (111) planes was calculated to be 0.9 % and 0.5 % for the two epitaxial relationships, respectively, indicating a good fit between the crystalline domains. HRTEM and electron tomography analysis further revealed the epitaxial relationships and crystalline habit of the heterostructures (the insert of Fig. 9j,k).

FIG. 9

Overview with inset TEM and XRD measurements of the chemical levers that control the composition, size, and morphology of Ni_xP_y NPs. Low P: Ni precursor ratios resulted in large, hollow NPs (a,c), while higher P: Ni precursor ratios gave small, solid NPs (b,d). Reproduced with permission [152]. Copyright 2011, American Chemical Society. (e) Schematic of the synthesis of Cu₃P via phosphorization. (f–i) TEM images documenting the formation of Cu NPs and their progressive phosphorization, (f) 4 min, (g) 10 min, (h) 25 min, (i) 45 min. The scale bar is 50 nm for the panels and 20 nm for the insets. (j,k) HRTEM images of the dimers. (l) XRD pattern of the powder sample of Janus-like particles shown in panel h. Reproduced with permission [270]. Copyright 2012, American Chemical Society.

Besides the use of phosphines such as TOP, TBP, and TPP as anionic reagents, white phosphorous (P₄), as a cheap and more reactive phosphorus source, can also be used to prepare metal

phosphide NPs [278,338]. For instance, Carenco et al. reported that amorphous solid Ni₂P NPs, crystalline Ni₂P-amorphous Ni₂P core-shell NPs, and crystalline Ni₂P-crystalline Ni core-shell

NPs can be prepared by the phosphorization of Ni NPs using P_4 as the anionic reagent.

Besides Ni, other metals such as Fe, Cu, and Pd NPs can also be used to produce metal phosphide NPs by reacting them with P_4 (Fig. 10a) [338]. Here, due to the higher reactivity of P_4 , at the low reaction temperatures (180 °C), the amorphous FeP NPs can be prepared by using Fe NPs as starting materials. Notably, to demonstrate the precise control over the phosphorization process, the utilization of higher reaction temperatures (250 °C) leveraged the Kirkendall effect, enabling the formation of hollow FeP NPs with well-defined crystalline structures. Interestingly, similar to the crystalline Ni_2P -crystalline Ni core-shell NPs, Fe_2P -Fe (Fe is the outer shell) double-shell NPs can be formed at a low P amount (Fe: P = 16) by the Kirkendall effect at 250 °C in 1 h. Then, the double-shelled Fe_2P - Fe_xO_y (Fe-rich phases of Fe_xO_y) NPs with a central void can be obtained by an oxidation process due to air exposure during the isolation process (Fig. 10b).

Additionally, they also reported that the Cu-Cu₃P core-shell NPs (with no amorphous intermediate) can be prepared by an incomplete anion-driven synthesis of Cu NPs and P_4 due to the low reaction temperature of 100 °C and short time of 30 min. It is worth noting that this core-shell Cu-Cu₃P NP is different from the Janus structures [270]. Similar to the Fe-P system, core-double-shell Cu-Cu₃P-Cu_xO NPs can also be formed during the washing of the Cu-Cu₃P core-shell NPs. Finally, they reported that the case of metal Pd NPs showed more versatility because both Pd₅P₂ and PdP₂ NPs can be prepared by changing the stoichiometry of Pd and P_4 although the crystallization of the phase generally requires a high temperature.

Similarly, utilizing P_4 as the phosphorizing agent, Nguyen et al. delved into the phosphorization of Cu-Ni core-shell NPs with reactive P_4 (Fig. 10c). Their work highlighted the unique phosphorization process where phosphorus migrated inward while copper diffused outward, culminating in the formation of hollow (Ni,Cu)₂P NPs coexisting with metallic Cu NPs (Fig. 10c-h). The formation of hollow (Ni,Cu)₂P NPs is facilitated by multiple factors in the phosphating process.

- (1) Phosphorus preferentially reacts with nickel due to the stability of nickel phosphides, leading to the initial formation of a nickel phosphide layer (Fig. 10n,o);
- (2) This triggers the outward migration of copper atoms, driven by the increase in copper concentration within the particle;
- (3) This migration exemplifies a nanoscale Kirkendall effect, resulting in the hollow structure (Fig. 10i-o);
- (4) The NPs undergo amorphization during phosphorus diffusion and copper migration, followed by recrystallization into the (Ni,Cu)₂P phase at 250°C (Fig. 10i-o). Precise control of reaction conditions is crucial for successful formation of the hollow structure during the phosphating process, rather than other structures and compositions.

Understanding the void conversion process in phosphorization has remained a challenge over the past decades due to the limited ability to accurately monitor the intermediate reaction stages. Ha et al. reported that a metastable cubic structure of ϵ -

Co can convert to Co₂P (intermediate stages) and then to CoP via reacting with TOP [346]. Specifically, the structural evolution and the diffusion processes can occur during the phase transformation of NPs. There are two sequential diffusion steps during the conversion of ϵ -Co into Co₂P, (1) Similar to other anion-driven synthesis, the inward diffusion rate of P atoms is initially faster than the outward diffusion of Co (Fig. 11a); (2) However, voids can generate when the Co₂P shell forms (Co₂P becomes the majority phase in the NPs), which arise from the faster outward diffusion of Co. For the transformation of Co₂P to CoP, there is no additional void generated and the average size remains unchanged, which is presumably due to the fast outward diffusing of Co while the anion lattice remains intact (Fig. 11b) [346]. However, Co-rich NPs could generally continue the Kirkendall hollowing process in further anion-driven synthesis because of the residual metal.

Similarly, for the study of the morphology and composition of metal phosphide NPs via phosphorization reaction by the Kirkendall effect, in 2017, Tianou et al. investigated the conversion of solid cube Pd NPs into hollow sphere Pd NPs (monometallic hollow NCs, a special composition of products by the phosphorization of metals) through phosphorization reaction (Fig. 11f) [97]. Here, it is worth noting that the cavitation (or phosphorization) process could be repeated several times, and the thickness of the shell and diameter of the hollow sphere can be tuned. Importantly, different from the previous work, the phosphorus source of TOP in this process only acts as an anionic excess rather than a phosphorization reagent in preparing hollow metal phosphide NPs. Hence, this study confirms that the anion-driven synthesis of metal NPs is carried out by a non-Kirkendall process and does not produce holes. However, the subsequent phosphorus ions extraction process is usually accompanied by hole production. Specifically, there are three steps during this anion-driven synthesis: (1) During the initial stage of the phosphorization reaction, cubic solid Pd NCs with relatively weak binding energy can become spherical solid PdP₂ because P has a faster diffusion rate than Pd; (2) Then, the amorphous PdP₂ NPs can convert into hollow Pd NCs through heating at 250 °C under air (Fig. 11h/i). Thanks to $v_P > v_{Pd}$ (diffusion rate), phosphorus elements in NPs perhaps first react with oxygen to form P₂O₅ and then can be extracted via reaction with oleylamine in this system; (3) Moreover, Pd hollow NCs of their outer diameter and shell thickness can be gradually increased and reduced via repeating the processes of insertion and extraction of P. It has been long known that the hollow metal NCs normally show intriguing catalytic, magnetic, and optical properties, and the resulting NPs with thin Pd shells generally exhibit increased catalytic activity and durability toward formic acid oxidation [97,179,253,347–351].

Interestingly, in 2016, Yang et al. provided a new chemical method for the preparation of cobalt phosphide nanostructures, [178] which can show superparamagnetic behaviour at room temperature and ferromagnetic properties at 2 K. In a typical synthesis, firstly, oleylamine is used to reduce Co(acac)₂ to Co metal phase. Then Co atoms can react with TOP to produce a Co₂P phase. Specifically, (1) The location at the surface of Co NPs may break at high temperatures; (2) The P atoms can be generated by the breaking of the P-C bonds; (3) The P atoms are uti-

FIG. 10

(a) Overview of the reaction pathways identified in this phosphorization process and of the most relevant parameters for each system. (b) TEM of the NCs that were prepared with Fe/P = 4 (250 °C, 1 h). The pictures showed a three-stage structure, interpreted as a hollow-Fe₂P-Fe_xO_y structure (from inside to outside). Reproduced with permission [338]. Copyright 2012, American Chemical Society. (a) STEM bright-field and (b) STEM-HAADF images of the NPs after reaction with P₄ at 150 °C. (c) Schematic of the synthesis of (Ni,Cu)₂P NPs via phosphorization. (d) STEM-HAADF images of Cu_{0.25}Ni_{0.75} NPs after reaction with P₄ at 250 °C. (e-g) Single-element STEM-EDS maps describing the distribution of Cu, Ni and P, respectively. (h) Merged STEM-EDS elemental map. The arrows indicate Cu NPs deposited outside the phosphide NPs. (i) STEM bright-field and (j) STEM-HAADF images of the NPs after reaction with P₄ at 150 °C. (k-m) Single-element STEM-EDS maps describing the distribution of Cu, Ni and P, respectively. (n) Merged STEM-EDS elemental map. (o) Schematic illustrations of different stages of phosphorus insertion. Reproduced with permission [345]. Copyright 2019, American Chemical Society.

FIG. 11

(a) The evolutionary schematics of transition from Co to cobalt phosphide NCs. (b) The crystal structures of ϵ -Co, Co_2P and CoP , TEM images of ϵ -Co (c), Co_2P (d) and CoP (e). Reproduced with permission [346]. Copyright 2011, Royal Society of Chemistry. (f) Schematic illustration of the repeated Kirkendall cavitation process that leads to the formation and enlargement of hollow monometallic NCs. (g-i) TEM images of Pd nanocubes, Pd-P intermediates, and hollow Pd nanospheres, respectively. Reproduced with permission [97]. Copyright 2017, Nature Publishing Group.

lized to react with Co atoms, which are offered by Co NPs to form the Co_2P phase as the shell. It is known that hollow Co_2P NPs can be obtained easily because the rate of initial outward diffusion of Co atoms is faster than the inward migration of P atoms, and the void can be gathered simultaneously due to the Kirkendall effect. Finally, the Co_2P phase and morphology of nanorods and hollow NPs can be formed by adjusting the amount of TOP and the anion-driven synthesis time. Increasing the duration of exposure and the concentration of the phosphorus source facilitates the growth of the Co_2P phase, resulting in the formation of one-dimensional (1D) nanorods aligned along a preferential direction perpendicular to the $[0\ 0\ 1]$ crystallographic axis. This preferential growth direction is attributed to the preferential binding of the strongly interacting TOP surfactants to the specific crystal growth faces [178]. Subsequently, upon reducing the quantity of TOP, a majority of the NPs exhibit a hollow structure.

Selenization

As a distinct anion-driven synthesis, selenization reactions have been extensively employed in the synthesis of various metal selenide nanostructures such as CdSe , Ag_2Se , CoSe , and NiSe [68,151,264]. Similar to the sulfidation process, selenization could also be utilized to forge many functional nanostructures, which have attracted considerable interest in recent decades due to the unique magnetic, [264] optical, [173,267] catalytic, [43,96] and electrochemical properties of selenide compound NPs [96,352–358].

Monodisperse hollow selenide NPs is one of the most representative structures to investigate the underlying mechanisms and controllability of the selenization reaction. Generally, during the selenization of bulk systems, cracks can form near the interface due to the stress at the dislocation and boundary generated via the annihilation of excess vacancies. Subsequently, the crack usually acts as a nucleus to promote further condensation

of the supersaturated vacancies. They also reported that the voids can begin to develop and merge at the boundary due to the high defect content and surface energy [68,69]. Specifically, selenium dissolved in DCB was added to a solution containing cobalt NPs at 455 K, [68] and CoSe NPs with hollow structures were formed via a selenization process based on the Kirkendall effect. As the reaction time proceeds, as more cobalt atoms diffuse into the shell, the growth and coalescence of the initial vacancy can be promoted by the accompanied vacancy transport. Simultaneously, this leads to the formation of material bridges [49,68,83,141,259] between the core and the shell, and provides a fast transport path for the outward diffusion of cobalt atoms. The pore growth rate decreases significantly when the cobalt core is relatively small. Inspired by the formation mechanism of these hollow CoSe NPs, numerous reports have emerged in recent decades detailing the synthesis of metal selenide NPs with hollow nanostructures, [26,48,49,68,75, 76,83,99,105,141,148,151,171, 172, 179,190,261].

Besides hollow spherical metal selenide NCs, hollow selenide nanowires can also be obtained through selenization. Similar to the injection of the DCB solution of selenium into the dispersion of cobalt NPs at 455 K, Gao et al. used a method to prepare both hollow NPs and hollow nanowires of cobalt selenide NCs through the reaction between Co NPs and selenium for about 30 min [264]. Interestingly, the morphology of hollow nanospheres and hollow nanowires can be prepared in a controllable manner via adjusting the size of cobalt NCs and alternating the magnetic field (Fig. 12a). Specifically, when the diameter size of cobalt NCs is approximately 20 nm, the Co chains or necklaces can be formed because each metal Co NP could as a single magnetic dipolar originating from their magnetic property and strong magnetic dipolar interactions in solution. Furthermore, a thin layer of CoSe_2 can grow over the wires by adding selenium without the chain structure being destroyed. Under the condi-

tions described above, when the cobalt NPs with a smaller size of 6 nm were utilized as starting materials, only monodispersed hollow NCs were observed, which is presumably owing to the weak interaction of magnetic dipolar. Moreover, the individual hollow NCs of CoSe_2 (~20 nm) can be prepared in an alternating magnetic field (the vibrational magnetic torque can lead the NCs to rotate and prevent them from reconnecting), which disrupts the dipolar interactions between the NCs. Hence, we believe that the use of alternating magnetic fields in an anion-driven synthesis may be an effective method to prepare hollow nanostructure of some magnetic metal selenide NPs such as FeSe , CoSe_2 , and Ni_2Se .

In addition to hollow structures, selenization reactions play a significant role in the preparation of core-shell NCs as well. While core-shell structures exhibit prominent optical properties, their fabrication often involves a relatively complex process. For instance, Zheng et al. successfully prepared Au-CuInSe₂ core-shell hybrid nanostructures using Se powder as the anionic source (Fig. 12d). They discovered that the freshly formed Cu atoms present on the surfaces of Au NPs possess a high tendency to diffuse into the Au NPs, ultimately leading to the formation of an Au-Cu alloy layer on the exterior of the Au NPs [359,360]. Following this alloying process, selenization of the Cu(0) acts as a critical intermediate step, enabling the subsequent growth of a CuInSe₂ shell on the surface of the Au core (Fig. 12e-h).

Moreover, Ng et al. reported a feasible method to fabricate the Ag-Ag₂Se core-shell and Ag₂Se hollow nanowires (nanotubes) [99]. The special morphology of the Ag₂Se nanotubes and dendrite-like structures can be prepared by adding the CSe₂ solution as anionic reagent into the Ag nanowires starting materials with a diameter of approximately 45 nm irradiated with a Hanovia 254 nm lamp (20 W) that was used to release the selenium source. It is worth noting that the morphology of various structures can be tuned by adjusting the time duration of the photolysis. Specifically, (1) First, the core-shell nanowires with an average diameter of 85 nm (with about 45 nm cores) were prepared under irradiation for 15 min; (2) As time evolved, voids grown around the Ag nanowires were observed, and the shell grew thicker while the core became thinner; (3) Finally, the hollow nanotubes with average diameters of 90 nm and 45 nm voids can form through gathering the vacancy after 60 min of selenization, which is accompanied with to the complete disappearance of the Ag plasmon bands. Additionally, the dendrites grown from the solution were observed after aging of the reaction mixture. Here, in most cases, the growth of dendrites followed the diffusion-limited aggregation (DLA) model during aging for a long period [69,99,361–367]. Typically, these NPs are released sequentially from sites far from the central cluster and irreversibly stuck at first contact with the growing cluster. As a matter of fact, the low density of NPs in solution and the presence of strongly coordinating agents with multiple coordinating groups are generally deemed to be the important factors for dendrite formation during the aging process. Moreover, the photolysis of adsorbed CSe₂ under ambient conditions can be used as selenium reagent to prepare metal selenide NPs, such as Ag₂Se nanotubes [99] and solid and hollow Ag₂Se NPs [105]. Here, being different from using CSe₂ as selenium reagent, Zhang et al. found a simple route to synthesize monocrystalline Au-

AgSe core-shell NPs with excellent stability by reacting the Au-Ag core-shell NPs, which act as a starting material, with selenium powder in a mixed solution of oleylamine and oleic acid at room temperature [257]. Especially, the semiconductor shells of AgSe can be further applied as a starting material for the non-epitaxial growth of hybrid shell layers along the radial direction.

As aforementioned, all of the factors such as the size of starting NPs, alternating magnetic field (usually for magnetic NPs) and reaction time can be used to adjust the nanostructure of metal selenide NPs in selenization process. To fabricate unique nanostructures by design with a controlled selenization process, the mechanism of the selenization process needs to be understood. To demonstrate the controllability of selenization during the formation process of metal selenide NPs by metal NPs, Tang et al. reported that Ag₂Se hollow and solid NPs can be respectively formed through the reaction of selenium with two types of Ag NPs (one single crystalline (SC) and one multiply twinned (MT)) [105]. Here, they report that the properties and functionalities of metal NPs can be tailored through the selenization process, which can be regarded as a crystallinity engineering process here. They used a reactive selenium reagent that was generated from the photodissociation of CSe₂ to react with single-crystal NCs. They further generated hollow Ag₂Se NPs via the nanoscale Kirkendall effect, which may be related to the diffusion rate of silver atoms being faster than that of selenium atoms during the selenization process. Here, the difference in diffusion rate can lead to the formation of vacancies and condensation into a void. On the other hand, in the multiply twinned Ag NPs, the migration of metal atoms generally along the defects (line defects and twinning boundaries), [368] which allows interdiffusion of the Se into the Ag (akin to macroscopic ‘pipe’ diffusion), thus creating solid and homogeneous Ag₂Se NCs [67]. Importantly, this work suggests that the defects contained in the initial NPs can inhibit the formation of a cavity. Moreover, they reported that the porosity of Ag₂Se hollow NPs perhaps becomes more significant upon the oxidation process. In fact, this oxidation process is similar to an annealing treatment that is generally used to improve the stability of NPs. Similarly, Pradhan et al. reported the dopant-controlled change of both the rate and directional approach of selenization in Pd(0) NCs (Fig. 12i) [267]. Specifically, Ag dopant atoms were introduced into the Pd(0) metal, initiating the selenization process and significantly enhancing the reaction rate by over 30 times compared to undoped Pd(0). This accelerated rate facilitated the occurrence of selenization throughout the Pd(0) metal surfaces, leading to the activation of the Kirkendall effect (Fig. 12j-l). In this process, the formation of Ag-Se in the Ag doped Pd(0) crystal is expected to reduce the kinetic barriers for Pd-Se formation, thus, the internal Pd atoms promptly diffused outwards and resulting in the formation of a hollow nanostructure (Fig. 12o-p). Consequently, the doped NCs transformed into hollow cubes, while the undoped NCs maintained their heterostructure and solid cuboid structures (Fig. 12l-n). Therefore, the heterovalent dopant-induced enhancement of selenization rate could trigger the shape transformation by the Kirkendall effect. These advancements will be beneficial to deeper understanding of the fundamental principles for the controllability of selenization.

Furthermore, the selenization of metal NPs is closely related to the oxidation process, such as (1) The starting materials of selenization process, like metal oxide NPs, can be prepared by oxidation process; (2) The mechanism of selenization process is similar with oxidation process, such as the Kirkendall effect; For example, Schaak et al. investigated a method to synthesize the wurtzite-type ZnSe NPs through using (not soluble) wurtzite-type (WZ) ZnO nanorods as start materials [262]. Here, the small WZ-ZnSe NCs of ZnSe NPs tend to assemble into aggregates due to the permanent dipole–dipole interaction of ZnSe. And this phenomenon also appears in the formation process of PbSe NPs and related NCs system [369,370]. Different from the WZ-ZnSe, the stable zincblende ZB-ZnSe without any ZnO intermediate can form successfully when adding anionic reagent at 100 °C and substituting ethylenediamine (en) for tetramethylammonium hydroxide (TMAH) (the other conditions remain the same). Additionally, they reported that the structure-templating mechanism can also be applied to ZnS NPs. Furthermore, this special selenization process is similar to the aforementioned preparation process of sulfides NPs and oxides NPs.

It is well known that the nanoporous hollow nanosheets generally have a large surface area and thus perform better in some emerging applications. For example, among various nonprecious electrocatalysts, the nanocages of transition metal selenides will expose more active sites, which have attracted much interest for OER [371–373].

In 2020, Hossain et al. introduced a unique nanomaterial chemical transformation process to obtain nanostructured Ag₂Se NPs by reacting Na₂Se with Ag NPs [265]. Here, Ag₂Se exhibit degenerately-doped *n*-type semiconductor characteristics and high carrier mobility. Generally, oleic acid and oleylamine can act as long ligands to coat the Ag surface to prohibit charge transport between NCs, so Ag NPs coated with those ligands were electrically insulated. Importantly, adding a Na₂Se solution could remove the organic long insulating ligands. Furthermore, the Ag–Ag metallic bond is weaker than the Ag–Se ionic bond, [374] thus the transformation of Ag NCs into Ag₂Se is preferred. Interestingly, they reported two more special testing methods to explore the anion-driven synthesis: (1) The ligand removal can be indicated via significantly reduced FT-IR spectroscopy of C–H vibration peak intensity; (2) The Ag NCs thin-film showed a distinct localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) peak at around 440 nm [375]. After the Na₂Se treatment, the LSPR peak red-shifted, quenched, and broadened. Here, the observed red-shift as the material transforms from metal to semiconductor in anion-driven synthesis can be understood in terms of a decrease in carrier concentration [376]. The intensity quenching and peak broadening are expected to arise from the irregular fusion of NC, then, resulting in a large distribution of size and shapes of plasmonic resonators [265].

Nitridation

The controllable synthesis of metal nitride NPs by nitridation has gained much attention during the last decades. However, the manipulation of nitriding reactions is hard because of the highly covalent nature of the nitrogen element, relatively large reaction temperature and lack of reactive N sources [288,289,377–379]. In most cases, the nitriding reaction takes place in the solid–gas sys-

tem owing to the high required temperatures (even up to 1000 °C). Compared with other anion-driven synthesis, the difficulty of nitriding reactions resides in the need to overcome high energy barriers to form covalent compounds. Meanwhile, to decrease the nitrogen reaction energy barrier, another difficulty is to select a suitable nitrogen source that is both active and safe. For instance, ammonia is a corrosive and toxic gas that must be used in a properly ventilated area [291]. Hence, it remains a challenge to explore a route to convert solid metal NPs into solid or hollow metal nitrides NPs via nitriding reaction by ions diffusion (with different rates) at a relatively low temperature. Zheng et al. reported a method to fabricate aluminum nitride hollow nanospheres by simply heating aluminum NPs in ammonia at 1000 °C [286]. Interestingly, the size of shell thickness and cavity diameter of hollow nanospheres structures could be controlled by adjusting the precursor NCs size, reaction time, and temperature. Specifically: (1) First, the aluminium NPs form thin amorphous oxide layer to inhibit the aggregate process; (2) Then, the vacancies can accumulate at the center of the NP because the outward diffusion rate of Al is much faster when compared with the inward diffusion rate of N atoms.

Due to the attractive physical properties of AlN NPs, such as high thermal conductivity, high electrical resistivity, and low thermal expansion coefficient, [380–382] in recent several decades, there are many studies on the syntheses AlN NPs through a nitriding reaction using Al₂O₃ as a starting material [35,284–287,383]. For instance, AlN nanomaterials can be synthesized from some ordinary nitriding reagent like nitrogen with solid carbon [380,384] and HCN, [385–388] or a mixed gas of NH₃ and C₃H₈. While it shows potential to form products with low dispersity of NCs size, all of these methods still require high temperatures and a carbothermal reduction agent. In 2006, Ma et al. reported a simple self-templated route to prepare AlN hollow sphere NPs through the reaction of a mixture of NH₃–CH₄ gases with Al NPs [285]. The thickness of the shell was about 10 nm, and the hollow AlN nanospheres showed a green emission at around 533 nm [285]. The hollow AlN NPs with cavity diameters ranging from 15 to 100 nm and wall thickness from 5 to 15 nm could be obtained by using the Al NPs as a starting material, which is similar to the size range of Al NPs [286]. Based on the aluminum mass balance between the shell and precursor, they reported that the linear dependence of nanosized hollow spheres' wall thickness and hollow cavity radius can be explained by the following formula [286].

$$\rho_{\text{AlN}} \left(\frac{4}{3} \pi (r + d)^3 - \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 \right) \frac{A_{\text{Al}}}{A_{\text{Al}} + A_{\text{N}}} = \rho_{\text{Al}} \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 \quad (24)$$

where *r* is the radius of a precursor Al NP, *d* is the shell thickness, *r*_{Al} (or *r*_{AlN}) is the density of Al (or AlN) and *A*_{Al} (or *A*_N) is the molar mass of Al (or N). After some simple algebra, they assert that *d* = *k*(2*r*), where

$$k = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{A_{\text{Al}} + A_{\text{N}}}{A_{\text{Al}}} \frac{\rho_{\text{Al}}}{\rho_{\text{AlN}}} + 1 \right)^{1/3} - 1 \right] = 0.16 \quad (25)$$

The linear regression gives *d* (in nanometer) = 0.13(2*r*) (in nanometer) + 2.9. Most importantly, the fairly close results confirm the validity of this model, which supported the assumption that the Al NPs served as starting materials in the nitridation [286]. In fact, the Kirkendall effect mechanism, which explains

the formation of nanoscale hollow structures, aligns with the hollow cobalt sulfide and cobalt selenide nanospheres, as first illustrated by Yin et al. in 2004 [68].

To decrease the nitriding temperature, some highly reactive agents can be used. For example, Jung used polymeric carbon nitride as a nitridation reagent to promote the conversion of δ - Al_2O_3 NPs to AlN NPs at 900 °C, which is the lowest temperature reported so far [35]. To reach the aluminum nitride product obtained at 900 °C, 1400 °C is needed when no carbon source is introduced.

Similarly, Zhao et al. reported that the as-synthesized $\text{a-C}_3\text{N}_{3.69}$ can also serve as both the carbothermal reduction agent and nitriding agent [389]. Accordingly, some other nitrides such as GaN and VN can be obtained by adding this nitriding agent to react with their oxides at moderate temperatures [389]. Moreover, to forge unique nanostructures through nitriding reaction, Wu et al. obtained AlN nanotubes by simply nitriding the aluminum powder [284]. Here, most of the AlN nanotubes [390] have a pseudohexagonal morphology that is consistent with the crystal symmetry, and the diameter of the nanotube was from 30 to 80 nm. Additionally, this unique nanostructure provides an ideal starting material for constructing GaN nanoscale heterostructures. They speculated the nitriding reaction would follow these two processes: (i) Some AlN species aggregate to form hollow hexagonal seeds firstly, (ii) and then, the axial along c-axis can form faceted nanotubes because the later dangled bonds of surface atoms are saturated with trace oxygen to prevent lateral growth.

Some other unique nanostructures, such as mesoporous nanowires and nanocages, can also be fabricated by nitriding reaction. For instance, Moon et al. have illustrated that titanium nitride hollow shells can be prepared via annealing TiO_2 shells under NH_3 atmosphere at 700 to 900 °C, [118] and this hollow structure of nitride could be used for electrochemical energy storage. Meanwhile, in 2017, Dong et al. reported that the titanium oxynitride mesoporous nanowires with tunable O/N ratios can be synthesized by simply annealing under ammonia flow at 700 °C [117]. Typically, this reaction process consists of three parts: dehydration, phase transformation, and nitridation (Fig. 13a). Specifically, in the first stage, $\text{H}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ NWs with a diameter of ~ 100 nm in diameter undergoes two processes of dehydration and phase transforming from white $\text{H}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ (Fig. 13c) to olive-colored $\text{TiO}_2(\text{B})$ (Fig. 13e). At the same time, NWs with mesoporous structures were formed during dehydration and phase transition (Fig. 13d). In the second stage, the nitriding reaction occurs, forming a cubic Ti (O, N) phase that is similar to the titanium nitride or TiO phases (Fig. 13g). During this process, abundant porosity is formed because of large phase transitions and the loss of oxygen atoms (Fig. 13f). Furthermore, the pore size and O/N ratios can be tuned by adjusting the nitriding reaction temperature and time (Fig. 13b-g) (details will be given in Part 5.2 Pore size).

Interestingly, in 2018, Ma et al. encapsulated CoP into an N-doped carbon shell by using polyaniline as the source of nitrogen to prevent NPs corrosion, [120] and the obtained products show outstanding activity and stability in basic and neutral electrolytes. In the meantime, Guan et al. fabricated the carbon nanotube/graphene doped with different amounts of N via

annealing a mixture containing urea and graphene oxide at 850 °C in N_2 for 120 min [272]. Importantly, the products have many active sites, which can promote the formation of nanotubes and the HER activity.

Choosing stable anionic reagents and understanding the mechanisms underpinning the nitriding process are key to preparing metal nitride NPs. Similar to the other common anion-driven synthesis mentioned previously, the preparation of metal nitride NPs through the nitriding process also requires suitable starting material and anionic reagent. Hence, we believe that future work in this field should focus on exploring the controlled fabrication of nanostructures and optimizing the practicality of anionic reagents.

Other anion-driven synthesis

Different from the common NCs prepared by oxidation, sulfidation, selenization and phosphorization, other anion-driven synthesis such as tellurization, arseniding and halogenating of metal and metal oxide template NPs have been also reported in recent decades. There are two difficulties that limit the development of these reactions and they need to be tackled urgently: (1) The large radius of arsenic, tellurium and halogen ions leads to low anions diffusion rates; (2) Besides, the anion-driven synthesis reagents for these processes usually have low reactivity and are toxic, rare and expensive. Despite the challenges, in recent years, extensive efforts have been devoted to the engineering of some NCs with unique structures through tellurization, arseniding and halogenating reactions to further improve their physicochemical properties towards some emerging applications.

Ibañez et al. reported that hollow CdTe NCs could be gained using Cd NPs as starting materials through a tellurization reaction [151]. As a matter of fact, in the reaction with TOP = Te, Cd NPs can be used to form Cd/CdTe core-shell NPs while a further tellurization process leads to the formation of hollow CdTe NPs. It should be noted that the shell thickness and crystallinity of the products are found to depend upon the relative Te and Cd NPs concentrations. Similar to using TOP = Te as an anionic reagent, Xiao et al. reported a method to achieve controlled synthesis of hollow Cu_{2-x}Te NCs via adjusting the telluride reaction time, with the tellurization starting upon the injection of TOP = Te into a Cu colloidal solution at 250 °C (Fig. 14) [149]. The interior of the hollow Cu_{2-x}Te NPs can be adjusted by tuning the tellurization parameters, such as initial injection temperature and the ratio of precursor. Briefly, the void size of hollow NCs can be increased from ~ 6 nm to 9 and 11 nm by increasing the temperature from 230 °C to 250 °C and 260 °C because a high temperature could accelerate the diffusion rate of metal ions from the core. The average cavity size of the as-synthesized hollow Cu_{2-x}Te NPs with 6, 9, and 11 nm can be obtained by adjusting the Cu to Te ratio (5:1, 5:3 and 5:5), due to the relatively large change in the concentration between the core and the solution. Hence, the decrease of the concentration of $\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2$ can generally provide a driving force for the outward diffusion of the core material.

Different from the anion-driven synthesis associated with the conversion of metal NPs to metal telluride NPs, Patil et al. reported that the thin film of self-standing cobalt telluride nanotubes can be prepared by a simple tellurization process in aque-

FIG. 12

(a) Formation of hollow CoSe_2 NCs from cobalt NP in the (1) absence and (2) presence of an alternating magnetic field. TEM image of the nanowire of hollow CoSe_2 (b) and hollow CoSe_2 NP (c). Reproduced with permission [264]. Copyright 2006, Wiley-VCH. (d) Schematic of the strategy for synthesis of $\text{Au}@CuInSe_2$ hybrid nanostructures through a multi-step injection procedure. (e) Typical SEM image, (f). TEM images, (g) EDX spectrum and (h) TEM image combining the cross-sectional compositional line profiles of an individual hybrid nanostructure. Reproduced with permission [173]. Copyright 2012, Royal Society of Chemistry. (i) Schematic presentation of a typical graded structure assumed to be formed during the selenization, containing the unidirectional approach of the selenization process in the undoped NCs and multidirectional approach of the selenization in doped $\text{Pd}(0)$, and the successive products. (j) TEM image of different NCs of the selenization process. TEM image of (k) $\text{Pd}(0)$ NCs and (l) the $\text{Pd}_{17}\text{Se}_{15}$ cuboid nanostructures. (m) Magnified TEM image of the intermediate heterostructures. (n) HRTEM image of a single heterostructure. (o) Masked FFT pattern reflecting the core only. (p) Masked FFT pattern reflected from the shell. Reproduced with permission [267]. Copyright 2015, American Chemical Society.

ous solution at room temperature using Co hydroxycarbonate film as starting materials [42]. The morphology of the hydroxycarbonate film (such as nanobeam and nanobelt) can be regulated by the type of cobalt templates and the shape of the final product of telluride NPs prepared from the anion-driven synthesis is nanotube. Typically, the kinetic process of the formation of the telluride NPs follows the general anion-driven synthesis mechanism: (1) First, when the starting material surface is fully covered with the telluride reagent, telluride shells will form rapidly; (2) As the reaction continues, the tellurium anion needs to diffuse into the reaction substrate, and this step usually requires overcoming a certain kinetic barrier. Therefore, the rate of the telluride reaction is significantly reduced, and this situation may be improved by increasing the reaction temperature. Here, the existence of the anion-driven synthesis can be indi-

cated by the color change of the starting materials, darkening. In addition, the optimum time of the tellurization can be determined using the XRD analysis. Further, the kinetics of the tellurization can also be investigated [42]. Specifically, there are two steps during the anion-driven synthesis as inferred from the XRD patterns: (1) The crystallinity of the crystal phase changes dramatically as the reaction begins; (2) Then there is no drastic change of the crystallinity of NPs for a considerable period of time, (3) Finally, the XRD patterns reveal that no further development/disappearance of XRD peaks takes place after 12 h. Additionally, the Au-Ag core-shell NPs can also be used as starting materials for tellurization. For instance, Zhang et al. have reported that the Au-Ag₂Te core-shell NPs can be prepared by using Au-Ag core-shell NPs as starting materials to react with Te powder [257,294]. In fact, tellurium is a VI group element at

FIG. 13

(a) Mechanism of formation process for the titanium oxynitride mesoporous nanowires (Ti(O,N)-MP-NWs). SEM image of $\text{H}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ nanowires (b) $\text{TiO}_2(\text{B})$ (d) and $\text{Ti}(\text{O},\text{N})$ (f), respectively. Crystals structure of $\text{H}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ nanowires (c) $\text{TiO}_2(\text{B})$ (e) and TiN (g), respectively. Reproduced with permission [117]. Copyright 2017, Royal Society of Chemistry.

the boundary of metals and nonmetals in the periodic table. In 2022, Sen et al. reported that tellurium can adopt multiple oxidation states ranging from positive to negative and a strong tendency to grow anisotropically. Furthermore, they also reviewed that many metal-telluride NP heterostructures can be obtained by chemical transformation process [391].

Metal arsenides have been less studied probably due to the scarcity and low reactivity of common arsenic reagents. Most arsenic-related compounds are toxic, which hinders their applications. Compared with the other common II-V NCs, the metal-arsenide Cd_3As_2 NCs have a number of interesting features such as a narrow band gap (~ 0.15 eV), large Bohr radius (~ 47 nm), [392,393] and widely tunable electronic structures. Additionally, the cadmium and arsenic precursors in the prepara-

tion process of Cd_3As_2 NPs usually have a suitable reactivity. Hence, Cd_3As_2 NPs have gained notable attention. Indium and gallium arsenides are also interesting materials in the field of optoelectronics [394,395]. However, while there is some research on the colloidal synthesis of metal-arsenide NCs, [394–398] it is not possible to find any mature study on the preparation of metal arsenide NPs using anion-driven synthesis methods. We expect that some relevant breakthroughs may be emerging in this field in the future.

Halogenation is also an anion-driven reaction. The diffusion of some halogen ions (Cl^- , Br^- , I^-) is a key process in the perovskite-associated anion exchange reaction [36,53–55]. These studies are associated with numerous chemical transformations of NPs. Most importantly, halogenation such as chlorination is

FIG. 14

(a) Preparation of hollow Cu_{2-x}Te NPs via the tellurization reaction of Cu NPs with Te ions at 250 °C. (b–d) TEM and HRTEM images of Cu NPs with different magnification; (e–g) TEM and HRTEM images of hollow Cu_{2-x}Te NCs with different magnification. The insets show the corresponding size distribution, selected area electron diffraction (SAED) and fast Fourier transform (FFT) patterns. Reproduced with permission [149]. Copyright 2013, Wiley-VCH.

generally combined with a galvanic exchange reaction. For instance, Zhang et al. reported a series of galvanic exchange reactions on Ag nanocubes surface to form bimetallic NPs with several different morphologies via the reaction with K_2PtCl_4 in the presence of HCl. Here, HCl and polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) play an important role to control the morphology of PtAg products (Fig. 15) [31,58]. In fact, HCl can regulate the reaction kinetics by promoting the formation of AgCl NCs on the surface of the metal Ag NPs, which act as a removable secondary template or nucleation site for the deposition of Pt metal. Specifically, at a low amount of HCl (0.23 mL of 10 mM HCl), AgCl NCs can be obtained slowly via chlorination with only one nucleation site, which is one of the corner or side of the metal Ag nanocubes. At higher HCl concentrations, AgCl NCs formed more quickly at multiple sites. Consequently, this strategy led to the formation of Pt/Ag with several unique nanostructures such as hollow nano boxes, dimers, multimers, or popcorn-shaped, consisting of one, two, or multiple hollow domains, respectively. Similarly, due to the presence of large void space and porous walls, these unique nanostructures usually exhibit a high specific surface area, which can commonly improve the catalytic activity and their performance in energy storage and energy generation.

In addition, González et al. reported that the addition of ascorbic acid could prevent AgCl deposition and allow the access to another reaction regime [57]. Furthermore, for metal halide NPs of AgCl_x obtained slowly via anion-driven synthesis in galvanic exchange reaction, this strategy also could be used to syn-

thesize Au/Ag heterodimers by using 0.4 mL of 0.5 mM HAuCl_4 solution.

Unique nanostructures

One of the main purposes of this work is to systematically review the unique nanostructures obtained through the anion-driven synthesis, which cannot be prepared by using conventional colloidal methods, and to elucidate their formation mechanisms based on anion-driven synthesis. The syntheses of these unique nanostructures all evolve using the initial materials, such as metal and metal oxide NPs with certain morphology as the starting materials with defined geometry, such as spheres, cubes, rods/wires, platelets/sheets, and tetrapods. Importantly, as aforementioned, the differences in diffusion rates between the metal ions and the anions, as well as the differences in the morphology and size of the original templates will affect the final structures of the products that are produced via anion-driven synthesis.

Specifically, to design NCs with special structures rationally, we proposed that: (1) When the size of the template is relatively small, the inward diffusion rate of the applied anion is greater than the outward diffusion rate of the metal ion, thus a solid structure with a well-preserved morphology is frequently obtained [177,214,230–232]. A limit can be set at about 20 nm, although there may be some changes for different reaction systems, because the stability of the NC structure or the reaction conditions will change with the different anion-driven synthesis systems. Meanwhile, the core-shell structure based on the tem-

FIG. 15

(a) Graphical schematic and TEM images for reactions of Ag NPs with K_2PtCl_4 in the presence of HCl under different reaction conditions, resulting in (b) Pt/Ag nanoboxes, (c) Pt/Ag heterodimers, (d) Pt/Ag multimers. After washing with solutions of saturated NaCl and 50 mM $Fe(NO_3)_3$, the (c) dimers and (d) multimers were converted to nanostructures with (e) two or (f) multiple hollow domains, respectively. Reproduced with permission [58]. Copyright 2012, American Chemical Society.

plate morphology can be formed [151,257]. Furthermore, when the diffusion rate of the anion from the anionic reagent is slower than the metal cation, a hollow structure or a core–void–shell structure will be obtained; [26,67,117,118,178,264].

(2) When the size of the template for the anion-driven synthesis is large (usually greater than 50 nm), hollow structures can be formed even if the diffusion rate of the anion is faster than that of the cation from the core (metal Pb) [193]. In addition, nanocages may also be obtained with the help of etching processes. For instance, Cu_2S nanocages with a wall thickness of 10–20 nm and with ultrasmall pores of 1 nm or less can be fabricated through the anion-driven synthesis of Cu_2O NPs with Na_2S , and the interior Cu_2O cores of Cu_2S nanocages can be etched by using HCl solution; [28,34,77,108].

It is worth noting that the addition of an oxygen extraction reagent may also lead to the formation of typical nanostructures with preserved morphology when the original substrate size is large [75]. For the special phenomenon of unique nanostructures in the oxidation process, there are several empirical rules worthy of concern:

- (1) For oxidation, the diffusion of cations produced in the metal core and external anions can be hindered as there are some pycnomorphic metal oxide shells quickly formed;
- (2) Then, the oxidation process of some metal NCs does not satisfy the general law of experience (the size of metal could directly affect the nanostructures of the metal oxide NPs). Furthermore, Wang et al. summarized the critical diameters for obtaining hollow oxide NPs from oxidation of metal NPs at 423 K [67];
- (3) Moreover, the hollow necklace structures can be obtained through the NPs self-assembly, which is due to the dipolar interaction [90,264].

In fact, as influencing factors, both the ion diffusion rate and the size and morphology of the original substrates can be adjusted, which bring good rational guidance for the controllable

synthesis of complex nanostructures. Overall, anion-driven synthesis is a relatively powerful approach to preparing NCs with a wide spectrum of morphologies including core–shell, hollow, cage-like, and other complex nanostructures (Fig. 16).

We provided an overview of several specific nanostructures that were uniquely obtained as a result of anion-driven synthesis approaches in section 3. Specifically, these nanostructures exhibit distinct morphological or compositional features that set them apart from those achieved through other synthesis routes. Additionally, a series of intriguing works have recently been reported, demonstrating the successful synthesis of specific metallic compound NPs during the anion-driven process. These works highlight not only the preparation of the NPs themselves but also their integration into, or association with, additional chemical transformations that contribute to their final properties and functionalities. For instance, Zhang et al. reported that anion-driven synthesis can be combined through galvanic replacement reaction for the preparation of several complex hollow nanostructures, [58] such as hollow nanoboxes, dimers, multimers, or popcorn-shaped nanostructures with controlled surface area.

Properties

As aforementioned, the anion-driven synthesis can enable the formation of metallic compound NPs with unique architectures and thus unique physical, chemical and functional properties. The structures obtained through anion-driven synthesis underpin many interesting properties spanning from reactivity, catalytic activity, large surface area, tunable band gap, special magnetic, optical and electrical properties. Herein, we review some of the properties of these unique nanostructures, which can be adjusted by suitably tuning the chemical composition, structure, and morphology of NPs.

Surface area

The unique nanoscopic features of materials at the nanoscale, such as the small volume and consequently higher surface-to-

volume ratio of NCs composed of hundreds to thousands of atoms, significantly differ from their corresponding bulk solid materials. The large surface area gained from the decrease in the NCs size is not only one of the fundamental physical properties of nanomaterials, but also the cornerstone for the unique functional properties and superior performance exhibited by some nanomaterials in various applications. For instance, the electronic structure, optical, and magnetic properties of NCs can be tailored by precisely adjusting their size [4]. As the size decreases from bulk materials to NCs, novel phenomena emerge, such as the size-dependent band gap observed in semiconductor NCs, [3,404] exhibited by magnetic NPs, and local surface plasmon resonance in Cu, Au and Ag NPs [405–407]. Furthermore, the enlarged surface area of NPs enhances and even initiates chemical reactions at the surface that are not feasible in the bulk, owing to the heightened reactivity of surface atoms. To further augment the surface area of NPs, anion-driven synthesis methods can be employed, transforming solid structures into hollow nanocages, multi-shell structures, and other complex nanoarchitectures. These complex nanostructures often possess small pores, thin shells, or expansive internal voids, leading to a dramatic increase in the final surface area of the product.

Here, we mainly review some representative examples of increasing the surface area of the NCs after anion-driven synthesis, and briefly describe the methods used to measure the surface area [43]. For example, Cheon et al. reported that the specific surface area (SSA) of 2D WS₂ nanosheets was 37.2 m² g⁻¹, which is about 14.6 times higher than that of their bulk WS₂ (2.5 m² g⁻¹) as determined from N₂ adsorption–desorption isotherms using Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) calculation [76,408–410]. Besides the metal chalcogenides NCs, some metal nitride NPs with unique nanostructures were also formed by anion-driven synthesis to increase the SSA. For example, the SSA of AlN NPs prepared by nitridation was generally increased. In earlier work, Haussonne et al. prepared pure AlN powder with a SSA up to 17.51 m² g⁻¹ at 940 °C [411]. However, Zheng et al. reported that the surface area of the hollow AlN NPs was 37.2 m² g⁻¹ after the nitriding process, which was less than that of the Al NPs (48.3 m² g⁻¹). They attributed this decrease in SSA to the aggregation of smaller hollow AlN NPs at high reaction temperatures, which despite their small size, contribute minimally to the SSA [286]. Furthermore, in order to establish a carbon-free and cost-effective nitriding synthesis technique to prepare ultrafine AlN powder, Zhang et al. reported that the AlN with a crystallite size of 30–60 nm can be prepared by nitridation of d-Al₂O₃ NPs in

FIG. 16

Unique nanostructures enabled by anion-driven synthesis. (a₁) TEM and HRTEM image of Co-CoO core-shell NPs. Reproduced with permission [243]. Copyright 2013, American Chemical Society. (a₂) TEM and HRTEM image of Cu-CuO core-shell NPs. (a₃) TEM and HRTEM image of Au-Cu₂S core-shell NPs. Reproduced with permission [261]. Copyright 2018, Wiley-VCH. (a₄) TEM and HRTEM image of Co-Co₂P core-shell NPs. Reproduced with permission [346]. Copyright 2011, Royal Society of Chemistry. (b₁) TEM image of Au-Cu₂S core-void-shell NPs. Reproduced with permission [46]. Copyright 2017 Springer. (b₂) TEM and HRTEM image of FePt-CoS₂ core-void-shell NPs. Reproduced with permission [255]. Copyright 2007, American Chemical Society. (b₃) TEM image of Cd-CdS core-void-shell NPs. Reproduced with permission [259]. Copyright 2008, American Chemical Society. (b₄) TEM and HRTEM image of Ni-Ni₂P core-shell NPs. Reproduced with permission [276]. Copyright 2007, American Chemical Society. (c₁) TEM image of Fe₃O₄ hollow NPs. Reproduced with permission [191]. Copyright 2008, American Chemical Society. (c₂) TEM image of Cu₂O hollow NPs. (a₂) and (c₂) Reproduced with permission [232]. Copyright 2010, Wiley-VCH. (c₃) TEM and FFT image of Cu_{2-x}Te hollow NPs. Reproduced with permission [149]. Copyright 2013, Wiley-VCH. (c₄) TEM image of CuS hollow NPs. Reproduced with permission [78]. Copyright 2012 Springer. (d₁) TEM image of Cu₂S nanocages. (d₂) TEM image of Au-Cu₂S nanocages. (d₁) and (d₂) Reproduced with permission [77]. Copyright 2011, Wiley-VCH. (d₃) TEM image of Ru-Co_xP nanocages. Reproduced with permission [108]. Copyright 2019, American Chemical Society. (d₄) TEM and SEM image of Cu_{2-x}Se nanocages. Reproduced with permission [34]. Copyright 2006, Royal Society of Chemistry. (e₁) TEM and FESEM image of NiCo₂S₄ multi-shell NPs. Reproduced with permission [179]. Copyright 2015, Nature Publishing Group. (e₂) TEM image of Cu₂S multi-shell NPs. Reproduced with permission [49]. Copyright 2012, Wiley-VCH. (e₃) TEM image of ZnCo₂O₄ multi-shell NPs. Reproduced with permission [399]. Copyright 2019, Royal Society of Chemistry. (e₄) TEM image of NiCo₂S₄ multi-shell NPs. Reproduced with permission [263]. Copyright 2021, Elsevier. (f₁) TEM image of Au-Cu₂S heterodimer NPs. Reproduced with permission [171]. Copyright 2012, American Chemical Society. (f₂) TEM image of Pt-Ag₂S heterodimer NPs. Reproduced with permission [400]. Copyright 2013, Royal Society of Chemistry. (f₃) TEM image of Au-Cu_{1.8}Se heterodimer NPs. Reproduced with permission [172]. Copyright 2022, American Chemical Society. (f₄) TEM image of Cu-Cu₃P heterodimer NPs. Reproduced with permission [270]. Copyright 2012, American Chemical Society. (g₁) TEM image of CdSe-Cd(OH)₂ core-shell nanorods. (g₂) STEM and compositional line profiles image of CdSe-Cd(OH)₂ core-shell nanorods. (g₁) and (g₂) Reproduced with permission [192]. Copyright 2009, American Chemical Society. (g₃) TEM image of Ag-Ag₂O core-shell nanorods. Reproduced with permission [247]. Copyright 2016, American Chemical Society. (g₄) TEM image of Ag-Ag₂Se core-shell nanorods. (h₁) TEM image of NiCo₂S₄ hollow prisms. (h₂) TEM image of NiCo₂S₄ hollow prisms. (h₁) and (h₂) Reproduced with permission [401]. Copyright 2014, Wiley-VCH. (h₃) TEM image of CoS₄ hollow prisms. (h₄) FESEM image of CoS₄ hollow prisms. (h₃) and (h₄) Reproduced with permission [402]. Copyright 2016, Wiley-VCH. (i₁) TEM image of Ag₂Se nanotubes. (g₄) and (i₁) Reproduced with permission [99]. Copyright 2006, American Chemical Society. (i₂) TEM image of FeP-CNT nanotubes. Reproduced with permission [132]. Copyright 2019, American Chemical Society. (i₃) TEM image of Fe₂O₃ nanotubes. Reproduced with permission [403]. Copyright 2011, Royal Society of Chemistry. (i₄) TEM image of CoP-CNT nanotubes. Reproduced with permission [331]. Copyright 2014, Wiley-VCH. (j₁) TEM image of Co₃S₄ nanonecklace. (j₂) HRTEM and TEM image of CoTe nanonecklace. (j₁) and (j₂) Reproduced with permission [264]. Copyright 2006, Wiley-VCH. (j₃) TEM image of Co_xO_y nanonecklace. Reproduced with permission [90]. Copyright 2010, American Chemical Society. (j₄) TEM image of Co₃O₄ nanonecklace. Reproduced with permission [91]. Copyright 2009, American Chemical Society. (k₁) HRTEM image of ZnS tetrapods, and, (k₂) STEM-HAADF images and corresponding EDS maps of ZnS tetrapods. Reproduced with permission [45]. Copyright 2012, Wiley-VCH. (k₃) TEM image of ZnS tetrapods, and, (k₄) Corresponding EDS maps of ZnS tetrapods. (l₁) STEM image of Co₃O₄ nanosheets, Reproduced with permission [43]. Copyright 2014, American Chemical Society. (l₂) TEM image of TiO₂ nanosheets. Reproduced with permission [87]. Copyright 2013, American Chemical Society. (l₃) TEM image of WS₂ nanosheets. Reproduced with permission [76]. Copyright 2007, Wiley-VCH. (l₄) TEM image of Fe₃O₄ nanosheets. (k₃), (k₄) and (l₄) Reproduced with permission [75]. Copyright 2020, American Chemical Society.

FIG. 17

(a) TEM image of $\text{TiO}_2(\text{B})$ -600 (b), $\text{Ti}(\text{O},\text{N})$ -700 (f) and TEM image of $\text{Ti}(\text{O},\text{N})$ -700 (c). Nitrogen adsorption–desorption isotherms (d) and pore size distribution curves (e) of $\text{TiO}_2(\text{B})$ -600, $\text{Ti}(\text{O},\text{N})$ -700 and $\text{Ti}(\text{O},\text{N})$ -800, respectively. Reproduced with permission [117]. Copyright 2017, Royal Society of Chemistry.

flowing NH_3 at temperatures ranging from 1350 to 1400 °C for 2–5 h. The surface area of these products was measured to be over $30 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ using BET method based on N_2 adsorption/desorption curves [287]. Different from the pure metal nitride NPs, in 2017, Jun Dong et al. synthesized $\text{Ti}(\text{O},\text{N})$ (titanium oxynitride) mesoporous nanowires with tunable O/N ratios in flowing ammonia at 700 °C (Fig. 17a–c), and measured the SSA of mesoporous materials $\text{Ti}(\text{O},\text{N})$ with a pore size of 20 nm to be $70.75 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ [117]. Furthermore, the SSA of $\text{Ti}(\text{O},\text{N})$ mesoporous nanowires could be tuned (Fig. 17d). Specifically, (1) The SSA of $\text{Ti}(\text{O},\text{N})$ -700 was larger ($70.75 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) than TiO_2 -600 ($29.02 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) because more vacancies were created during the anion-driven synthesis and phase transformation processes; (2) The decrease of SSA for $\text{Ti}(\text{O},\text{N})$ -800 ($49.25 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) is associated with increasing the pore size, which is possible owing to the increased mass transfer and accelerated crystal growth at high temperature (Fig. 17e) [117].

As mentioned earlier, a typical method for NPs to increase the SSA during anion-driven synthesis involves fabricate complex nanostructures. However, it has been observed that smaller hollow aluminium nitride (AlN) NPs synthesized via anion-driven methods in solid systems tend to aggregate at elevated reaction temperatures, leading to a reduction in their SSA. To address this issue, the ligand-capping strategy, which is widely employed in anion-driven synthesis in colloidal systems, is an effective method for mitigating NP aggregation. This approach works by exerting a sufficient repulsive force on the NPs through the external ligands attached to their surfaces [412]. However, the ligand agents usually mask some activity sites and reduce the electrical conductivity and the energy conversion efficiency in electrochemical processes [413]. To address these limitations, embedding NCs of metallic compounds into a suitable matrix presents an effective method to enhancing the SSA.

For instance, to prepare metallic compound NPs and embed them into the matrix by anion-driven synthesis to get larger SSA, in 2014, He et al. reported a facile and scalable *in-situ* oxidation strategy to prepare novel carbon-encapsulated Fe_3O_4 NPs embedded in 2D porous graphitic carbon (PGC) nanosheets ($\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4\text{-C-PGC}$ nanosheets) [113]. Specifically, they first prepared the NaCl coated Fe-C-PGC core-shell structures by using $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6$ as the template and carbon precursor. The BET SSA of $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4\text{-C-PGC}$ nanosheets was measured to be approximately $470 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, significantly surpassing the commercial Fe_3O_4 NPs (about $2 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) and 3D $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{C}$ composite ($\sim 168.8 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$). The size of Fe_3O_4 NPs is $\sim 18.2 \text{ nm}$, while the thickness of nanosheet is less than 30 nm. Importantly, the thin carbon shell can avoid the NPs from being directly exposed to the atmosphere, similar to the role it plays in preventing direct contact with the electrolyte in the Li-ions battery. This shell maintains the structural and interfacial stability of the Fe_3O_4 NPs. Concurrently, the flexible and conductive PGC nanosheets can suppress the aggregation of Fe_3O_4 NPs.

Similarly, Zhang et al. fabricated CoP NPs with an average size of 11.3 nm by through embedding the NPs into a matrix to form nanosheets, which were further uniformly embedded in N-doping C nanosheets via a facile anion-driven synthesis method [274]. The Co-based metal–organic framework (Co-MOF) was used as starting material. Notably, the skeleton can prevent the agglomeration of CoP NPs during the phosphorization process. The BET surface areas of CoP-1 and CoP-2 were 102.19 and $73.431 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, respectively. Herein, the MOFs exhibit a range of advantages, such as a 3D carbon skeleton, high porosity, large surface area, and controllable morphology [109,116,414–416]. When preparing CoP NPs embedded in a nitrogen-doped carbon matrix, zeolitic imidazolate framework 67 (ZIF-67) is often used as the starting material for MOFs [95,108,109,116,134,417].

However, despite the numerous studies on metal phosphide NPs reported in recent works, the controllable preparation of efficient bifunctional catalysts for oxygen evolution and reduction reactions (OER and ORR) based on metal phosphide remains a significant challenge. This is primarily due to the need for the obtained metal phosphide NPs to be uniformly distributed within the matrix. Wang et al. have developed a method to prepare CoP NPs anchored on N, P co-doped porous carbon via a simple in situ phosphorization process [109]. Although the surface area of the MOF derivatives decreased due to the porous structure being destroyed, the obtained products after thermal treatment still have a high surface area of up to $180 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ [109]. This approach represents a promising strategy for the synthesis of bifunctional catalysts with desirable properties for OER and ORR.

To further expand the SSA of CoP NPs and mitigate aggregation Ma et al. in 2018 reported the synthesis of N-doped carbon-coated (NC) CoP-NC core-shell NPs deposited on the surface of N-doped graphene (NG) sheets. This approach, for the first time, utilized polyaniline as both a source of N-doping and nucleation sites for the metal ions to synthesize CoP-NC-NG. Notably, the BET surface areas are 272.8, 112.4, and $60.6 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for CoP-NC-NG, CoP-G and CoP, respectively. The increase in surface area for CoP-G compared to CoP NPs is attributed to the graphene support, which serves as a carrier and contributes additional surface area [120]. In parallel, the total surface area of FeP NPs for practical applications has also been enhanced by embedding them into carbon nanotubes. This approach demonstrates the versatility of using matrices to increase the surface area of metallic compound NPs [132]. To precisely demonstrate the augmentation in the SSA by embedding the metallic compound NPs into the matrix, Yan et al. fabricated ultra-small NiFe_2O_4 hollow NPs with a diameter and wall thickness of only 6 and 1.8 nm respectively. These NPs were synthesized using NiFe NPs as a template and subsequent thermal oxidation [418]. The analysis of the nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms shows that the BET SSA and pore volume of NiFe_2O_4 on graphene sheets are as large as $281.3 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and $1.10 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$, respectively.

Interestingly, rather than embedding metallic compound NPs into graphene sheets, which is a common approach to enhance material surface area, in 2019, Li et al. illustrated the design of Ru-doped cobalt phosphide nanocages $\text{Ru}/\text{Co}_x\text{P-NC}$ via the phosphorization of Ru-doped Co_3O_4 NPs by the Kirkendall effect, and the nanocages are composed of numerous pores and rich small NPs. The surface area of $\text{Ru}/\text{Co}_x\text{P-NC}$ BET is $12.7 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, which is slightly lower than that of $\text{Co}_x\text{P-NC}$ ($26.8 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) because the part of the inner space of the nanocage being blocked by the dopant of Ru NPs [108].

Generally, a significant increase in the surface area of materials leads to several advantageous effects. Firstly, it increases the number of active sites available for reactions, enhancing the material's reactivity. Secondly, it facilitates the formation of an efficient contact between different components, which is crucial for promoting interfacial reactions. Lastly, it shortens the migration distance of charge carriers, improving the material's electrical conductivity. These phenomena are of particular importance for the application of these materials in energy storage and conversion technologies, among others [26,133,159,240].

Pore size

The metallic compound nanocages often exhibit numerous small pores due to the different diffusion rates of cations and anions during the anion-driven synthesis. These nanoporous nanostructures, unlike their perfect hollow, core-shell, or solid nanostructures, offer a unique template for fine-tuning pore size. This adjustability is achieved through the anion-driven synthesis method, which typically employs larger-sized starting nanomaterials. As mentioned previously, an increase in the SSA of the product is often accompanied by the generation of voids. In most cases, the difference in the pore size of NPs with unique nanostructures can directly influence the performance of their applications. More specifically, the pore size of nanocages determines the size of the relevant active molecules or drug molecules that can to the surface or be transported into the interior of the core materials [29,111,326].

Here, we mainly review the typical examples that exhibited the control of the pore of metallic compound NPs, which were prepared through anion-driven synthesis. Furthermore, we also summarize several factors that may affect the pore size of the nanostructures based on recent works. Importantly, since the pore size of the products can be controlled by tuning the reaction conditions of the anion-driven synthesis, we can improve the performance of some emerging applications. For instance, Kuo et al. synthesized the cubic and octahedral Cu_2S nanocages and Au- Cu_2S core-cage nanostructures with thin walls using Cu_2O NCs and Au- Cu_2O core-shell heterostructures as sacrificial templates, respectively. The cages possessed ultrasmall pores with sizes of 1 nm or less, which was revealed by extensive TEM characterizations and the transfer of fluorescent group [77].

The formation of these ultrasmall pores is likely related to the fast sulfidation process, resulting in incomplete coverage of the shell. Interestingly, they reported that the pore of the nanocages allows the transport of molecular anthracene and pyrene. The molecules of anthracene and pyrene adsorbing onto the surfaces of the encapsulated Au NCs as core materials were proved by the enhanced fluorescence quenching of molecules. This result perhaps corresponds to the size of the organic molecule, which can be estimated to be about 1 nm by the chemical bond. Importantly, if the pore size is less than 1 nm, the molecular anthracene and pyrene may not be able to reach the Au (core) surface through the sulfide shell. Moreover, if the pore size is larger than the size of some molecules, such sulfide nanocages perhaps can be a carrier for drug delivery.

In order to adjust the pore size of nanoporous structures, we need to first understand the mechanism of ion diffusion on the surface of nanoporous structures. Here, we use the oxidation process to illustrate the mechanism which regulates the pore size on nanoporous structures, Nakamura et al. suggested a vacancy diffusion mechanism from the internal pores into the shells of iron oxide NPs or nanowires at a high temperature of 673°C , which can produce a large occupancy vacancy in the hollow NP shell as compared to the solid NPs [239,240]. Furthermore, the large number of occupancy vacancies in the shell would aggregate into pores.

Additionally, this mechanism is also consistent with the hollow nanostructure with the large size ($> 200 \text{ nm}$) because the shell of this hollow nanostructures usually also has some smaller

FIG. 18

TEM images and statistical analyses of pore size distribution for (a, d) H-Pd-1, (b, e) H-Pd-2, and (h, k) H-Pd-3. Reproduced with permission [97]. Copyright 2017, Nature Publishing Group. SEM (g, j) and TEM (h, k) images of NiCo₂S₄ (g, h) and Ni₂CoS₄ (j, k) hollow prisms obtained after sulfidation process in ethanol. TEM images of NiCo₂S₄ (i) and Ni₂CoS₄ (l) hollow prisms annealed in nitrogen at 350°C. N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms and pore size distributions (inset) at 77 K of (m) NiCo₂S₄ and (n) Ni₂CoS₄ hollow prisms. Reproduced with permission [401]. Copyright 2014, Wiley-VCH. SEM and TEM images of samples. NiCo-glycerate solid spheres and products obtained after sulfidation of NiCo-glycerate solid spheres at 160°C for different durations: (o,r) 0.5 h; (p,s) 2 h; (q,t) 6 h. Scale bars, 200 nm. (u) N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms at 77 K and pore size distribution (inset) of NiCo₂S₄ ball-in-ball hollow spheres. Reproduced with permission [179]. Copyright 2015, Nature Publishing Group.

size pores (a pore size smaller than 2 nm is difficult to detect). Although the main vacancies diffuse into the interior of NPs and aggregate to form hollow nanostructures in anion-driven synthesis, some occupancy vacancies in the shell can also aggregate into a single pore [97]. In addition to using TEM and SEM images to visually analyze the pore size, the pore size distribu-

tions can also be obtained typically by calculation using the Barrett-Joyner-Halenda [419–421] method from the desorption branch [422,423].

To engineer the pore size of the nanostructure via anion-driven synthesis, Moon et al. fabricated the nanoporous nitrated titania spheres through nitrating hollow TiO₂ shells under

FIG. 19

(a) UV-vis spectra of the Cu NPs with different size (14 nm and 8 nm), Cu-Cu₂O core-shell NPs and hollow Cu₂O. Reproduced with permission. Copyright 2010, Wiley-VCH. (b) Schematic of anion-driven synthesis. (c) Series of high-resolution TEM images highlighting different synthetic stages of Au-Cu₂S growth. Scale bar, 5 nm. Red and yellow dashed lines are guides for the eye, distinguishing the core and shell boundaries, respectively. Reproduced with permission [258]. Copyright 2011 American Association for the Advancement of Science. UV-vis spectra of the (d) cubic and (e) octahedral Cu₂O crystals (red), Cu₂O-Cu₂S core-shell heterostructures (blue), and Cu₂S cages (green). The corresponding UV-vis spectra for the NCs with octahedral gold NC cores and the octahedral gold cores are provide (black). Reproduced with permission [77]. Copyright 2011, Wiley-VCH. (f) Schematic of anion-driven synthesis and Extinction cross Section as a function of time (indicated). Reproduced with permission [169]. Copyright 2016, American Chemical Society.

an NH₃ environment at different temperatures ranging from 700 to 900 °C [118]. Furthermore, they reported that the hollow shells of TiO₂ as starting materials and porous nitridated titania spheres have similar pore sizes ~1.0 nm, but the surface areas of the hollow shell and porous nitridated titania sphere are 46 and 62 m² g⁻¹, respectively. As aforementioned, similar to adjusting the pore size of nitride titania by changing the nitridation temperature, Dong et al. reported that the average pore sizes for the TiO₂-600, Ti(O, N)-700 and Ti(O, N)-800 nanowires were 9.85, 9.333 and 11.823 nm, respectively, which formed by corresponding temperatures at 600, 700, 800 °C, respectively.

Besides changing the temperature to turn the pore size of nanoporous structures, He et al. reported that the reaction times can also adjust the pore size of NPs [97]. Here, repeating phosphorization and dephosphorization cycles are used for the transformation of solid Pd NCs into hollow Pd NCs. Specifically, the first cycle on insertion and extraction of P can form hollow Pd NCs (H-Pd-1) with a pore size of ~7.5 nm. Moreover, the process could be further repeated to produce shallow NCs of (H-Pd-2) and (H-Pd-3) with average pore sizes of ~16.0 nm and ~19.2 nm, respectively (Fig. 18a-f). Hence, the pore sizes can be tuned by adjusting the cycle number of times of anion-driven synthesis. Additionally, they reported that the performance of catalytic activity and durability can be increased via the “inflation” of the Pd hollow NCs (by progressively increasing their pore size and reducing the shell

thickness). Besides changing the temperature to tune the pore size of nanoporous structures, He et al. demonstrated that reaction times are another crucial factor in adjusting the pore size of NPs [97]. In parallel, Yu et al. [401] and Shen et al. [179] on nickel-cobalt sulfides showcase an innovative approach where the sulfidation reaction of metal oxide NPs, harnessing the Kirkendall effect, enables the precise engineering of hollow nanostructures with tailored porosity. Yu et al. [401] revealed that by adjusting the Ni/Co molar ratio in the precursors and optimizing sulfidation conditions, hollow Ni_xCo_{3-x}S₄ nanoprisms with well-defined inner cavities and controlled pore sizes below 10 nm could be synthesized (Fig. 18g-l). These nanoprisms exhibited BET specific surface areas ranging from 22.5 to 30.0 m² g⁻¹, underlining the significance of reaction conditions in modulating porosity (Fig. 18m-n). Similarly, Shen et al. [179] demonstrated the formation of NiCo₂S₄ ball-in-ball hollow spheres with tunable interiors (Fig. 18o-t), and a Brunauer-Emmett-Teller specific surface area of 53.9 m² g⁻¹, where most pores were smaller than 10 nm (Fig. 18u). By manipulating sulfidation temperature and reaction time, they achieved control over the pore size distribution, facilitating efficient electrolyte diffusion and reaction kinetics, essential for enhanced performance in applications such as supercapacitors.

Collectively, these findings highlight the versatility of anion-driven synthesis reactions in tailoring the physical properties of NPs, particularly their porosity, through meticulous manipula-

FIG. 20

TEM image and HRTEM (inserts) images of M vs. H after cooling from 300 K in a 5 T field at different temperatures and M vs. T for ZFC and field-cooled FC samples measured in 0.01 T field of Co NPs with (a) native, (b) partial and (c) full oxidation, respectively. Reproduced with permission [242]. Copyright 2005 American Physical Society. (d) Evolutionary process of different size of Fe NCs and shell. (e–g) Temperature-dependent magnetization (M vs T for ZFC and field-cooled FC). Reproduced with permission [89]. Copyright 2013, Wiley-VCH.

tion of reaction conditions. This level of control paves the way for optimizing nanomaterial performance across diverse technological applications.

Band gap

Semiconductor NCs with any dimension smaller than their Bohr radius generally show size-dependent absorption and fluorescence spectra due to the quantum confinement effect [138,424,425]. In fact, the most studied phenomenon of the quantum confinement effect is the size dependence of the band gap for semiconductor NCs. Through confining the excitons of semiconductor NCs, the band gap can be tuned to a precise energy depending on the dimensionality and the degree of confinement [424,426]. Most importantly, for NPs of different shapes, their band gaps are determined by their smaller dimension. Hence, undoubtedly, the band gap [427–429] of some metal compound NCs can be easily changed and designed via anion-driven synthesis. Quantum dots (QDs) have attracted much attention due to their extensive optical tunability and emerging applications. However, the properties of QDs are limited by band alignment, tunability of the composition, charge carrier dynamics, and so on. To enhance their properties, heterostructured NCs (like core-shell NPs in our review) are proposed [430].

As described in Section 'Pore size', the surface area and pore size of NPs prepared using large-size NPs as starting material to react with anionic reagent can be adjusted by changing the temperature and number of times of the anion-driven synthesis. Here, for the preparation of core-shell NPs or some other hetero-structured NPs by anion-driven synthesis using solid QDs with small sizes as templates, the band gap of the NPs can be tuned by changing the anion-driven synthesis conditions

when their size is below its Bohr radius. In fact, the starting materials can have a variety of morphologies, such as spherical dots, nanorods (or nanowires), and nanosheets. In addition, the band alignment engineering [430–434] of NPs with core-shell or some other heterostructures prepared by anion-driven synthesis have been widely reported [27,31,92,100,154,229,265,270,435,436]. Although the metallic compound generally is a conductor, the band gap of products that obtained through anion-driven reaction using the metallic compounds as the starting material, can also be adjusted by changing the thickness of the shell or wall. Furthermore, it is well known that the optical and electronic properties of semiconductor NCs directly relate to their band gap [428,437]. Hence, this Section will mainly review how band gap of NPs with unique nanostructures can be designed and tailored through the anion-driven reaction and how the band tunability will influence the properties of such materials.

To illustrate the change of band gap of semiconductor NCs with unique nanostructures, a representative example is to prepare the metallic compound NPs (semiconductor NCs, band gap) by using metal NPs (Fermi levels) as starting material. Ng et al. reported that the formation of Ag₂Se nanotubes and dendrite-like structures can be achieved via UV irradiation of a CSe₂/Ag colloidal solution [99]. Due to the low band gap of Ag₂Se, the product exciton peak is likely to exist in the near-infrared region, which also explains the lack of distinct spectral features for the products. Furthermore, to prepare NPs by using metal oxide NPs as the starting material, Xiong et al. converted Cu₂O into Cu₂S with multi-shell nanostructures through a anion-driven process, which demonstrates that the band gap of NPs can be adjusted. Specifically, the band gaps of the products (with multi-shell nanostructures) of Cu₂S hollow spheres with single-,

FIG. 11

(a) Scheme of synthesis cobalt oxide nanowires by colloidal polymerization of ferromagnetic polystyrene-coated cobalt NPs. (b–d) TEM images of the polystyrene-coated cobalt NPs with NCs size, $D = 20 \pm 2.4$ nm after oxidation for 0 h (b), with $D = 29 \pm 2.7$ nm 3 h (c), and with $D = 29 \pm 2.7$ nm, 1 week (d). (e) Curves of M vs H of nanocomposites 1–4 at 27 °C: PS coated Co NPs (1), PS- Co_xO after 3 h (2), PS- Co_xO after 1 week (3), and bare Co_3O_4 nanowires after calcination at 400 °C (4). (f) High resolution magnetometry of (3). (g) High resolution magnetometry of (4). Reproduced with permission [91]. Copyright 2009, American Chemical Society. (g–k) Morphology evolution of FeCo NCs from 0 (g), 1 (h), 3 (i), 5 (j), and 7 h (k). (l) The scheme of Kirkendall effect during the hollowing process. (m) The M – H loop of NCs at different oxidation stages from pure metal NCs, core–shell NCs, and hollow NCs, (n) the corresponding saturated magnetization and coactivity field at different oxidation stages. Reproduced with permission [250]. Copyright 2018, Royal Society of Chemistry.

double-, and triple-shell show a gradual decrease from 2.10, to 1.49, and to 1.42 eV with an increasing diameter of the spheres [49].

Xia et al. synthesized a ternary compound of NiCo_2S_4 nanosheets via selective anion-driven synthesis of NiCo_2O_4 [48]. There are some arguments about whether the ternary compound NiCo_2S_4 is a semiconductor or a metal [48,438–440]. In order to solve the problem, they prepared 15 nm-thick freestanding quasi-single-crystal NiCo_2S_4 thin film and transferred it onto the Si/SiO₂ substrate to study the transport behavior. Then, they calculated the carrier density of freestanding NiCo_2S_4 thin film at 2 K which is $4.3 \times 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, and observed the typical metallic behaviour of electron–phonon scattering in NiCo_2S_4 of. Additionally, they found that the electrical transport in NiCo_2S_4 took place mainly through electrons rather than holes, and the calculated Hall mobility is $23 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, which is 115 times higher than the bulk NCs of the same material [48].

Another typical selenide is CdSe, which can be synthesized through the anion-driven synthesis of a metal cyanamide template with complete retention of morphology and crystallinity [24]. The CdNCN NPs colloidal suspension is white due to its wide band gap (~ 3.7 eV), while the corresponding CdSe colloidal suspension turns orange, also demonstrating optical band gap narrowing induced by the quantum confinement effect

[24,441]. In 2020, Tiwari et al. synthesized Pd- Co_2P - $\text{Co}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ -PdSAs/GO using NaH_2PO_2 as the phosphorization reagent. Additionally, the high current density was larger than any carbon-based metal catalysts reported previously, which is due to the formation of the pure Co_2P phase with a metallic character (electronic band gap = 0 eV) and the removal of $\text{Co}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ phase (band gap = 2.881 eV). The Pd- Co_2P NPs display a zero band gap so that the NPs have faster electron transfer kinetics during the EOR process [273].

Finally, as previously mentioned, we conclude that there are three main different methods to adjust the band gap of NPs: (1) The anion-driven synthesis of small-size starting nanomaterial (metal, and metal oxide) typically accompanied by the composition changes of nanomaterial; (2) Moreover, much of the anion-driven synthesis can be used as facile method to fabricate heterostructures, such as core–shell nanostructures and several others; (3) Some unique nanostructures such as nanotubes, dendrite-like and multi-shell structures can be prepared by anion-driven synthesis.

Localized plasma resonance and other optical properties

The localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) effect refers to the collective coherent oscillation of the free electrons in a material in response to an external oscillating electric field. Light

FIG. 22

(a) Amount of intercalated/deintercalated Li^+ ions as a function of cycle numbers at different rates with different individual electrodes and (b) On one same electrode. (c) Voltage profiles of the hollow NP electrode tested with different current rates (30, 300, and 3000 mA/g). (d) Voltage profiles showing that extensive cycling enhances the working voltages for each rate test. Reproduced with permission [240]. Copyright 2012, American Chemical Society. (e) Mechanism of method to fabricate 2D $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4\text{-C-PGC}$ nanosheets by using the surface of NaCl NPs as the template. (f) CV curves of an electrode based on the nanosheets. (g) Voltage profiles plotted for the first, second, third, 10th, 50th, and 100th cycles of the nanosheets composite electrode. (h) Charge/discharge capacities of the different materials composite electrodes and (i) At various rates for 350 cycles. Reproduced with permission [113]. Copyright 2014, American Chemical Society.

below the plasma frequency can be reflected due to the electrons in the noble metal NPs screening the electric field of the light. On the other hand, light above the plasma frequency is transmitted because electrons in the noble metal NPs cannot respond fast enough to shield it. Specifically, there are three steps to generate the LSPR effect in the plasmonic NPs [185,442,443]:

- (1) In the external oscillating electric field, like the solar irradiation in the case of photocatalysis, the electron cloud near the plasmonic NPs tends to be distributed asymmetrically;
- (2) Then, a Coulombic restoring force can be established between the positive nuclei and negative electrons, resulting in a series of oscillations for the electrons relative to the nuclear framework (like the oscillation of a stretched spring);
- (3) Due to the redistribution of charge density in the oscillations process, a new electric field in the opposite direction to the external electric field is created [442]. This oscillation and the established electric field are referred to as localized surface plasmons [444]. In order to better understand the LSPRs [445–449] in NPs, Comin and Manna et al. intro-

duced the Drude model [450] of the dielectric permittivity of metals to correlate the optical response in metal NCs [451].

As mentioned previously, the properties of semiconductor nanoclusters (NCs) can be tailored to alter their band gap and modify their optical and electronic properties through anion-driven synthesis via three distinct routes. This enhancement occurs due to the incorporation of anions that influence charge carrier dynamics, effectively tuning the electronic band structure and improving charge separation efficiency. For instance, sulfur anions can introduce deeper energy states, thereby facilitating greater electronic transitions and enhancing photoelectric properties [172,179,260]. Similarly, plasmonic absorption is determined by the morphological features of plasmonic materials. Hence, we conclude that the LSPR effect of the appropriate plasmonic NPs such as Au, Ag and Cu [452–459] can also be adjusted by anion-driven synthesis [149,172,247,249,269].

Here, we mainly illustrate the adjustment of plasma resonance of plasmonic NCs and the changes in these spectral properties of the absorption and emission of NCs in the anion-driven

FIG. 23

(a) Schematic illustration of the (asymmetric supercapacitor) ASC device. (b) CV curves of the ASC device at various scan rates from 5 to 200 mV/s measured between 0 and 1.6 V. (c) Galvanostatic charge/discharge voltage profiles. Reproduced with permission [179]. Copyright 2015, Nature Publishing Group. (d) Schematic illustration of the preparation process of multi-shelled NiCo_2S_4 hollow microspheres. (e) Nyquist plots and (f) specific capacity at various current density of NiCo_2O_4 , NiS_2 and NiCo_2S_4 electrodes. (g) Cycling performance of NiCo_2S_4 , NiS_2 and NiCo_2S_4 . (h) Coulombic efficiency of NiCo_2S_4 electrode. Reproduced with permission [263]. Copyright 2021, Elsevier. (i) Schematic of the AC//Ti(O,N)-MP-NWs Na-HEC. Charge/discharge curves (j), cycling performance (k), and rate performance (l) of Na-HEC, respectively. (m) Ragone plots of various supercapacitors. Reproduced with permission [117]. Copyright 2019, Royal Society of Chemistry.

FIG. 24

TEM images of (a) sol-gel derived amorphous TiO₂ shells, (b) crystalline TiO₂ shells, (c) nitridated shells. (d) Schematic illustration of the manufacturing process for the assembled monolayer of hollow nitridated shells for electrochemical electrodes. (e) CV curves of hollow TiO₂ and nitridated shells on ITO glass. (f) Areal capacitances of the assembled films of hollow TiO₂ and nitridated shells. (g) Galvanostatic charge-discharge curves of TiO₂ and nitridated titania. (h) Cycling performance of TiO₂ and nitridated titania supercapacitors. Reproduced with permission [118]. Copyright 2014, Wiley-VCH.

synthesis. For instance, Hung et al. prepared the Cu-Cu₂O core-shell and Cu₂O hollow NPs by using plasmonic Cu NPs (8, 14 nm; the SPRs of the absorption were centered at 600 and 578 nm, respectively) as starting materials (Fig. 19a) [232]. Importantly, the central wavelength of the SPR of Cu NPs exhibited a red-shift by the transformation process of Cu-Cu₂O core-shell NPs due to the decreased Cu size and the increased oxide shells, which is consistent with other findings [234,235,237,460]. Meanwhile, the SPR of Cu NPs will disappear by the formation of the Cu₂O hollow NPs. Similarly, Xiao et al. prepared the Cu-Cu₃P core-shell NPs by using 21 nm Cu NPs as starting materials. Unfortunately, the plasmon resonance of Cu NPs disappeared in a short time of 5 s [149]. Hence, the monotonous decrease in the plasmonic resonance intensity with a small size NPs (<20 nm) can be concluded. Furthermore, in order to interpret the optical behavior of plasmon resonance of Cu NPs with a relatively large size (>200 nm) during the oxidation, Susman et al. reported an ion-governed diffusion-controlled process under the steady-state concentration gradients, a general model for solid-state anion-driven synthesis of spherical NPs is employed to form a layered product, with consideration of the nanoscale Kirkendall effect [169]. Importantly, according to this model, the spectral evolution (like the wavelength shift) depends on the accumulation of vacancies and formation of the voids in the Cu core. Furthermore, the LSPR band of Cu can reach its maximum extinction when ~40 % of the metal is oxidized [233,236-238]. Typically, the adjustment of SPR evolution in plasmonic NPs by anion-driven synthesis requires meticulous consideration of three aspects [169]:

- (1) The initial size of NPs perhaps is a critical factor for adjusting the observed SPR trends;

- (2) The SPR property of the metal core can be changed by varying the formation of the voids, which affects the kinetics of the anion-driven synthesis, hence, the nanoscale Kirkendall effect may need to be considered;
- (3) Modifying the nanostructures in common colloidal anion-driven synthesis to adjust the SPR of metal NPs, and the partial dissolution of products have to be considered.

Compared to Cu NPs, the stable coinage metal (Au, Ag) NPs have been extensively studied and applied in the nanotechnology arena. Tang et al. reported that both the hollow and solid Ag₂Se NP can be prepared by using plasmonic Ag NPs as anion-driven synthesis template [105]. Here, the LSPR spectra of single-crystalline (SC)-Ag and multiply twinned (MT)-Ag NPs collected in different solvents were evaluated and compared. They reported that twinning defects of NPs play a key role in the formation of solid Ag₂Se NPs, and simultaneously the defects also play an important role in the attenuation of the LSPR, and significantly enhance the scattering process in the Mie theoretical work [461]. Specifically, the average full-widths at half-maximum (FWHM) of the LSPR peaks for the metal-templated silver NPs (MT-Ag NPs) is consistently larger, with a value of 0.50 ± 0.01 eV, compared to the self-assembled silver NPs (SC-Ag NPs), which exhibit an average FWHM of 0.29 ± 0.01 eV. Additionally, the plasmonic Ag nanowires show three broad peaks at ~340 and ~380, which belong to the transverse and longitudinal SPR of Ag nanowires (with 5-fold symmetry), respectively. And the plasmonic Ag nanowires can be used as starting material to prepare the Ag₂Se by anion-driven synthesis [96].

Consistent with Cu NPs, Ng et al. reported that during this anion-driven synthesis of Ag nanowires to Ag-Ag₂Se core-shell nanowire and further to Ag₂Se nanotube, the plasma bands of Ag nanowires become wider (decrease in the size of Ag nanowires

FIG. 25

(a) Illustration of the formation process of Ru/Co_xP-NC, (b) LSV and (c) Tafel curves of Co_xP-NC, Ru/Co_xP-NC, and 20% Pt-C. (d) Double-layer capacitance of Co_xP-NC and Ru/Co_xP-NC electrodes. (e) Current-time chronoamperometric response of Ru/Co_xP-NC at 10 mA cm⁻². Inset: LSV curves of the Ru/Co_xP-NC catalyst before and after 1000 CV cycles. Reproduced with permission.[108] Copyright 2019, American Chemical Society.

would lead to a decrease in the number of conduction electrons and an increase in the relaxation or damping frequency of the oscillations) and red-shift [99] (compared to the solvent, the dielectric constant of the Ag₂Se shell is increased), and the SPR intensity gradually decreases until complete disappears (form nanotube). However, the anion-driven synthesis of Au NPs are less studies than Cu and Ag NPs, which may be due to the relatively low reactivity of Au NP.

Furthermore, in order to modify the plasma resonance of NCs by anion-driven synthesis, converting NCs into heterostructures could be an effective method to change the recombination of exciton and electron. Importantly, instead of using single plasmonic NP as an anion-driven synthesis template, shell-wrapped plasmonic NPs and alloy NPs were generally used as an anion-driven synthesis template to form heterostructures. For instance, Wang et al. combined Au NPs with CdSe shells that formed Au-CdSe core-shell (heterostructure) NPs (with an average size of 6.0 nm and Au core of 2.2 nm diameter). The lattice mismatch between the core of Au NPs and the shell of CdS is minimized through the formation an alloy AuCd layer [269]. Similarly, Zhang et al. developed a strategy to prepare Au-semiconductor core-shell heterostructures with large lattice mismatch such as Ag₂S, Ag₂Se or Ag₂S_xSe_{1-x} using the Au-Ag core-shell NPs as starting materials (Fig. 19b,c) [257]. Additionally, they reported that the shell with different thicknesses leads to different couplings with surface plasmon resonance of Au NPs, then, different colors can be manifested in the product solutions. Kuo et al. reported that the Au-Cu₂O core-shell heterostructures can be used as the template for the growth of the Au-Cu₂O-Cu₂S core-shell-shell and Au-Cu₂S core-cage structures. Interestingly, the nanocages themselves have certain absorption and fluorescence properties (Fig. 19d, e). Furthermore, they compared the various UV-vis spectra of different nanostructures in sulfurization, such as

cubic and octahedral Cu₂O NCs, Cu₂O-Cu₂S core-shell heterostructures, octahedral Cu₂S nanocages and Au-Cu₂S core-cage structures (Fig. 19d,e) [77]. Specifically, they first prepared Cu₂O-Cu₂S core-shell heterostructures using Cu₂O NCs as anion-driven synthesis template. The broad bands of Cu₂O NCs and Cu₂O-Cu₂S core-shell heterostructures from ~550 nm to the near infrared regions are associated with light scattering by the relatively large Cu₂O crystals. In addition, the absorption feature is almost the same after the shell formation, which indicates that the thickness of the shell is very thin. Then, forming the Cu₂S nanocages by removal of Cu₂O core NCs can be certified by the disappearance of broad bands. Interestingly, both the cubic and octahedral Au-Cu₂O core-cage structures show a shoulder located at ~590 nm (Fig. 19c,d), which perhaps results from the SPR absorption of the octahedral Au cores.

Moreover, combining with two plasmonic NPs, such as AuCu alloy NPs will produce for bimetal alloy NPs. Zhan et al. reported that both the fcc- and fct AuCu alloy NPs exhibit the surface plasmon peak at 545 nm, which lies between the surface plasmon peak of Au (520 nm) and Cu (570 nm) [249,359,462,463]. Furthermore, the surface plasmon of AuCu alloy NPs can also be adjusted via anion-driven synthesis [171,172,175,249]. For example, Motl et al. reported that the sulfurization of AuCu alloy NPs produced Au-Cu₂S heterodimers which manifest both the plasmonic property of Au NPs and the semiconductor property of Cu₂S [171]. Importantly, the Au-Cu₂S heterodimers exhibit the plasmon resonance peak of Au NPs. The Au and copper chalcogenide heterodimers represent a unique hybrid material system, which integrates two different types of plasmon resonances in a single nanoscale entity produced by conduction electrons and valence holes, respectively [172]. In 2022, Sun et al. reported that the Au and copper chalcogenide dual-plasmonic heterodimers such as Au-CuS, Au-Cu_{1.8}S, Au-CuSe, and Au-

FIG. 26

TEM image of H-Pd-1 (a), H-Pd-2 (b) and H-Pd-1 (c). (d) Mass and (e) specific activities of the catalysts. (f) Specific electrochemically active surface areas of the catalysts. (g) Mass activities of the catalysts before and after the durability test. Reproduced with permission.[97] Copyright 2017, Nature Publishing Group.

$\text{Cu}_{1.8}\text{Se}$ can be prepared by the anion-driven synthesis of Au-Cu alloy NPs and the structural arrangements and the crystalline phases of the constituent domains could be precisely tailored by changing the chalcogen precursor concentration and the anion-driven synthesis temperature [172]. Hence, the optical properties of AuCu alloy NPs can be fine-tuned in anion-driven synthesis. When AuCu NPs are converted into Au and copper chalcogenide dual-plasmonic heterodimers, there will be a wide plasma resonance band in the near-infrared region, which correlates to the spectral signature of the Cu_xE plasmons [464–470]. Additionally, the extinction peak of Cu_xE plasmon resonance becomes more obvious with the increase of the size of Cu_xE domain. Importantly, in comparison to the Au- $\text{Cu}_{1.8}\text{S}$ and Au- $\text{Cu}_{1.8}\text{Se}$, the Au-CuS and Au-CuSe exhibited stronger plasmon resonance peaks because the free pore concentration of $\text{Cu}_{1.8}\text{S}$ and $\text{Cu}_{1.8}\text{Se}$ is much lower than that of CuS and CuSe [471–473].

In most cases, the LSPR of NPs generally change after the anion-driven synthesis occurs as mentioned previously. Moreover, the LSPR of NPs in anion-driven synthesis also has some other interesting functions. Specifically, (1) For several light concentrators in solar cells, their properties stem from the possibility of the LSPR appearance, which induces the collective oscillations of free charge carriers [449,451]. (2) Due to different structures corresponding to different spectral properties, these optical maps can also be used to partially prove the occurrence of the reaction and detect the process of the anion-driven synthesis, and may even illustrate the characteristics of the anion-driven synthesis. (3) On the other hand, for plasma resonance, the initial template

of anion-driven synthesis such as metal NPs, the amounts can be quantitatively measured through an inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscope [89]. Generally, in most cases, the adjustment of the LSPR effect can be achieved by changing the anion-driven synthesis of the Cu, Ag, Au, and their alloys (like AuCu) NPs.

Magnetic properties

Ferromagnetic NPs are an important class of NPs whose magnetic properties are closely related to anisotropy, including shape and structure, and surface anisotropy [106,474–476]. Ferromagnetism originates from the coherent exchange interactions of free electrons and electronic spin-spin, and spin-orbit, which fix their magnetic moments in a specific orientation within a structure. In fact, the electron interaction of magnetic materials will be confined when the dimension is reduced to the nanometer scale. Furthermore, the ferromagnetism of NPs will become dimension-dependent, and the magnetization values and coercivity can be rationally controlled by adjusting the size and shape of NPs [85].

In most cases, magnetic NPs are increasingly utilized in various emerging applications, such as biological, medical, and engineering applications [106,477–484]. For instance, some magnetic NPs can play a key role in the catalysis of some chemical reactions [73,102,106,178,343,480,485]. Here, we mainly overview some typical examples of modified magnetic properties of NPs which are prepared through anion-driven synthesis. Furthermore, we will illustrate the mechanisms of their properties with unique nanostructures that are adjusted by the anion-driven syn-

FIG. 27

(a) The response to 100 ppm CO of hollow Cu_{2-x}Te based sensor as a function of operating temperature; (b) The response of hollow Cu_{2-x}Te -based sensor at 260°C and the linear fitting (dashed line); (c) Dynamical response-recovery curve of the sensor exposed to different concentrations of CO; (d) Response transients of hollow Cu_{2-x}Te -based sensor to 100 ppm CO at the operating temperature of 260°C (The inset shows three periods of the response curve); (e) Schematic diagram of CO gas sensing process of hollow Cu_{2-x}Te NCs. Reproduced with permission [149], Wiley-VCH. Copyright 2013. (f) Effect of operating temperature on the gas response of (f1) Co_3O_4 nanorods and (f2) commercial Co_3O_4 powder to 50 ppm CO gas. (g) Repetitive response of Co_3O_4 nanorods to 50 ppm CO gas. (h) Response of Co_3O_4 nanorods for different gases. Reproduced with permission [565]. Copyright 2010, Elsevier.

thesis. Several metal NCs, such as iron, cobalt and nickel, have certain magnetic properties. When anion-driven synthesis occurs, the magnetic properties of the nanomaterials will change continuously due to the changes in chemical composition, size, and shape of the NPs. In 2005, Tracy et al. reported that the magnetic properties of Co NPs can be adjusted by changing the degree of oxidation [242]. Furthermore, they observed three distinct magnetic NCs, such as cobalt NPs with (a) native (has a thin (1.0 nm) CoO shell), (b) partial (has a thicker (3.2 nm) antiferromagnet CoO shell with ferromagnet Co core), and (c) full oxidation. Specifically, (1) For M vs. H curves (Fig. 20a2), the native sample with a thin CoO shell exhibits no exchange shift (H_{EB}) in a 5 T field because Co cores are too small to sustain domain walls (and are single-domain magnets). Under high fields, however, the curves do not exactly overlap, and they conclude that this additional component is caused by the thin CoO shell. Meanwhile, in dc (direct current) measurements [486–488] of the native sample (Fig. 20a3), they found that the blocking temperature (T_B) of the Co NPs was 120 K (Co is ferromagnetic when

$T < T_B$, and for $T > T_B$ it is superparamagnetic). (2) For dc measurements in Fig. 20b3, after oxidizing the Co NPs to form a partially oxidized product, the T_B of Co core increased to 170 K. (3) Finally, the sample (Co NPs) is fully oxidized into CoO, and there no peak appeared, which corresponds to a ferromagnetic core becoming superparamagnetic (for Fig. 20c3). Here, they conclude that beyond a minimum CoO shell thickness, exchange biasing (EB) [489] could greatly stabilize the magnetic moments (to higher temperatures) and enhance the anisotropy of Co NPs. Importantly, the nanomaterials can exhibit an additional unidirectional anisotropy when they contain an interface between a ferromagnet and antiferromagnet (and be cooled in a magnetic field, then achieve magnetic coupling at the interface).

Furthermore, this special effect of EB was first discovered in the oxidation process of Co NPs. Additionally, these exchange-biased Co-CoO core-shell NPs have important technological applications, such as magnetic access memory and giant-magnetoresistance-based spin valves (that are used in hard drive read heads) [242,490–495]. Nevertheless, in the subsequent

FIG. 28

(a) Illustration of a possible mechanism accounting for FePt-CoS₂ yolk-shell NCs killing HeLa cells. HR-TEM images of FePt-CoS₂ yolk-shell (b) and hollow CoS₂ (c). Optical microscopy images of HeLa cells incubated for (d) 48 h with 5 µg/mL of FePt-CoS₂ NCs and growth medium as the negative control (e). (f) MTT assay of FePt-CoS₂ yolk-shell NCs on HeLa cells at 1.0, 2.0, and 4.0 µg/mL, respectively. Reproduced with permission [255]. Copyright 2007, American Chemical Society.

works, the low-temperature behavior of cobalt NPs with partial oxidation shows numerous unusual properties, as follows:[242]. (1) M_S of the Co core increases significantly as the temperature is lowered. This is contrary to the expectation that M_S should be independent of temperature in this range. (2) H_{EB} and H_C appear to be suppressed. (3) The M vs H curve splits into two highly asymmetric lobes. Actually, each of these observations can be explained by using a simple model, considering only the core magnetization, EB, and other interface effects in the partially oxidized sample, they concluded that $M_{core} = M_{partial} - 0.947M_{full}$, which can be used to describe the unusual M vs H curves for partially oxidized NPs at low temperature [242].

Similarly, to adjust the magnetic properties of magnetic metal NPs by oxidation in a colloidal system, Peng et al. prepared monodisperse crystalline hollow Fe₃O₄ NPs with an overall diameter of 16 nm and an oxide shell thickness of around 3.5 nm by using core-shell Fe-Fe₃O₄ NPs (diameter is 13 nm, 8 nm core/2.5 nm shell) as starting materials at 250 °C. Here, the hollow Fe₃O₄ NPs with the shell containing small Fe₃O₄ magnetic grains are superparamagnetic at room temperature. Interestingly, the hollow Fe₃O₄ NPs prepared by controlling anion-driven synthesis at 210 °C have a saturation moment M of 47.9 emu/g (about 60 % of approximately 16-nm solid Fe₃O₄ NPs (83 emu/g)) and cannot be saturated magnetically in fields as high as 1 T (unlike solid NPs). Furthermore, An et al. reported that the solid Fe₃O₄ metal NPs (20 nm) were used as starting materials to form hollow metal phosphite NPs, and then the magnetiza-

tion behavior of Fe₃O₄ NPs was changed greatly from superparamagnetic to paramagnetic [191]. Similarly, Yang et al. synthesized the cobalt phosphide nanorods and hollow NPs via using anion-driven synthesis of phosphorization between Co atoms and P atoms from TOP, showing superparamagnetic behavior at room temperature [178].

Besides regulating the magnetic properties of Co or Fe NPs by controlled oxidation in the colloidal system, Ni NPs can also be adjusted by anion-driven synthesis. Compared to the oxidation of Fe and Co NPs, Ni NPs generally require higher temperatures to transform to NiO. Peck et al. reported that Ni-NiO core-shell NPs with a shell thickness of 2–3 nm can be obtained by using Ni NPs as starting materials to react with atmospheric oxygen at 200 °C. Moreover, they reported that Ni-NiO core-shell NPs have decreased superparamagnetic T_B and no H_{EB} (but a small enhancement in the coercivity (H_C) signifies weak exchange bias) because the NiO moments cannot pin the core moment in moderated applied fields due to the amorphous and thin thickness of NiO shell. In fact, compared with bulk materials, characterizing the magnetic properties with anion-driven synthesis of magnetic NPs remains challenging.

In 2013, Yoon et al. successfully characterized the magnetic and oxidation properties of Fe NPs [89]. Here, it is worth noting that the coercivity of differently sized NCs could be estimated by the classical Bean-Livingston mode [89,496–498] (Fig. 20d). Importantly, the magnetic properties of Fe NPs such as saturation magnetization, magnetic anisotropy, and intrinsic coercivity, which

FIG. 29

(a) Schematic illustration of the synthetic route of Au-Cu_{2-x}S-FA core-shell NPs and in vivo applications for SERS/PA imaging-guided PTT in cancer. (b) In vivo IR thermal images of mice after the intravenous injection of PBS, Au-CuS NPs, or Au-CuS-FA NPs upon 808 nm laser irradiation (0.72 W cm⁻²). (c) Tumor temperature variation in different groups as a function of laser irradiation time. (d) Tumor growth curves for different treatments. (e) Average weight of tumors collected from the mice 14 days after treatment. Reproduced with permission [261]. Copyright 2019, Wiley-VCH.

are similar to those of bulk material all can be measured by Bean-Livingston model. Specifically, the temperature-dependent magnetization can be shown by using zero-field cooled (ZFC) and field-cooled (FC) curves (Fig. 20d). For instance, the Fe-Fe₂O₃ core-shell heterostructure NPs (with a core diameter of 13.6 nm) show the presence of two blocking temperatures ($T_{B1} > T_{B2}$), which is related to the separate occurrence of superparamagnetism [499–501] in the Fe core and the oxide shell. When the core size is reduced to 11.6 nm, the decrease of T_{B1} (58 %) is strongly correlated with the expected reduction (62 %) of anisotropy energy, which arises from the smaller Fe-core volume. Here, T_{B1} was $\approx 8 \times 10^5$ erg cm³, which is slightly larger than that of the magnetocrystalline [502–505] anisotropy constant of bulk material ($\approx 5 \times 10^5$ erg cm³). Meanwhile, T_{B2} remains relatively constant for all NPs, which is close to the T_B of hollow NPs (Fig. 20e-f) [89]. Additionally, they concluded the critical diameter for superparamagnetism in Fe NPs: all Fe NPs with a core diameter (D_c) ≤ 11.6 nm were superparamagnetic and $D_c > 11.6$ nm were ferromagnetic via measuring by field-dependent magnetization.

Additionally, in anion-driven synthesis, the magnetic interaction of NPs can also be used as the driving force to direct the self-assembly and then form some unique nanostructures. For example, Gao et al. prepared nanowires of hollow NPs of cobalt selenide via magnetic-dipolar-interaction-induced self-assembly of cobalt NP [264]. Herein, to verify the accuracy of this mechanism, they present evidence from two different aspects:

- (1). When the size of cobalt NCs is 6 nm, the magnetic dipolar interaction will not strong enough to form wires of hollow CoSe₂ due to its relatively small size;
- (2). On the other hand, when 20 nm Co NPs are in an alternating magnetic field and there are no wires of hollow CoSe₂ NCs, because the alternating magnetic field destroys the driving force of the NPs self-assembly.

In a similar approach, Keng et al. reported that the combination of magnetic dipolar assembly and oxidation of dipolar NPs can be used as a facile and robust method to prepare hollow cobalt oxide (Co₃O₄) nanowires by using the colloidal polymer-coated of ferromagnetic cobalt NPs as starting materials (Fig. 21-a-d) [91]. The overlay hysteresis curves of (applied magnetic field (H) vs. magnetization (Ms) of nanocomposites) show that both the saturation magnetization (M_s) and coercivity (H_c) are significantly decreased after the magnetic dipolar self-assembly and the anion-driven synthesis, which was associated with the formation of antiferromagnetic CoO and Co₃O₄ (Fig. 21e). Specifically, the native polystyrene-coated cobalt NPs (PS-Co NPs) showed weak ferromagnetic behavior at room temperature ($M_s = 41.2$ emu/g; $H_c = 713$ Oe). After conducting oxidation in DCB for 3 h, the ferromagnetic PS-CoO materials exhibit a significant decrease in the saturation magnetization at room temperature ($M_s = 4.6$ emu/g; $H_c = 362$ Oe), which was attributed to the presence of residual metallic cobalt as verified by the XRD. Meanwhile, the magnetization and coercivity behaviors were also decreased by the oxidation for 1 week, which further exhibits a linear relationship of magnetization (M) and applied field (H). However, its high-resolution magnetic intensity measurements also exhibited weak ferromagnetism due to the presence of trace amounts of Co metal NP ((3), Fig. 21f). Additionally, the calcined Co₃O₄ nanowires ((4), Fig. 21f) showed a linear magnetization curve with a reduced M value even in the high-resolution magnetometry, which was well consistent with the paramagnetic behavior of Co₃O₄ NPs.

Similarly, Kim et al. synthesized Au-Co₃O₄ nanowires from ferromagnetic Au-Co core-shell NPs, which is also defined as a combination of magnetic dipolar NPs assembly and oxidation [90]. Different from using the Au-Co core-shell magnetic NPs as a template to modify their magnetic properties, Zhang et al. reported that the magnetic properties of FeCo alloy NPs can be

adjusted via changing the reaction time of anion-driven synthesis (Fig. 21g–i) [250]. Specifically, the adjustment process of alloy FeCo NPs has the following five steps (Fig. 21m, n): (1) Consistent with previous reports about the high saturation magnetization of FeCo NPs, [506–509]. FeCo NPs of 9.6 nm have a high saturation magnetization of 124 emu/g and a coercibility of 200 Oe at initial oxidation time (0 h); (2) As the oxidation evolves for 1 h, the NPs are gradually oxidized at the surface, and the saturated magnetization of the FeCo-Co_{1-x}Fe_x⁽²⁺⁾Fe₂⁽³⁺⁾O₄ core-shell NP is decreased to ~100 emu/g. However, the coercive field is slightly increased to 310 Oe; (3) When the iron oxide is formed, and the Co is then oxidized and diffused into the iron oxide to form CoFe₂O₄ phase. Here, they concluded that the formation of CoFe₂O₄ structure can increase the coercive field due to strong spin-orbit coupling. (4) As the oxidation time increases from 3 h to 5 h, the saturation magnetization undergoes a gradual decrease, from approximately 90 emu/g to 82 emu/g. Concurrently, the stress field exhibits a slight increase, reaching 420 Oe after 3 h and 530 Oe after 5 h of oxidation; (5) In the final state of the hollow crystal, where the saturation magnetization attains a value of 78 emu/g and the stress field reaches 610 Oe, it is observed that the FeCo cores have undergone a complete transformation or removal, resulting in their non-detection within the structure.

Electrical conductivity

As mentioned previously, the unique nanostructures obtained by anion-driven synthesis generally have a large surface area, high porosity, and modified morphology, and they can also effectively improve the electrochemical performance by the three typical methods: (1) Shortening the diffusion distance of ions; (2) Increasing the contact area between the active material and the electrolyte; (3) Improving the conductivity, and providing internal expansion space in some emerging application fields, such as Li ions battery, catalysis and supercapacitor.

Furthermore, electrical conductivity, as a physical property of semiconductor NCs, is undoubtedly an important aspect that directly affects nanomaterial applications [74,91,96,99,116,117,132,163,291]. Specifically, when the applications involve charge transport and transfer, the conductivity [510–516] of the materials prepared by anion-driven synthesis will play an important role. Generally, due to the changes in the crystal structure and chemical composition of the products in anion-driven synthesis, the electrical properties will change as much as any other physical properties. Here, we briefly introduce the changes in the electrical conductivity of some materials fabricated by the anion-driven synthesis.

For instance, Zolotavin et al. prepared nanofilms consisting of Pb-PbSe core-shell NPs via anion-driven synthesis by using Pb NPs as starting materials [177]. It is noteworthy that the surface of Pb NPs tends to readily form a thick PbO shell, and the presence of ligands and this oxide shell on the Pb NPs surface significantly hamper the electrical conductivity. Therefore, this needs to be solved to produce nanostructured superconductors using bottom-up approaches. Specifically, nanostructured superconductors allowing a reduction of the charging energy and increasing the Josephson energy were produced following the two necessary steps: (1) Removing the ligand by using hexamethyld-

isilane, and the films still show a resistance larger than 10¹¹ Ω/sq; (2) By employing selenization, the PbO shell can be transformed into a PbSe shell, which possesses a significantly lower barrier and a higher dielectric constant. Importantly, compared with bulk films, the kinetic inductance in granular films will be greatly enhanced [177,517]. Furthermore, if oxidation is prevented, high kinetic energy inductors can be used for optical inspection in the infrared and microwave regions in the future.

In addition to removing the ligands and the oxide shell on the surface of the Pb NPs, embedding the NPs into the matrix with good electrical conductivity is also a common method to improve their charge transport properties and thus enhance the performance, which render them suitable in a range of applications, such as lithium ions battery, electrolysis of water and solar cell [95,96,116,132].

Application

As mentioned above, the unique nanostructures produced through anion-driven synthesis can be used in several practical applications. While numerous applications can benefit from the materials produced by anion-driven synthesis, we will focus the discuss on some applications in the fields of energy and biomedicine such as lithium-ion batteries, catalysis, supercapacitors, sensor, solar cells, and drug delivery. We will also elaborate the underlying mechanisms that underpin their high performance in a variety of applications.

Lithium-ion battery

The intensification of environmental pollution and climate change associated with the widespread reliance on fossil fuels is compelling us to swiftly transition to a new energy paradigm. However, a complete transition to an electrified society requires the development of high-performance electrochemical energy storage technologies both for electric transportation and the integration of renewables into the grid. Future batteries should have higher energy and power density, be efficient, durable, and cost-effective, and they should be made based on non-toxic and relatively abundant materials. Nowadays, lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) [74,91,96,104,112,115,179,518–520] with relatively high energy and power densities, are not only the power source of choice for popular consumer electronics, but also have great potential for application in electric vehicles. The commercial anode and cathode materials used currently have been highly optimized and are close to reaching their theoretical limits. For example, the commercial graphite electrode delivers a low theoretical specific capacity (372 mAh/g). Hence, exploring alternative anode and cathode materials with higher charge/discharge rate, high energy and power density, reversible capacity and long cycle life, more environmental friendliness, low cost, and the ability to be produced at large scale has become a highly appealing task worldwide [104,115,116,240,519]. Materials with high surface area and porosity prepared by anion-driven synthesis are expected to is a promising candidate for high energy and power density of anode materials for LIBs. Here, we mainly review the methods of improving the electron-chemical performance of LIBs via fabricating new nanostructures through anion-driven synthesis.

Electrode materials with hollow nanostructures are advantageous over their counterpart of solid NPs. Specifically, Shevchenko et al. obtained hollow iron oxide NPs by an oxidation process, and explored their electrochemical properties using hollow NPs as a cathode (Fig. 22a) [240]. They reported that the hollow iron oxide NPs have high capacity (~132 mAh/g at 2.5 V), high Coulombic efficiency (99.7 %), superior rate performance (133 mAh/g at 3000 mA/g) and excellent stability (no fading at fast rate during more than 500 cycles) as LIBs electrode cycling in a high voltage range [240]. In fact, due to the different diffusion rates of metal and oxygen ($D_{\text{metal}} > D_{\text{oxygen}}$) in oxidation process, the formation of hollow metal-oxide NPs is mainly ascribed to the incorporation of the cation vacancies. Therefore, the iron oxide hollow NPs can be efficiently utilized for reversible Li-ion intercalation to enhance the capacity in the conversion reactions without structural change because iron oxide hollow NPs possess high concentration of cation vacancies. Additionally, iron oxides show many advanced properties, such as very large capacities (up to 1007 mAh/g), low cost, easy fabrication, and low toxicity, making them attractive candidates for LIB electrodes. Moreover, the hollow nanostructures generally provide a faster diffusion for Li-ion insertion/removal compared to solid NPs of the same mass [240,521–524]. Herein, to validate this hypothesis, cycling tests were conducted on the electrodes within the high voltage range of 4.5 – 1.5 V. Remarkably, during these tests, a reversible capacity of 192 mAh/g was achieved, corresponding to the intercalation of 1.1Li⁺ ions at a current density of 30 mA/g, with a Coulombic efficiency of 98.7 % and excellent capacity retention (Fig. 22a). Notably, the preservation of the hollow morphology further confirms the reversible intercalation of Li⁺ ions into the vacancies, indicating minimal structural alterations, unlike the typical conversion reactions observed in transition metal oxides [525]. After rigorous cycling at a high rate, electrodes exhibited near-theoretical capacity (221 mAh/g) at a slower rate, validating the resilience of hollow iron oxide NPs with 44 % (1.32 Fe atoms) vacancies (Fig. 22b). Extensive cycling at a slow rate not only influenced the capacity but also modified the voltage profile, as illustrated in Fig. 22d, e, and f. These findings indicate that a higher concentration of Li⁺ can intercalate into the hollow NPs at elevated voltages. Consequently, high current densities of 104 mAh/g at 2.5 V and 63 mAh/g at 3.0 V (at a rate of 30 mA/g) were achieved in this work, exceeding previously reported values for iron oxide NPs [526].

Furthermore, in order to prepare more complex hollow nanostructures for promoting the performance of LIBs, such as, high specific capacity, rate capability and ameliorated cycling performance, Wang et al. reported that the uniform multi-shell Co₃O₄ hollow spheres (in high yield) with high purity were synthesized by using the hard-template method [518]. Similarly, because the porous hollow multi-shelled Co₃O₄ structures have a shorter lithium-ion diffusion length and can guarantee more lithium-storage sites, and sufficient void space to buffer the volume expansion, the LIBs using the hollow multi-shelled Co₃O₄ as anode materials exhibited excellent rate capacity, good cycling performance, and an ultrahigh specific capacity (1615.8 mAh/g at the 30th cycle) [518]. Here, the multi-shelled Co₃O₄ structure is prepared by template methods (the hydrated cobalt ions ([Co(H₂O)₆]²⁺) was absorbed in the carbonaceous microspheres

(CMSs), and heated in air to 500 °C for 1 h), the number of shells and the interior structures of Co₃O₄ can be accurately controlled by controlling the size and the diffusion rate of the [Co(H₂O)₆]²⁺ and the ion absorption capability. Being different from relying on cumbersome template mediation strategies to generate complex internal structures, Xue et al. reported that uniform multi-shell Co₃O₄ hollow spheres can be prepared by using Co NPs as a template [399]. Meanwhile, this facile universal self-templated approach was used to synthesize a series of multi-shelled (single-, binary- and ternary- shell) hollow metal (Co, Mn-Co, Ni-Co, Ni-Co-Mn, etc.) oxide spheres (such as ZnCo₂O₄). Due to their unique nanostructures, multi-shelled hollow ZnCo₂O₄ spheres exhibited high specific capacity, excellent cycling durability (1200 mAh·g⁻¹ after 200 cycles at 0.1 A/g) and prominent rate capability (730 mAh·g⁻¹ at 5.0 A/g). Despite these exciting advances, present studies on complex hollow structures (like multi-shelled nanostructures) for LIBs are generally limited to metal oxides [403,527–531]. In the future, some other complex hollow nanostructures perhaps can be prepared through anion-driven synthesis for super LIBs, although there are many challenges at the moment.

Additionally, hollow or other complex hollow nanostructures prepared by anion-driven synthesis can as attractive anode material for LIBs with two potential advantages: (1) Provide a high concentration of cation vacancies, and, (2) Offers faster diffusion for Li ions uptake/removal as compared to the solid NPs. On the other hand, this anion-driven synthesis method for preparing unique nanostructures NPs for LIBs electrode material usually needs to remove the ligands (reduce the conductivity), which may unfortunately lead to NP aggregation. Here, embedding these NPs (prepared by anion-driven synthesis) into the matrix (with excellent conductivity) can not only avoid the aggregation of NPs, but also promote the conductivity of NPs, which is perhaps a practical method to prepare high performance electrode material for LIBs.

In the earlier work, besides oxidizing the metal NPs into metal oxide NPs, some studies reported the oxidization of the metal NPs on graphene (conductive carbon) to improve the efficiency of metal oxide-base electrode materials for LIBs because matrix material of graphene has superior electrical conductivity, high surface-to-volume ratio, ultrathin thickness, structural flexibility, and chemical stability. Similar to embedding the metal oxide NPs into the matrix by anion-driven synthesis, He et al. fabricated novel carbon-encapsulated Fe₃O₄ nanosheets by an oxidation process. Importantly, this oxidation process is a facile and scalable *in-situ* synthesis method to embed Fe₃O₄ NPs into 2D porous graphitic carbon nanosheets (Fe₃O₄-C-PGC nanosheets), which are also further used as LIB anode material (Fig. 22e) [113]. The nanosheets with a thickness of less than 30 nm coated Fe₃O₄ NPs (~18.2 nm), can effectively avoid the direct exposure of Fe₃O₄ to the electrolyte and thus preserving the structural and interfacial stabilization of Fe₃O₄ NPs. Moreover, the Fe₃O₄-C-PGC electrode exhibited an extremely high capability of 858 mAh/g at 5C, 587 mAh/g at 10C, and 311 mAh/g at 20C (1C = 1 A/g).

Additionally, the 2D nanostructured electrode also exhibits extremely excellent cycling performance at high rates, briefly, only 3.47 % capacity loss after 350 cycles at a high rate of 10C.

Here, Fig. 22f shows that the first four cyclic voltammograms (CV) curves of the Fe₃O₄-C-PGC composite electrode at room temperature:

(1) In the first discharge cycle, two well-defined peaks are observed at 0.97 and 0.60 V (vs Li⁺/Li) between 0.0 and 3.0 V at a scan rate of 0.1 mV/s;

(2) The peak intensity drops significantly in the second cycle, which is attributed to the occurrence of side reactions to form solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) on the electrode surfaces. Typically, the lithiation reaction of Fe₃O₄ contains electrochemical oxidation and reduction process of Fe and Fe₃O₄ NP (Fe₃O₄ ⇌ Fe), including step 1, Fe₃O₄ + 2Li⁺ + 2e⁻ → Li₂(Fe₃O₄) and step 2, Li₂(Fe₃O₄) + 6Li⁺ + 6e⁻ → 3Fe⁰ + 4Li₂O [113]. In fact, it is well-known that the lithium storage capacity of Fe₃O₄ is mainly achieved through the reversible conversion between Li⁺ and Fe₃O₄, and forming Fe NCs dispersed within a Li₂O matrix;

(3) The relatively low initial Coulombic efficiency of representative discharge/charge voltage profiles of Fe₃O₄-C-PGC nanosheets may be caused by the irreversible capacity loss, which also includes the inevitable formation of SEI and decomposition of the electrolyte. As shown in Fig. 22g, compared with the reversible capacity of 1003 mAh/g after 50 cycles, the bare carbon exhibits a very low reversible capacity of about 305 mAh/g after ~20 cycles, which illustrates that the bare carbon nanosheets might contribute little to the Li storage capacity of the Fe₃O₄-C-PGC nanosheets. Moreover, as displayed in Fig. 22h, the electrode of the 3D Fe₃O₄/C composite prepared without using NaCl shows significantly lower capacity and weaker cycling performance, which further verifies the advantages of using this special method with the assistance of the water-soluble NaCl NPs to fabricate the Fe₃O₄-C-PGC nanosheets for LIBs. As shown in Fig. 22i, it provides a reversible capacity of 963 mAh/g when first cycled 50 times at C, 932 mAh/g after 100 cycles at 2C, 868 mAh/g after 150 cycles at 5C, and 570 mAh/g after 200 cycles at 10C, which exhibits an extremely durable high-rate capability of the Fe₃O₄-C-PGC composite electrode.

Different from embedding the NPs into conductive carbon materials via anion-driven synthesis, Co₃O₄ NPs that were embedded into a matrix to form nanocages have been reported, which can be fabricated via a phosphorization process by using Co-MOF as a template [520]. The nanocage exhibits good rate capability and cycling stability as LIB anode materials, briefly, after 100 cycles at a high specific current of 500 mA/g and the LIB anode maintains a reversible charge capacity of 810 mAh/g.

Besides embedding Co₃O₄ NPs into a matrix to form nanocages, in 2017, Zhu et al. successfully synthesized cobalt phosphide NPs by utilizing ZIF-67 as a sacrificial template. The subsequent phosphorization process, conducted under an argon atmosphere, effectively embedded the cobalt phosphide NPs into a nitrogen-doped carbon matrix [116]. Owing to their unique architecture characteristics and large surface area, the active material exhibits a superior specific capacity of 522.6 mAh/g after 750 cycles at a current density of 200 mA/g and outstanding cycling stability up to 2000 cycles at a high current density of 500 mA/g. Additionally, they reported that the electrochemical performance of cobalt-base materials for LIBs can be enhanced by (1) Developing the cobalt-based materials into nanoscale; (2) Coating or doping with conductive carbon; (3)

Designing and fabricating unique nanostructures (hollow sphere or multi-shelled hollow structures).

Because the global distribution of Na resources is far wider than that of Li resources, and Na salts are more affordable than Li salts, the sodium-ion battery (SIB) [532–537] is gaining increasing attention and is expected to partially replace Li-ion batteries in a near future [274,533,538,539]. In fact, there are some anode materials of Na ion battery with high performance as LIBs, which are obtained by phosphorization reaction. Here, Zhang et al. prepared cobalt phosphide NPs with a diameter of 11.3 nm, which were embedded in N-doped C nanosheets (CNSs) [274]. Here, these nanosheets were fabricated via one-step calcination of a Co-based MOF and red P, and exhibited a high capacity, fast kinetics and a long cycle life [274]. Specifically, due to the robust P-C bonding and high conductivity of CNSs, the composite as SIBs exhibited a higher rate capability and long-term cyclability (174 mAh·g⁻¹ at 20 A·g⁻¹ and 98.5 % capacity retention after 900 cycles at 1 A·g⁻¹) [274]. Similar to titanium oxynitride mesoporous nanowires, [117] the Na-storage mechanism is CoP + 3Na⁺ + 3e⁻ ↔ Co + Na₃P [274].

However, because the large radius and heavy mass of Na ions can negatively affect the capacity, stability and rate capability, exploiting high-performance anode materials of SIBs is still urgent [540].

Supercapacitors

There is a growing demand for electrochemical energy storage (EES) devices for portable electronic products, electric vehicles, and smart grids [540]. While batteries usually show high energy density, EES devices with high power density are also required for applications in electric vehicles and large-scale energy storage systems (smart grids). Here, supercapacitors (SCs, hybrid electrochemical capacitor) can provide much higher power densities and longer cycle life than batteries. Over the past ten years, the supercapacitor has gained numerous applications in many fields such as communication, automobile and new energy resources. As a matter of fact, according to the different energy storage mechanisms, supercapacitors can be divided into Faraday capacitors (also generally named pseudo-capacitor or redox supercapacitor) and electrical double-layer capacitors (EDLC) [541]. The EDLC mainly uses the charge separation formed by the electrode material and electrolyte interface to achieve the purpose of storing charges. When EDLC is charged, the external power source causes the positive and negative electrodes of the capacitor to be charged positively and negatively, respectively. While the positive and negative ions in the electrolyte moving next to the surface of the electrode can simultaneously form a double electric layer. Upon discharge, the charge on the electrode moves from the negative to the positive through the circuit, and the cations and anions migrate to the solution to maintain electroneutral state.

As for the Faraday capacitor, generally, charge storage was performed by using fast and reversible surface or near-surface reactions. The electrode material of supercapacitor is the main factor affecting the performance of the capacitor, such as specific capacitance, power density, energy density and cycle stability. Therefore, the main research direction in the field of SCs is to develop new advanced electrode materials. In this scenario,

anion-driven synthesis-derived nanostructures such as Co_3O_4 , [90,91] CoP, [272,274] NiS, [256] titania nitride and oxynitride [117,118] with a high specific surface area are favorable for SCs. The unique nanostructures obtained by anion-driven synthesis, such as nanocages, nanorods, nanosheets and hollow structures can combine large surface areas with fast electronic transport and ion transmission. Moreover, redox metal compound NCs generally used as electrode materials have a high capacitance, which can be 10 to 100 times higher than that of carbon materials. Additionally, metal compound NCs also exhibit outstanding stability in supercapacitors. On the other hand, the disadvantages are generally a denser structure, poorer electrical conductivity, and a narrower potential window when compared with some carbon materials.

Recently, hollow nanostructures of metal oxide, sulfide and nitride NCs have been extensively reported as advanced electrode materials for SCs [90,91,117,118,187,256]. For instance, Keng et al. successfully synthesized cobalt oxide nanowires using a facile and robust method. They demonstrated, for the first time, that these hollow nanomaterials exhibit electrical and electrochemical activity, making them suitable for use in hybrid electrochemical capacitors [91]. Similarly, Kim et al. reported using Au-Co NPs to prepare Au- Co_3O_4 nanowires via oxidation in air at 400 °C [90]. Interestingly, through direct comparing Au- Co_3O_4 and Co_3O_4 nanowire films with the same total NP coverage, it can be indicated that the enhancement of the (background-corrected) Faradaic electrochemical activity is increased by at least 2-fold. In addition, the capacitive current can also be enhanced, which presents specific capacitances per NP of $C_{\text{Au-Co}_3\text{O}_4} = 1.21 \times 10^{-13}\text{F}$ and $C_{\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4} = 4.50 \times 10^{-14}\text{F}$, respectively. The hollow nanostructures showed an ideal capacitive behavior with a specific capacitance and good cycling stability. Moreover, iron oxide hollow NCs have also been explored due to these elements are very cheap, abundant in earth crust and environmentally friendly.

Furthermore, compared to simple hollow structures with a single shell, complex hollow nanostructures, such as multi-shell nanostructures, [102] prepared by anion-driven synthesis, possess more advantages such as specific surface area, energy density and structure stability, and may be more suitable for high-performance supercapacitors. Furthermore, transition metal oxides, often obtained through oxidation processes, typically display low-rate capability stemming from their poor electronic conductivity. In contrast, transition metal sulfides, obtained through sulfidation processes, have emerged as promising candidates for various applications due to their excellent electronic and optical properties [26,49,179,354,542–545]. For instance, Shen et al. prepared a novel ball-in-ball hollow structure of ternary NiCo_2S_4 [401] by anion-driven synthesis [179]. Here, in order to evaluate the high specific capacitance and significant rate capability of the NiCo_2S_4 multi-shell nanostructures, as shown in Fig. 23 a, an asymmetric supercapacitor (ASC) device was fabricated. The NiCo_2S_4 electrode is the cathode and a nanocomposite of graphene/carbon spheres (G/CSs) film is the anode in KOH aqueous electrolyte, with one piece of cellulose paper as the separator. Importantly, in Fig. 23b, the CV curves at different scan rates between 0 and 1.6 V show capacitance from both electric double-layer capacitance and pseudoca-

pacitance. Additionally, even at a high scan rate of 200 mV/s, the CV curves of the ASC device show a similar shape and no obvious distortion, thus, it indicates the device has excellent fast-charge/discharge properties.

Consistent with the CV results in Fig. 23 c, the charge/discharge curves (at different current densities ranging from 1 to 20 A/g.) of the NiCo_2S_4 electrode suggest the pseudocapacitive behavior and the presence of some Faradaic processes [546,547] (reversible Faradaic redox processes of $\text{Co}^{2+}/\text{Co}^{3+}/\text{Co}^{4+}$ and $\text{Ni}^{2+}/\text{Ni}^{3+}$ redox couples). Specifically, the Faradaic processes are based on the following reactions:

Moreover, Yang et al. reported that the multi-shelled NiCo_2S_4 hollow spheres were prepared by sulfurization, and a low-cost carbon sphere was used as a template to absorb ternary metal precursors. These multi-shelled NiCo_2S_4 hollow spheres exhibited high conductivity, porous features, large surface area, and fast ion/charge transmission) (Fig. 23d) [263]. Compared with NiCo_2O_4 and NiS_2 , multi-shelled NiCo_2S_4 hollow spheres exhibit largely enhanced capacities and rate performance (specific capacities of 1521.3 F g^{-1} at 0.5 A/g and 1131.5 F g^{-1} at 10 A/g), higher energy density (58.18 Wh kg^{-1} at the power density of 400.03 W kg^{-1}) and cycle stability (capacity retention of 85.49 % after 5000 cycles at 5 A/g). Specifically, the multi-shelled NiCo_2S_4 hollow spheres usually have relatively high conductivity compared to the NiCo_2O_4 and NiS_2 . Besides the large surface area, the electrolyte solution can be stored in the internal space, which greatly improves the charge transfer efficiency [102] (Fig. 23 e): the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) values of NiCo_2O_4 , NiS_2 and NiCo_2S_4 are 1.56 Ω , 1.14 Ω , and 1.06 Ω , respectively. Additionally, as shown in Fig. 23 f, the capacity retention of the multi-shell NiCo_2S_4 hollow spheres is 74.3 % between 0.5 and 10 A/g. However, despite the low initial capacity of NiCo_2O_4 and NiS_2 electrodes, they still exhibit relatively good capacity retention over time. Furthermore, in order to investigate the cyclic stability, as shown in Fig. 23 g, 5000 cycles of GCD (an electrochemical measurement) tests were performed on NiCo_2O_4 , NiS_2 and NiCo_2S_4 , the multi-shell NiCo_2S_4 hollow spheres electrode reveals comparable capacity retention ratio to that of NiCo_2O_4 and NiS_2 electrodes in 5000 cycles, while showing a significantly higher specific capacity. Most importantly, they conclude that NiCo_2S_4 hollow multi-shelled spheres with porous structure and high internal space can efficiently buffer the volume change during the charge/discharge process. Therefore, the NiCo_2S_4 hollow multi-shelled spheres could exhibit good cycle stability. For instance (as shown in Fig. 23 h), the coulombic efficiency of the NiCo_2O_4 electrode remains at 86.5 % after 5000 cycles, demonstrating high electrochemical reversibility of the supercapacitors [548]. These impressive performances of the multi-shelled NiCo_2O_4 spheres endow them considerable potential of practical application for energy storage devices.

Here, the transition metal nitrides are also regarded as a potential candidate for energy storage because of their superior

electrical conductivity and sustainability. Additionally, the porous nanostructures with larger porosity prepared by anion-driven synthesis can be used to further improve the performance of SCs. For example, Dong et al. prepared titanium oxynitride mesoporous nanowires (Ti(O,N)-MP-NWs) with tunable O/N ratios through nitridation in ammonia flow [117]. Here, Ti(O,N)-MP-NWs are composed of *iso*-oriented interconnection grains with preferred orientation along the axial direction [99] and the kinetics is not diffusion-limited but fast, and Ti(O,N)-MP-NWs exhibit pseudocapacitive [549,550]. Furthermore, these nanowires in sodium-based non-aqueous have exhibited excellent performance of the pseudo-capacitor because the hybrid supercapacitor used a non-faradaic active carbon (AC) cathode whose charge storage is based on electrical double layer (EDL) adsorption/desorption ClO^{4-} anion, and a faradaic redox reaction anode (Ti(O,N)) that is based on a reversible pseudocapacitive process with Na^+ cation (as shown in Fig. 23i). Specifically, the sodium-ion hybrid electrochemical capacitor (Na-HEC) shows a general average operating voltage about 2.6 V, which is much higher than 1.23 V of other aqueous hybrid electrochemical capacitor HECs (Fig. 23j) [551]. The capacity of Ti(O,N) can be retained after 1000 cycles with high coulombic efficiency, specifically, the capacity retention is 82.9 % after 500 cycles, as exhibited in Fig. 23k,l. Here, the energy and power densities of different capacitors are compared in Fig. 23m, according to the rapid pseudocapacitive charge storage, the AC//Ti(O,N)-MP-NWs Na-HEC exhibits a maximum energy density of 46 Wh kg^{-1} , which indicates their great potential in the high-rate storage fields [117].

Similar with nitridation process, Moon et al. reported that TiN hollow shells can be produced via a complete nitridation process of TiO_2 NCs, and these shells can be assembled to form a robust monolayer film (Fig. 24d) [118]. Interestingly, the hollow porous film was exploited as a supercapacitor electrode through a binder-free approach (first, the nitridated shells suspended in 1-butanol simultaneously spreads on the water surface due to the high surface tension of water, and finally forms a robust film, which is not ruptured by any fluctuation [118,552]). As shown in Fig. 24e, the enclosed area of the CV curve in nitridated titania sample is about 45 times larger than that of the porous TiO_2 sphere electrode, which is caused by the functionalization with hydroxyl groups on the surface of the nitridated shells. Additionally, they reported that the areal capacitance obtained from galvanostatic charge-discharge measurements can be calculated by the following equation (Fig. 24f):

$$C = \frac{I \times \Delta t}{\Delta V \times A} \quad (26)$$

where I , Δt , ΔV , and A are the constant discharging current, time, potential window, and electrode area, respectively. In contrast, the hollow TiO_2 shell film electrode areal capacitance is 0.0137 and 0.0074 mF cm^{-2} at the same scan rates, which are 181 and 258 times less than those of the hollow TiN shell film electrode, respectively [118]. The improved electrochemical performance of the nitridated shell film electrode is attributed to the fact that the nitridated shell film offers an electronically conducting framework and a fast charge separation network. Moreover, the areal capacitance of the nitridated shell sample drops from 2.48 to 1.54 mF cm^{-2} with a retention of 62 % when the scan rate increases from 10 to 1000 mV/s . However, the bare TiO_2 film electrode maintains only 39 % of the initial capac-

itance, indicating that the rate of ion diffusion (mass transport) and the conductivity of the TiN electrode is higher than TiO_2 electrode. Fig. 24g compares the curve of the nitridated titania electrode with that of TiO_2 electrode, which is substantially prolonged, suggesting a good capacitive behavior. Furthermore, it has a small IR drop (0.03 V), confirming the low internal resistance of the nitridated titania film. Besides, compared with the TiO_2 electrode, the nitridated shell electrode shows good cycling stability with 1000 cycles (Fig. 24h).

As discussed previously, since the special hollow NCs generally offers an electronically conducting framework and a fast charge separation network desirable for electrochemical energy storage application, the controlled preparation of hollow nanostructure by anion-driven synthesis perhaps can further improve the performance. Furthermore, the key to improve the capacitor energy density of supercapacitors is to prepare electrode materials that can provide high specific capacitance and wide potential window in the future. Therefore, some strategies to improve the performance of electrode materials for supercapacitors are listed as following:

1. The electrode materials should have a large specific surface area, because a high surface area can provide more reactive sites.
2. Hollow and porous nanomaterials should have appropriate pore distribution and pore diameter, because they can provide short channels for the transmission and diffusion of electrons and ions, thus improving the contact between the electrode material and electrolyte ions, so that the material also has a high charge and discharge speed at high current density.
3. NCs are recombined with some matrixes to form a composite electrode, which has a lower charge transmission resistance.
4. Electrode materials used for supercapacitors should have high electrochemical stability and mechanical properties in order to keep the structure intact of supercapacitors during the charging and discharging process. For instance, complex hollow nanostructures exhibit superior properties compared to their simpler versions. They offer larger volumetric capacity and improved mechanical and electrochemical stability. Due to these benefits, a wide range of hollow nanostructures, including Co_3O_4 , Fe_2O_3 , Mn_2O_3 and NiO, have been developed and utilized as high-performance electrode materials [518,553–555].

Catalysis

To solve urgent problems such as the overuse of fossil fuels, the development of highly efficient catalysis undoubtedly is the basic and effective route to achieve clean and sustainable energy conversion. So far, traditional noble-metal-based catalysts such as Au, Ag, Pt, Pd, Rh and Ru have exhibited outstanding performances toward the oxygen evolution reaction (OER), and hydrogen evolution reaction (HER). Unfortunately, the high price of noble-metal-based NPs catalysts hinder their widespread adoption in commercial applications. Recently, to solve these problems, new nanostructures including but not limited to nanocages and hollow nanostructures have emerged as a burgeoning class of promising electrocatalysts [26,50,97,98,108,371,556]. As a matter of fact, using hollow nanostructures as catalysts can minimize the cost and maximize

performance because these NPs generally possess a high proportion of active surfaces and then can significantly reduce the amounts of expensive noble metals. In this section, we mainly review the NPs with unique nanostructures, which are partially or wholly obtained by anion-driven synthesis as emerging electrocatalysts for renewable energy conversion such as OER and HER.

For instance, using hollow nanostructures to increase the activity in HER electrocatalysis, Nelson et al. reported that the $\text{CoO}_x\text{S}_{0.18}$ hollow structures were prepared by anion-driven synthesis of CoO hollow NPs. Furthermore, the critical role of a transition-metal-containing electrocatalyst is the metastable, distorted S-substituted CoO phase [26]. The anionic substitution can positively affect the HER activity as shown in the cobalt oxysulfide system. In addition, a small amount of S is best for enhancing the efficiency HER and the activity for HER was 2–3 times greater than that of any of the end-members of the substituted series. These results suggested that controlling anion composition can be used not only to elucidate the role of anions, but also to further improve the activity of electrocatalysts [26].

In order to further enhance the surface area and adjust the composition of the unique nanostructure to improve the performance of catalyst, Zhang et al. synthesized porous FeP nanosheets by phosphorization as electrocatalysts for hydrogen evolution reaction [50]. The FeP porous nanosheets exhibited high electrocatalytic activity toward HER with a low overpotential (~ 0.1 V) and small Tafel slope (~ 67 mV per decade), which makes the FeP porous nanosheets as a promising inexpensive electrocatalysts for hydrogen production. Similarly, to obtain NCs by phosphides process in HER, Wang et al. successfully synthesized a-Co(OH)₂ nanosheets and bulk a-Co(OH)₂ via precipitation-dipping two-step process at room temperature, then used a-Co(OH)₂ nanosheets and bulk as an effective template to prepare CoP_2 and $\text{CoP}_{1.34}$ through a phosphides process at 573 K [557]. Meanwhile, the CoP_2 NPs show more excellent electrocatalytic activities, with overpotentials at 10 mA cm⁻² of 348 mV for OER and 200 mV for HER in 1 M NaOH.

Doping of noble-metal-based catalysts in these nanostructures is also a widely used method to improve the performance of catalyst for OER or HER. For example, Si et al. reported that Ru-doped cobalt phosphide nanocages ($\text{Co}_x\text{P}:\text{Ru}$) were synthesized by using $\text{Co}_x\text{O}:\text{Ru}$ nanocage as a template for anion-driven synthesis [108].

As depicted in Fig. 25, the $\text{Co}_x\text{P}:\text{NC}$ catalyst without doping metal Ru shows good electrocatalytic ability despite of a relatively larger onset overpotential of 68 mV. On the contrary, a low onset potential of about 41 mV is observed for Ru doped $\text{Co}_x\text{P}:\text{NC}$, which is slightly higher than that of commercial Pt-C (0 mV). Importantly, the $\text{Co}_x\text{P}:\text{NC}$ catalyst needs an overpotential of 239 mV to reach a current density of 10 mA cm⁻², while the Ru/ $\text{Co}_x\text{P}:\text{NC}$ catalyst only needs 165 mV (Fig. 25b) which means the Ru/ $\text{Co}_x\text{P}:\text{NC}$ catalyst has better electrical conductivity in catalysis. In addition, the Tafel slope of Ru/ $\text{Co}_x\text{P}:\text{NC}$ is 54.7 mV dec⁻¹, which is 13 mV dec⁻¹ lower than that of $\text{Co}_x\text{P}:\text{NC}$ (67.7 mV dec⁻¹), implying that the HER pathway follows a Volmer–Heyrovsky reaction mechanism [108,558,559]. In Fig. 25c, electrochemically active surface area (ECSA) was assessed by bilayer capacitance (C_{dl}), the curves showed that

the C_{dl} of Ru/ $\text{Co}_x\text{P}:\text{NC}$ (1.92 mF cm⁻²) is 1.58 times higher than that of $\text{Co}_x\text{P}:\text{NC}$ (1.21 mF cm⁻²), which illustrates that the Ru/ $\text{Co}_x\text{P}:\text{NC}$ catalyst possesses a larger ECSA (Fig. 25d). Furthermore, Fig. 25e reveals that the Ru/ $\text{Co}_x\text{P}:\text{NC}$ catalyst maintains its original morphology and nanostructure following stability measurements, exhibiting excellent durability with a retention of 84 % of the initial current over a duration of 10 h. This demonstrates the good stability of the $\text{Co}_x\text{P}:\text{NC}$ backbone in the Ru/ $\text{Co}_x\text{P}:\text{NC}$ composite.

Although new nanostructures can be used to improve the catalytic performance, this lifting process cannot be well controlled. To solve this issue, Tianou et al. demonstrated a repeated phosphorization process that can transform solid palladium NCs into hollow palladium NCs through the insertion and extraction of phosphorus (Fig. 26a–c).[97] Here, the thin shells exhibit enhanced catalytic activity and high durability toward formic acid oxidation (FAO). Specifically, H-Pd-1 (one cavitation cycle) exhibited a recessive mass activity compared with Pd/C (Fig. 26d, e). Moreover, both H-Pd-2 and H-Pd-3 were superior to Pd/C in terms of specific activity and mass activity, despite their relatively large NCs size. Obviously, the mass activity of H-Pd-3 on Ag/AgCl electrode at 0.22 V is 1800 mA/mg, which is almost 4 times of that of Pd/C (Fig. 26d). Moreover, the specific activity demonstrated by H-Pd-3 (1800 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$) was also three times higher than that of commercial Pd/C (Fig. 26e). As illustrated in Fig. 26f, the electrochemically active surface areas (ECSAs) calculated from the carbon monoxide (CO) stripping cyclic voltammetry curves, which indicated an increased order of H-Pd-1 < Pd/C < H-Pd-2 < H-Pd-3. Moreover, this order further verifies an inference that catalytic performance can be improved by increasing the number of accessible atoms due to continuous thinning of the shells. As shown in Fig. 26g, over 60 % of the initial activities were sustained for all hollow Pd catalysts after 1000 cycles, while the activity of Pd/C dropped by 75 % after 1000 cycles of the FAO reaction. Hence, it was concluded that the mass activity and specific activity of hollow metallic catalysts are four and three times higher than those of commercial Pd/C catalysts, satisfying the requirements for efficient electrocatalytic applications.

Some heterostructures obtained by anion-driven synthesis can also be used as catalysts. Saruyama et al. prepared phase-segregated $\text{NiP}_x\text{-FeP}_y\text{O}_z$ core-shell heterostructures NPs via an oxidation process, which were used as catalyst in electro- and photo-catalytic water oxidation and exhibited higher electrocatalytic activity than those of other metal phosphide-based catalysts [556]. In addition, $\text{NiP}_x\text{-FeP}_y\text{O}_z$ heterostructures can also be used as a cocatalyst of BiVO_4 photocatalyst to boost the photocatalytic OER [556]. The OER process was induced spontaneously by the removal of ligands and *in-situ* formation of the NP/substrate heterointerfaces, which provided ready-to-use OER hybrid catalysts without any post-treatment.

Additionally, some general NPs prepared by anion-driven synthesis and encapsulated or anchored in a matrix to form new nanostructures, which can also be used to enhance the performance of the catalyst, [95,109,132,134,190,275,560] such as carbon nanotube, [132] nitrogen-doped carbon nanocages, [95] nitrogen-doped reduced graphene oxides, [190] hollow quasi-polyhedra structures, [134] and N-doped porous carbon sheet

networks and vanadium nitride/graphitic carbon composites [275,560]. For instance, Wu et al. prepared ultrasmall FeP NPs by phosphorization, which can be inlaid in carbon nanotubes as an efficient electrocatalyst for hydrogen evolution, achieving a very low overpotential (68 mV at 10 mA cm⁻²) [132]. Similarly, Guan et al. synthesized multilevel N-doped carbon nanotube/graphene-supported cobalt phosphide NPs in 2019 [272]. The electrocatalyst developed therein has excellent electronic conductivity (17.8 s/cm) and high HER activity, requiring only a low overpotential of 155 mV to achieve 10 mA/cm² in 0.5 M H₂SO₄. It also features a low Tafel slope of 69.1 mV/dec. Furthermore, the CoPeCNT/NG material maintains outstanding electrochemical durability after 18 h of use.

The electrochemical double-layer (EDL) capacitance was also tested by CV to investigate the kinetics mechanism of the HER process [272], and the resulting anode materials with unique nanostructures can also be used for lithium ions battery to improve their performance (as mentioned in Section 'Lithium-ion battery').

Sensing

As the Internet of Things (IoT) continues to expand, the deployment of billions of sensors across various environments becomes increasingly prevalent. The development of new sensors requires taking into account the following performance metrics: (1) high sensitivity, (2) low cost, (3) short response time, (4) low power consumption, and (5) multi-functional integration. Furthermore, compared to traditional sensors, nanosensors can operate at the atomic and molecular scale, which makes full use of the reactivity of nanomaterials, such as Raman spectral effect, catalytic efficiency, conductivity, strength, hardness, toughness, super plasticity, and superparamagnetism [561–564]. There is no doubt that the performance of the sensor largely depends on the structure and morphology of the nanomaterials.

For the common gas sensors, hollow metallic compound NCs generally exhibit significant advantages over bulk materials due to their large surface-to-volume ratio, which could greatly enhance the gas diffusion and mass transportation in the active layers. Therefore, the variation of nanostructures will lead to different sensing parameters. While the types of sensors and sensing materials are enormous, here, we review the use of anion-driven synthesis-derived NPs in some sensing technologies. For instance, Chen et al. prepared iron oxide nanotubes as gas sensor [112]. The sensor sensitivity of the as-prepared Fe₂O₃ nanotubes is about five times greater than that of Fe₂O₃ NPs for ethanol detection with same concentration at room temperature because the specific surface area of the Fe₂O₃ nanotube (45 m² g⁻¹) is large than Fe₂O₃ NPs (25 m² g⁻¹). Additionally, when Fe₂O₃ nanotubes are exposed to hydrogen (H₂), the sensitivity of the Fe₂O₃ nanotubes sensor is greatly improved due to the large change in resistance. Moreover, the good reversibility of the Fe₂O₃ nanotubes sensor was also indicated by the on and off responses, which could be repeated more than 50 times without obvious changes in the signal.

Nowadays, many hollow metal oxide nanostructures have been prepared for the detection of various gases, such as CO, EtOH, H₂, H₂O, acetone, and CH₂O. Among these gases, it is worth noting that carbon monoxide (CO) is a colorless, odorless,

and tasteless toxic gas, therefore, it is difficult to detect it. CO gas can lead to significant toxicity on the central nervous system and heart, and even death at 100 ppm or greater. Xiao et al. prepared hollow Cu_{2-x}Te NCs with tunable interior volume by telluride reaction (based on the Kirkendall effect) [149]. Here, the Cu NPs sever as not only the initial materials but also the sites of sacrificial self-templates. Due to the small grain size and large surface-to-volume ratio of hollow Cu_{2-x}Te NCs, the nanostructures generally exhibit enhanced sensitivity for the detection of CO as low as 5 ppm. As shown in Fig. 27a, it is clear that the sensitivity ($S = R_g/R_a$, R_g and R_a are the resistance of the sensor in test gas (R_g) and in dry air (R_a)) increased rapidly until reached a maximum (of about 1.37 at an operating temperature of 260 °C) and then decreased with further temperature increases. This phenomenon was attributed to the kinetics of the gas adsorption and desorption process on the surface of hollow Cu_{2-x}Te NCs [149,566].

Specifically, on the one hand, because the gas molecules do not have enough thermal energy to react with the surface-adsorbed oxygen species at a low operation temperature, a low response would be expected. On the other hand, the response of a CO gas sensor is restricted by the speed of diffusion of gas molecules at high temperatures due to the significant increases of electron concentration from the sensing reaction. Hence, the sensor response can run up to the maximum at a certain intermediate temperature (260 °C), which is the point of the two processes become equal in their reaction and diffusion speed. Moreover, further gas-sensor characters were examined at this temperature. It showed that the sensitivity was identified as a linear increase with the increasing concentration of CO gas in the range from 5 to 500 ppm (Fig. 27b), which also implies that the hollow Cu_{2-x}Te NCs can be easily designed in the future.

Additionally, from the dynamic response-recovery curves of the sensor (Fig. 27c), these results firstly reveal that the sensor can detect CO at a very small amount of concentration (of 5 ppm), and the sensitivity can be further improved by increasing the CO gas concentration, due to that the more adsorbed CO molecules on the hollow Cu_{2-x}Te NPs surface will react with the oxygen species. For example, when the as-prepared Cu_{2-x}Te-based sensor are immersed in massive CO gas, the sensitivities are 1.11, 1.14, 1.16, 1.24 and 1.37, for the different CO concentrations at levels of 5, 10, 20, 40 and 100 ppm, respectively. In addition, it is worth noting that the response and recovery times of the CO sensor are estimated to be about 21 and 100 s, respectively, as shown in Fig. 27d. Moreover, the signal can be restored to its initial values without significant changes in the resistance after several test cycles, indicating its reproducible and stable properties (inset in Fig. 27). The CO gas-sensing mechanism of the hollow Cu_{2-x}Te NCs is shown in Fig. 27e. Typically, when the hollow Cu_{2-x}Te NCs were exposed to air, oxygen molecules could absorb on the surface and capture free electrons to form chemisorbed oxygen species (O₂⁻, O⁻ and O²⁻), as shown in equations (27)-(28) [567].

Cu_{2-x}Te is a p-type semiconductor [149,568]. When the above adsorption process reaches an equilibrium, the hole density of hollow Cu_{2-x}Te NPs in the valence band will increase. Furthermore, the conductivity of the semiconductor also increases accordingly. Meanwhile, another approach to induce an increase in hole density is to enhance the electron transfer from the conduction band to the chemically adsorbed oxygen. When the Cu_{2-x}Te NCs is exposed to the target gas, then, CO molecules will react with the adsorbed oxygen species on the Cu_{2-x}Te surface and release the trapped electron back to the conduction band, which is depicted by Langmuir-Hinshelwood mechanism as shown in equations (30)-(31) [149,565,569–571].

In addition, this process will decrease the hole density in the surface charge layer, presumably due to the presence of electrons, which ultimately improves the sensitivity of the hollow Cu_{2-x}Te sensor [572]. Hence, the synthesized monodispersed hollow Cu_{2-x}Te NCs based on anion-driven synthesis will provide new functional blocks that are expected to be a promising candidate for CO gas sensors or other catalytic applications.

Furthermore, Patil et al. synthesized the Co_3O_4 nanorods with diameters $\sim 6\text{--}8$ nm and lengths $\sim 20\text{--}30$ nm via oxidation of cobalt hydroxyl carbonate in air and use such NPs for CO gas sensors [565]. The Co_3O_4 nanorods exhibit excellent gas sensing characteristics such as higher gas response ($\sim 6.55\text{--}50$ ppm CO gas at 250°C), outstanding repeatability, good selectivity and lower operating temperature ($\sim 250^\circ\text{C}$) (Fig. 27 g). Specifically, (1) the response time was nearly 3–4 s and the recovery time was found to be 5–6 s. As shown in Fig. 27 f(a), at low temperatures, the gas response is relatively low (1.66 at 100°C), but it increases rapidly with an increase in the operating temperature. (2) The gas response is then peaked to its maximum value of 6.55 at 250°C . Above 250°C , the gas response decreases with further increasing the operating temperature. In addition, the gas response to 50 ppm of CO gas remains fairly constant at ~ 2.20 between the operating temperatures at $200\text{--}300^\circ\text{C}$ for commercially available Co_3O_4 powder (Fig. 27f(b)). (3) The Co_3O_4 nanorods showed a significantly higher response to CO (6.55) but a significantly lower response to hydrogen, LPG, carbon dioxide and ethanol (<3.51) (Fig. 27h). Obviously, the gas response of the Co_3O_4 nanorods is about three times greater than that of commercial Co_3O_4 powder, (indicating the improved sensitivity of the Co_3O_4 nanorods), which is due to the small size and higher specific surface area of the rod morphology.

Drug delivery

In addition to the common sensor applications for the nanostructures obtained via anion-driven synthesis, another area is the biomedical application, including drug delivery and bioimaging [255,261,297,326,573]. In the past few decades, as useful nanocarriers for drug delivery, hollow NPs have been utilized for diagnostics and therapeutics in many ways [102,104,255,297,326,484,573].

For instance, Xu et al. reported the evaluation of cytotoxicity of a new type of engineered nanomaterials and prepared FePt/CoS₂ yolk/shell NPs through sulfurization via using FePt/Co core-shell NPs as the reaction template and FePt NPs as the initial seeds of FePt/Co NPs [255,326]. Typically, the specific drug transport process is mainly divided into three steps (Fig. 28a), (1) The yolk/shell FePt/CoS₂ NPs were ingested by the cell membrane into the cells interior; (2) Pt ions are released from the FePt cores; (3) Pt ions diffuse through the CoS₂ shell and enter into the nucleus (bind to DNA), and lead to apoptosis of the HeLa cell (cancer cells). The results showed that these platinum ions were approximately 7-fold more cytotoxic than cisplatin in terms of the amount of Pt [255]. According to the data, after uptake of the NPs, HeLa cells were killed after incubation with 5 g/mL of FePt-CoS₂ yolk-shell NPs. It is worth noting that the nanosized core-shell NPs generally have higher reactivity when the surface ligands on the NPs surface are removed. After cellular uptake, FePt cores will be oxidized and destroyed to become metal ions, because the high reactivity of unprotected iron promotes the disintegration of FePt to release platinum ions (Pt^{2+}) under the acidic environment inside the secondary lysosomes (Fig. 28a) [255].

Moreover, the permeability (or the rupture) of CoS₂ shells allows these Pt^{2+} ions to diffuse out of the shells easily and enter into the cores and mitochondria, resulting in the damage to the DNA double-helix chains by coordinating with 5'-GG-3' bases of DNA, [574,575] and thus the apoptosis of the HeLa cells. From Fig. 28b and c, it can be seen that the FePt ($\sim 2\text{nm}$ in diameter) cores disintegrated after cellular uptake. Furthermore, as shown in the optical microscopy images of HeLa cells (Fig. 28d) incubated for 48 h with 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of FePt-CoS₂ NCs and (Fig. 28e) for 48 h with only the growth medium as the negative control, the high cytotoxicity of FePt-CoS₂ is proved by the result of almost total death of the HeLa cells after 48 h. In fact, the cytotoxicity of the FePt-CoS₂ NCs (35.5 ± 4.7 ng of Pt/mL) is much lower than the semi-inhibitory concentration recorded with cisplatin (230 ng of Pt/mL) [255,576]. Additionally, the slow dissolution of FePt cores have increased the cytotoxicity of the core-shell NPs, which consist of the sustained cell death over time (Fig. 28f). Since very few anti-cancer drugs have lower semi-inhibitory concentrations values than cisplatin in terms of platinum content, it can be expected that the formation of core-shell nanostructure may be a useful route to lead the development of anticancer nanodrugs [255].

Cancer therapy

The photothermal therapy (PTT) based on nanomaterials and nanotechnologies has attracted tremendously increasing interest in cancer therapy in the past decades [261,577–580]. The PTT usually utilizes near-infrared (NIR) laser-induced thermal effects of NPs to treat or ablate diseased tissues and cells [261,581–583]. The NPs combined with PTT and multiple imaging functions are of great significance for biomedical applications [261,584]. Furthermore, these multifunctional NPs have the potential to enable simultaneous precise diagnosis, effective treatment approaches, and treatment response monitoring. Consequently, the use of such NPs offers the potential to mitigate common side effects associated with chemotherapy or radiother-

apy while enhancing treatment efficacy [261,585–588]. Recently, the cuprous sulfide with numerous copper-deficient stoichiometries (Cu_{2-x}S) prepared by anion-driven synthesis has been extensively studied because its (chemically measured dependent) near-infrared LSPR absorption and high photothermal conversion efficiency comparable to that of gold nanostructures (typically 25.7 % Cu_9S_5) [261,589–591]. Moreover, plasmonic Au metal NPs, which have been typically employed in earlier studies, commonly exhibit photothermal (PT) conversion as well as surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) properties. The integration of plasmonic Au metal NPs and Cu_{2-x}S semiconductors can yield fascinating properties in such as SERS and PT enhancement, providing high recognition, ultra-low background signals, high spatial resolution and long-term stability even under continuous illumination [261,592,593]. However, Au- Cu_{2-x}S core-shell NPs cannot be prepared by a traditional one-pot synthetic strategy due to the large lattice mismatch of Au and Cu_{2-x}S [171]. Such heterogeneous NPs can be prepared by sulfurization using Au-Ag core-shell NPs as the template [257]. Nonetheless, current synthesis processes of Au- Cu_2S core-shell NPs are generally complex and tedious, and also involve non-resins, organic reagents (such as harmful templates and organometallic copper or S precursors), and harsh chemical environments (no oxygen or water).

In most cases, high-quality Au- Cu_2S core-shell NPs are synthesized using simple methods to enhance the photothermal conversion efficiency for cancer therapy [594–600]. For instance, Lv et al. synthesized monodisperse Au- Cu_{2-x}S core-shell NPs through sulfidation-based facile and green approach in an aqueous system (Fig. 29a) [261]. The shell thickness and Cu/S atomic ratio of the Cu_{2-x}S can be sequentially adjusted by anion-driven synthesis. The integration of the plasmonic Au nucleus and Cu_{2-x}S shell into a unified entity not only enables highly efficient PT conversion but also facilitates the development of a SERS-based navigator. These SERS-based NPs offer dual functionality, enabling accurate tumor navigation and non-destructive PTT.

Furthermore, these applications can be differentially guided *in vivo* using two distinct optical imaging modalities, owing to the NPs ability to be steered with enhanced photoacoustic signals [261]. In order to estimate the PTT therapeutic efficiency of NPs *in vivo*, Au-CuS-FA (folic acid) NPs were intravenously injected (at a single dose of 10.0 mg kg^{-1}) into BALB/c nude mice bearing 4 T1 tumors. After injection for 6 h, the observation reveals that both the Au-CuS-FA NP and Au-CuS NP groups exhibit a significant temperature elevation zone upon irradiation of the tumor with a laser (808 nm, 0.72 W cm^2 , 5 min). This finding demonstrates the robust absorption capability at 808 nm and the high photothermal (PT) conversion efficiency of Au-CuS, as evident in Fig. 29b.

Furthermore, the temperature in the tumor region of mice treated with Au-CuS-FA NPs was much higher than that of Au-CuS NPs under the same conditions (Fig. 29c). The higher medical performance of Au-CuS-FA is attributed to the enhanced active tumor targeting, the permeability, and retention effects. Additionally, the tumor suppression ability was illustrated by the 14 days relative tumor volume (cm^3) test. The administration of Au-CuS-FA NPs significantly inhibited tumor growth due to

the PTT under (808 nm) laser irradiation. However, the tumor treated with PBS (phosphate-buffered saline) grew rapidly within 14 days, which resulted in similar growth profiles as the intravenous injection of Au-CuS and Au-CuS-FA NPs into mice without laser irradiation (Fig. 29d). Moreover, as shown in Fig. 29e, the PT performance of various materials with different conditions (whether to use laser) can be visualized by the weight of tumor tissues (harvested from mice after the same treatments).

Conclusions and outlook

The anion-driven synthesis of NPs is a maturing field, with rich opportunities to better understand the thermodynamics and kinetics of anion-driven synthesis mechanisms, as well as to explore new nanostructures and compounds toward a wide spectrum of applications. Anion-driven synthesis is accessible to a wide range of metal compounds such as metal oxide, sulfide, selenide, phosphide, nitride, and less frequently telluride and halide NPs with unique architectures, including yolk-shell, hollow, nanonecklace, nanocage, nanopipe, and several others, which may be trouble or impossible to prepare using other synthesis strategies. Indeed, a better understanding of the mechanism of the Kirkendall effect in the anion-driven synthesis is needed, which could allow for the improvement of the relatively accurate morphological and structural control. In addition, improved models and theories of chemical transition reactions could provide a deeper and more detailed understanding of the anion-driven synthesis mechanism. Recently, the increased availability of investigative nanoscale tools (such as the transmission electron microscope and the atomic force microscope), particularly allowing *in-situ* analysis, is facilitating the understanding of the involved processes at the atomic scale. While there are many examples of controlling the composition, structure, morphology, and crystallinity of anion-driven synthesis-derived metal compounds, improving control of the anion-driven synthesis is still a major challenge. Currently, it is difficult to fully cover the principles governing such anion-driven synthesis to produce unique nanostructures owing to the variety of phenomena and inaccurate situations out of the established rules, which have been summarized according to the numerous combinations of template NCs and anionic reagents. We believe that new mechanisms of anion-driven synthesis will be elucidated, and novel nanomaterials alongside their advanced properties will be harnessed in this field. These novel nanostructures enabled by anion-driven synthesis may play a fundamental role in current and emerging applications.

Overall, the metal compound NPs with unique architectures and properties obtained by anion-driven synthesis have potential for a wide range of applications in energy, sensing, biomedicine, and more. We anticipate that, by manipulating the physical, chemical, and biological properties of unique nanostructures, or exploring some novel anionic reagent with suitable stability and reactivity, it will be possible to design and fabricate new nanostructures to utilize them for energy applications towards simultaneous storage and conversion. For this purpose, we need to further tackle many issues including the control over reaction selectivity and development of new reaction mechanisms.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Yi Zhou: Writing – original draft. **Jun Li:** Writing – review & editing. **Long Liu:** Writing – review & editing. **Cuifang Wang:** Writing – review & editing. **Reilly P. Lynch:** Writing – review & editing. **Bing Bai:** Writing – review & editing. **Hsien-Yi Hsu:** Writing – review & editing. **Zongyou Yin:** Writing – review & editing. **Andreu Cabot:** Writing – review & editing. **Richard D. Robinson:** Writing – review & editing. **Ido Hadar:** Writing – review & editing. **Zongping Shao:** Writing – review & editing. **Mark A. Buntine:** Writing – review & editing. **Xuyong Yang:** Writing – review & editing. **Guohua Jia:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the financial support from the Australian Research Council (ARC) Future Fellowship Scheme (GFT210100509), the ARC Discovery Project Scheme (DP220101959), the Hebrew University of Jerusalem - Zelman Cowen Academic Initiatives (ZCAI) Joint Projects 2021, the National Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant No. 22205053), the Fellowship of China Postdoctoral Science Foundation (No. 2021M701062) and Innovation and Technology Commission (Grant no. MHP/104/21).

References

- [1] V.I. Klimov et al., *Science* 290 (5490) (2000) 314–317.
- [2] M. Bruchez Jr et al., *Science* 281 (5385) (1998) 2013–2016.
- [3] L. Brus, *J. Phys. Chem.* 90 (12) (1986) 2555–2560.
- [4] D.V. Talapin et al., *Chem. Rev.* 110 (1) (2010) 389–458.
- [5] A. Nurmiikko, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 10 (12) (2015) 1001–1004.
- [6] M. Nasilowski et al., *Chem. Rev.* 116 (18) (2016) 10934–10982.
- [7] Y. Yin, A.P. Alivisatos, *Nature* 437 (7059) (2005) 664–670.
- [8] P.K. Jain et al., *Plasmonics* 2 (3) (2007) 107–118.
- [9] J.P. Clifford et al., *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 4 (1) (2009) 40–44.
- [10] Z.B. Li et al., *J. Nanosci. Nanotechnol.* 7 (8) (2007) 2567–2581.
- [11] R. Hergt et al., *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* 18 (38) (2006) S2919–S2934.
- [12] M.A. Malik et al., *Chem. Rev.* 110 (7) (2010) 4417–4446.
- [13] J.C. Sarker, G. Hogarth, *Chem. Rev.* 121 (10) (2021) 6057–6123.
- [14] S.E. Habas et al., *Chem. Mater.* 27 (22) (2015) 7580–7592.
- [15] S. Schulz et al., *Chem. Mater.* 24 (11) (2012) 2228–2234.
- [16] S. Shen et al., *Chem. Mater.* 24 (12) (2012) 2407–2413.
- [17] J. Akhtar et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 134 (5) (2012) 2485–2487.
- [18] C.J. Barrelet et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 125 (38) (2003) 11498–11499.
- [19] M. Akhtar et al., *J. Mater. Chem. A* 2 (48) (2014) 20612–20620.
- [20] A.W. Xiao et al., *Nat. Mater.* 19 (6) (2020) 644–654.
- [21] J. Wu et al., *Small* 16 (15) (2020) 1900550.
- [22] A. Cabot et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 129 (34) (2007) 10358–10360.
- [23] J.M.R. Parrondo et al., *Nat. Phys.* 11 (2) (2015) 131–139.
- [24] B.Q. Jia et al., *Chem. Mater.* 31 (22) (2019) 9532–9539.
- [25] T.L. Ha et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 135 (4) (2013) 1378–1385.
- [26] A. Nelson et al., *J. Mater. Chem. A* 4 (8) (2016) 2842–2848.
- [27] M. Saruyama et al., *Acc. Chem. Res.* 54 (4) (2021) 765–775.
- [28] H.L. Wu et al., *Science* 351 (6279) (2016) 1306–1310.
- [29] S. Jiao et al., *Adv. Mater.* 18 (9) (2006) 1174–1177.
- [30] S. Kim et al., *Chem. Sci.* 11 (6) (2019) 1523–1530.
- [31] B.D. Anderson, J.B. Tracy, *Nanoscale* 6 (21) (2014) 12195–12216.
- [32] K.M. Nam et al., *Chem. Mater.* 22 (15) (2010) 4446–4454.
- [33] A.E. Henkes, R.E. Schaak, *Chem. Mater.* 19 (17) (2007) 4234–4242.
- [34] H. Cao et al., *Chem. Commun. (Camb)* 43 (2006) 4548–4550.
- [35] W.-S. Jung, B. Dunn, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 99 (5) (2016) 1520–1524.
- [36] M. Yamauchi et al., *ACS Omega* 5 (24) (2020) 14370–14375.
- [37] A. Yan et al., *Nanoscale Res. Lett.* 13 (1) (2018) 185–192.
- [38] D. Yin et al., *Nanoscale* 13 (9) (2021) 4828–4834.
- [39] H. Zhang et al., *Dalton Trans.* 42 (35) (2013) 12596–12599.
- [40] S. Zhuo et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 52 (33) (2013) 8602–8606.
- [41] J.B. Rivest, P.K. Jain, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 42 (1) (2013) 89–96.
- [42] S.A. Patil et al., *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 7 (46) (2015) 25914–25922.
- [43] W. Zhao et al., *ACS Nano* 8 (10) (2014) 10909–10919.
- [44] L. De Trizio, L. Manna, *Chem. Rev.* 116 (18) (2016) 10852–10887.
- [45] J.M. Hodges et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 54 (30) (2015) 8669–8672.
- [46] M.W. Ji et al., *Nano Res.* 10 (9) (2017) 2977–2987.
- [47] B.A. Aragaw et al., *Rsc Adv.* 7 (72) (2017) 45470–45477.
- [48] C. Xia et al., *Chem. Mater.* 29 (2) (2017) 690–698.
- [49] S. Xiong, H.C. Zeng, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 51 (4) (2012) 949–952.
- [50] Y. Xu et al., *Chem. Commun. (Camb)* 49 (59) (2013) 6656–6658.
- [51] E. Groeneveld et al., *ACS Nano* 7 (9) (2013) 7913–7930.
- [52] Y. Hong et al., *ACS Nano* 14 (9) (2020) 11205–11214.
- [53] Y. Liu et al., *ACS Photonics* 5 (11) (2018) 4504–4512.
- [54] A. Louidice et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 141 (20) (2019) 8254–8263.
- [55] G. Nedelcu et al., *Nano Lett.* 15 (8) (2015) 5635–5640.
- [56] J.L. Peltier et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 142 (38) (2020) 16479–16485.
- [57] E. González et al., *Science* 334 (6061) (2011) 1377–1380.
- [58] W. Zhang et al., *ACS Nano* 6 (8) (2012) 7397–7405.
- [59] M.H. Oh et al., *Science* 340 (6135) (2013) 964–968.
- [60] L.M. Moreau et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 139 (35) (2017) 12291–12298.
- [61] A.N. Chen et al., *Chem. Mater.* 31 (4) (2019) 1344–1351.
- [62] D. Seo, H. Song, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 131 (51) (2009) 18210–18211.
- [63] X. Xia et al., *Adv. Mater.* 25 (44) (2013) 6313–6333.
- [64] Y. Yang et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 136 (23) (2014) 8153–8156.
- [65] S.E. Skrabalak et al., *Acc. Chem. Res.* 41 (12) (2008) 1587–1595.
- [66] X. Lu et al., *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng., Pt. N: J. Nano* 221 (1) (2008) 1–16.
- [67] W. Wang et al., *Chem. Mater.* 25 (8) (2012) 1179–1189.
- [68] Y.D. Yin et al., *Science* 304 (5671) (2004) 711–714.
- [69] F. Aldinger, *Acta Metall.* 22 (7) (1974) 923–928.
- [70] R.K. Chiang, R.T. Chiang, *Inorg. Chem.* 46 (2) (2007) 369–371.
- [71] Z. Wang et al., *Crystengcomm* 12 (6) (2010) 1899–1904.
- [72] I.K. Hewavitharana, S.L. Brock, *ACS Nano* 11 (11) (2017) 11217–11224.
- [73] X. Wang et al., *Chem. Rev.* 116 (18) (2016) 10983–11060.
- [74] J. Wang et al., *Adv. Mater.* 31 (38) (2019) 1–24.
- [75] Y. Lim et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 142 (20) (2020) 9130–9134.
- [76] J.-W. Seo et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 46 (46) (2007) 8828–8831.
- [77] C.-H. Kuo et al., *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 21 (4) (2011) 792–797.
- [78] W. Chen et al., *Nano Res.* 5 (5) (2012) 320–326.
- [79] Q.A. Akkerman et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 137 (32) (2015) 10276–10281.
- [80] Y.-C. Chen et al., *J. Phys. Chem. C* 123 (4) (2019) 2353–2360.
- [81] S.E. Creutz et al., *Nano Lett.* 18 (2) (2018) 1118–1123.
- [82] D. Parobek et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 139 (12) (2017) 4358–4361.
- [83] Y. Yin et al., *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 16 (11) (2006) 1389–1399.
- [84] S.K. Meena et al., *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 18 (19) (2016) 13246–13254.
- [85] N.T. Thanh et al., *Chem. Rev.* 114 (15) (2014) 7610–7630.
- [86] P. Muhammad et al., *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 34 (29) (2024) 2314686–2314742.
- [87] J.H. Han et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 135 (10) (2013) 3736–3739.
- [88] S. Peng, S. Sun, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 46 (22) (2007) 4155–4158.
- [89] T.J. Yoon et al., *Part. Part. Syst. Char.* 30 (8) (2013) 667–671.
- [90] B.Y. Kim et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 132 (10) (2010) 3234–3235.
- [91] P.Y. Keng et al., *ACS Nano* 3 (10) (2009) 3143–3157.
- [92] Y. Lim et al., *Acc. Chem. Res.* 54 (7) (2021) 1565–1574.
- [93] J. Li et al., *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 463 (2016) 69–74.
- [94] M. Colombo et al., *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 41 (11) (2012) 4306–4334.
- [95] X. Wang et al., *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 12 (14) (2020) 16548–16556.
- [96] G. Wang et al., *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 10 (38) (2018) 32133–32141.
- [97] H. Tianou et al., *Nat. Commun.* 8 (1) (2017) 1–9.
- [98] J. Park et al., *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 47 (22) (2018) 8173–8202.
- [99] C.H.B. Ng et al., *Langmuir* 22 (23) (2006) 9712–9717.
- [100] A.G. Roca et al., *Adv. Drug Del. Rev.* 138 (2019) 68–104.
- [101] D.-H. Ha et al., *J. Phys. Chem. C* 117 (27) (2013) 14303–14312.
- [102] J. Wang et al., *Acc. Chem. Res.* 52 (8) (2019) 2169–2178.

- [103] X.W. Lou et al., *Adv. Mater.* 20 (21) (2008) 3987–4019.
- [104] J. Liu et al., *Chem. Commun. (Camb)* 47 (47) (2011) 12578–12591.
- [105] Y. Tang, M. Ouyang, *Nat. Mater.* 6 (10) (2007) 754–759.
- [106] Z.H. Ma et al., *Chem. Rev.* (2021) 3904–3943.
- [107] Z.S. Wu et al., *Acs Catal.* 9 (4) (2019) 2956–2961.
- [108] C.D. Si et al., *Acs Sustain. Chem. Eng.* 7 (11) (2019) 9737–9742.
- [109] Y. Wang et al., *J. Mater. Chem. A* 8 (36) (2020) 19043–19049.
- [110] C. Clavero, *Nat. Photonics* 8 (2) (2014) 95–103.
- [111] F. Li et al., *Adv. Mater.* 29 (14) (2017) 1–30.
- [112] J. Chen et al., *Adv. Mater.* 17 (5) (2005) 582–586.
- [113] C. He et al., *ACS Nano* 7 (5) (2013) 4459–4469.
- [114] N. Liu et al., *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 9 (3) (2014) 187–192.
- [115] Z.S. Wu et al., *ACS Nano* 4 (6) (2010) 3187–3194.
- [116] K.J. Zhu et al., *Adv. Mater. Interfaces* 4 (2017) 19.
- [117] J. Dong et al., *J. Mater. Chem. A* 5 (22) (2017) 10827–10835.
- [118] G.D. Moon et al., *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 24 (6) (2014) 848–856.
- [119] X.W. Lv et al., *Acs Sustain. Chem. Eng.* 7 (9) (2019) 8993–9001.
- [120] J.W. Ma et al., *Small* 14 (2) (2018) 1702895.
- [121] A. Ermoline, E.L. Dreizin, *Chem. Phys. Lett.* 505 (1–3) (2011) 47–50.
- [122] E. Sutter, P. Sutter, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 116 (38) (2012) 20574–20578.
- [123] A.E. Powell et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 138 (2) (2016) 471–474.
- [124] B. Bai et al., *Chem* 6 (11) (2020) 3086–3099.
- [125] K. Mizuta et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 137 (38) (2015) 12195–12198.
- [126] A.X. Wang et al., *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* 11 (13) (2020) 4990–4997.
- [127] D.H. Son et al., *Science* 306 (5698) (2004) 1009–1012.
- [128] N. Meir et al., *Chem. Mater.* 28 (21) (2016) 7872–7877.
- [129] M. Casavola et al., *Chem. Mater.* 24 (2) (2012) 294–302.
- [130] M.W.M. Hisham, S.W. Benson, *J. Phys. Chem.* 93 (8) (1989) 3308–3311.
- [131] H.D.B. Jenkins, *J. Chem. Educ.* 82 (6) (2005) 950–952.
- [132] F. Wu et al., *Acs Sustain. Chem. Eng.* 7 (15) (2019) 12741–12749.
- [133] J.G. Railsback et al., *ACS Nano* 4 (4) (2010) 1913–1920.
- [134] Y. Li et al., *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 9 (7) (2017) 5982–5991.
- [135] H.F. Oztop, K. Al-Salem, *Renew. Sust. Energ. Rev.* 16 (1) (2012) 911–920.
- [136] W. Niedenzu et al., *Nat. Commun.* 9 (1) (2018) 165.
- [137] L.L. Mu et al., *Match-Commun Math Co* 56 (1) (2006) 97–111.
- [138] B. Bai et al., *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 52 (1) (2023) 318–360.
- [139] R.G. Agarwal et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 143 (7) (2021) 2896–2907.
- [140] C.H. Kelly, M. Lein, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 18 (47) (2016) 32448–32457.
- [141] J. Park et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 131 (39) (2009) 13943–13945.
- [142] R.G. Parr, R.G. Pearson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 105 (26) (1983) 7512–7516.
- [143] J.L. Reed, *Inorg. Chem.* 47 (13) (2008) 5591–5600.
- [144] P.W. Ayers, *Faraday Discuss* 135 (2007) 161–190.
- [145] S. Ahrland et al., *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 12 (3) (1958) 265–271.
- [146] F.H. Walters, *J. Chem. Educ.* 68 (1) (1991) 29–31.
- [147] M.L. Morris, R.D. Koob, *Inorg. Chem.* 20 (8) (1981) 2737–2738.
- [148] Y. Wang et al., *Adv. Mater.* 17 (4) (2005) 473–477.
- [149] G. Xiao et al., *Small* 9 (5) (2013) 793–799.
- [150] M. Saruyama et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 133 (44) (2011) 17598–17601.
- [151] M. Ibáñez et al., *Chem. Mater.* 23 (12) (2011) 3095–3104.
- [152] E. Muthuswamy et al., *ACS Nano* 5 (3) (2011) 2402–2411.
- [153] R.G. Pearson, *Inorg. Chem.* 27 (4) (1988) 734–740.
- [154] G. Cho et al., *Nano Converg.* 6 (1) (2019) 17.
- [155] J.T. Rubino, K.J. Franz, *J. Inorg. Biochem.* 107 (1) (2012) 129–143.
- [156] G.D. Moon et al., *ACS Nano* 4 (4) (2010) 2307–2319.
- [157] L.-M. Lyu, M.H. Huang, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 115 (36) (2011) 17768–17773.
- [158] W. Huang et al., *ACS Nano* 15 (4) (2021) 6481–6488.
- [159] F. Chang et al., *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 235 (2020) 116171.
- [160] X. Xia et al., *Small* 10 (4) (2014) 766–773.
- [161] A.D. John, *Lange's handbook of chemistry*, in: *Universitas Of Tennessee Knoxville, Fifteenth Edition*, Mc. Graw Hill Inc, New York. Conference, 1999, pp. 687–688.
- [162] L. Sillen, A.E. Martell, *Search PubMed* (1971) 231.
- [163] G.D. Moon et al., *Nano Today* 6 (2) (2011) 186–203.
- [164] S. Lewin, *The Solubility Product Principle: An Introduction to Its Uses and Limitations*, Interscience Publishers, 1960.
- [165] A.T. Fromhold, E.L. Cook, *Phys. Rev.* 163 (3) (1967) 650–664.
- [166] A.T. Fromhold, E.L. Cook, *Phys. Rev.* 158 (3) (1967) 600–612.
- [167] P.C.J. Graat et al., *J. Appl. Phys.* 82 (3) (1997) 1416–1422.
- [168] S.J. Roosendaal et al., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 84 (15) (2000) 3366–3369.
- [169] M.D. Susman et al., *J. Phys. Chem. C* 120 (29) (2016) 16140–16152.
- [170] A. Cabot et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 131 (32) (2009) 11326–11328.
- [171] N.E. Motl et al., *Chem. Mater.* 24 (9) (2012) 1552–1554.
- [172] M. Sun et al., *Chem. Mater.* 34 (4) (2022) 1965–1975.
- [173] Q. Zhang et al., *J. Mater. Chem.* 22 (5) (2012) 1765–1769.
- [174] K. Koga, D. Zubia, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 112 (6) (2008) 2079–2085.
- [175] K.W. Jeon et al., *Chem. Mater.* 29 (4) (2017) 1788–1795.
- [176] Y. Yu et al., *Acc. Chem. Res.* 51 (7) (2018) 1711–1721.
- [177] P. Zolotavin, P. Guyot-Sionnest, *ACS Nano* 6 (9) (2012) 8094–8104.
- [178] W. Yang et al., *Nanoscale* 8 (9) (2016) 4898–4902.
- [179] L. Shen et al., *Nat. Commun.* 6 (2015) 1–8.
- [180] N.W. Ashcroft, N.D. Mermin, *Thomson Learning Inc* (1976) .
- [181] M. Sun, B. Huang, *Inorg. Chem.* 56 (14) (2017) 7975–7984.
- [182] J. Kim et al., *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* 5 (8) (2014) 1312–1317.
- [183] E. Mosconi et al., *Energy Environ. Sci.* 9 (10) (2016) 3180–3187.
- [184] A. Smigelskas, *Trans. Aime* 171 (1947) 130–142.
- [185] A. Li et al., *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 48 (7) (2019) 1874–1907.
- [186] M.Y. Liu et al., *Crystengcomm* 13 (17) (2011) 5460–5466.
- [187] J.S. Cho et al., *Sci. Rep.* 6 (2016) 38933.
- [188] A.A. El Mel et al., *J. Phys. Chem. C* 121 (35) (2017) 19497–19504.
- [189] H.J. Fan et al., *Nano Lett.* 7 (4) (2007) 993–997.
- [190] A. Pendashteh et al., *Energy Stor. Mater.* 20 (2019) 216–224.
- [191] K. An et al., *Nano Lett.* 8 (12) (2008) 4252–4258.
- [192] H.S. Shim et al., *Chem. Mater.* 21 (9) (2009) 1875–1883.
- [193] R. Nakamura et al., *J. Appl. Phys.* 101 (7) (2007) 074303–074310.
- [194] G. Simons et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 98 (24) (1976) 7869–7870.
- [195] M.E. Thompson et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 109 (1) (1987) 203–219.
- [196] K.C. Crellin et al., *Organometallics* 13 (9) (1994) 3733–3736.
- [197] P. Shewmon, *Diffusion in Solids*, Springer, 2016.
- [198] D.R. Cummins et al., *Nano Lett.* 13 (6) (2013) 2423–2430.
- [199] R.H. Condit et al., *Oxid. Met.* 8 (6) (1974) 409–455.
- [200] E. Fryt et al., *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 126 (4) (1979) 673.
- [201] W.D. Kingery et al., *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 43 (9) (1960) 473–475.
- [202] J.A. Van Orman, K.L. Crispin, *Rev. Mineral. Geochem.* 72 (1) (2010) 757–825.
- [203] C.E. Birchenall, *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.* 46 (5) (2002) 893–898.
- [204] C.L. Muhich et al., *Chem. Mater.* 28 (1) (2015) 214–226.
- [205] C. Bothe et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 54 (47) (2015) 14183–14186.
- [206] N. Cabrera, N.F. Mott, *Rep. Prog. Phys.* 12 (1949) 163–184.
- [207] Q. Fu, T. Wagner, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 109 (23) (2005) 11697–11705.
- [208] W.H. Blades, P. Reinke, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 10 (49) (2018) 43219–43229.
- [209] D.B. Pedersen et al., *J. Phys. Chem. C* 111 (37) (2007) 13665–13672.
- [210] J. Wu et al., *J. Phys. Chem. C* 116 (23) (2012) 12861–12874.
- [211] G. Gupta et al., *Langmuir* 31 (24) (2015) 6917–6923.
- [212] U. Khalilov et al., *Acc. Chem. Res.* 50 (4) (2017) 796–804.
- [213] Z. Xu et al., *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 14 (42) (2012) 14534–14539.
- [214] V.P. Zhdanov, B. Kasemo, *Chem. Phys. Lett.* 452 (4–6) (2008) 285–288.
- [215] Z.J. Farrell, C. Tabor, *Langmuir* 34 (1) (2018) 234–240.
- [216] L.P.H. Jeurgens et al., *J. Appl. Phys.* 92 (3) (2002) 1649–1656.
- [217] L.P.H. Jeurgens et al., *Phys. Rev. B* 62 (7) (2000) 4707–4719.
- [218] C.M. Wang et al., *J. Appl. Phys.* 98 (9) (2005) 094308–094315.
- [219] E. Sutter, P. Sutter, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 100 (23) (2012) 231602–231606.
- [220] J.M. Eldridge et al., *Thin Solid Films* 12 (2) (1972) 447–451.
- [221] H. Liu et al., *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 13 (48) (2021) 58134–58143.
- [222] N. Syed et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 141 (1) (2019) 104–108.
- [223] K.Y. Niu et al., *Nano Lett.* 13 (11) (2013) 5715–5719.
- [224] L. Castilla-Amoros et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 144 (4) (2022) 1993–2001.
- [225] G. Valensi, *Compt. Rend* 202 (4) (1936) 309–312.
- [226] G. Valensi, *CR Acad Sci* 202 (4) (1935) 309–312.
- [227] R.E. Carter, *J. Chem. Phys.* 34 (6) (1961) 2010–2015.
- [228] R.E. Carter, *J. Chem. Phys.* 35 (3) (1961) 1137–1138.
- [229] L.P. Ramirez et al., *J. Phys. Chem. C* 126 (5) (2022) 2517–2530.
- [230] M. Yin et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 127 (26) (2005) 9506–9511.
- [231] S. Uk Son et al., *Chem. Commun. (Camb)* 7 (2004) 778–779.
- [232] L.I. Hung et al., *Adv. Mater.* 22 (17) (2010) 1910–1914.
- [233] K.P. Rice et al., *J. Phys. Chem. C* 115 (5) (2011) 1793–1799.
- [234] D.B. Pedersen et al., *J. Phys. Chem. C* 112 (24) (2008) 8819–8826.
- [235] G.H. Chan et al., *Nano Lett.* 7 (7) (2007) 1947–1952.
- [236] C. Barrière et al., *J. Mater. Chem.* 22 (5) (2012) 2279–2285.
- [237] K.P. Rice et al., *Part. Part. Syst. Char.* 32 (3) (2015) 373–380.
- [238] M.D. Susman et al., *Nanoscale* 9 (34) (2017) 12573–12589.
- [239] R. Nakamura et al., *Acta Mater.* 57 (14) (2009) 4261–4266.
- [240] B. Koo et al., *Nano Lett.* 12 (5) (2012) 2429–2435.
- [241] T. Hyeon et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 123 (51) (2001) 12798–12801.
- [242] J.B. Tracy et al., *Phys. Rev. B* 72 (6) (2005) 064404–064412.
- [243] Z. Yang et al., *ACS Nano* 7 (2) (2013) 1342–1350.
- [244] N. Doan et al., *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 350 (1) (2010) 126–131.

- [245] R. Sainju et al., *ACS Nano* 16 (4) (2022) 6468–6479.
- [246] R. Nakamura et al., *Philos. Mag.* 88 (2) (2008) 257–264.
- [247] L. Yu et al., *Nano Lett.* 16 (10) (2016) 6555–6559.
- [248] Z. Zhuang et al., *Adv. Mater.* 26 (23) (2014) 3950–3955.
- [249] W. Zhan et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 139 (26) (2017) 8846–8854.
- [250] Z. Zhang et al., *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.* 1 (10) (2018) 5837–5842.
- [251] R. Nakamura et al., *Mater. Lett.* 61 (4–5) (2007) 1060–1063.
- [252] P. Zolotavin, P. Guyot-Sionnest, *ACS Nano* 4 (10) (2010) 5599–5608.
- [253] K.M. Nam et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 47 (49) (2008) 9504–9508.
- [254] J.Y. Sun et al., *Small* 15 (6) (2019) 1804272.
- [255] J. Gao et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 129 (5) (2007) 1428–1433.
- [256] T. Zhu et al., *Rsc Adv.* 1 (3) (2011) 397–400.
- [257] J. Zhang et al., *Science* 327 (5973) (2010) 1634–1638.
- [258] J.F. Román-Zamorano et al., *J. Mater. Sci.* 44 (18) (2009) 4781–4788.
- [259] A. Cabot et al., *ACS Nano* 2 (7) (2008) 1452–1458.
- [260] Q. Li, R.M. Penner, *Nano Lett.* 5 (9) (2005) 1720–1725.
- [261] Q. Lv et al., *Adv. Healthc. Mater.* 8 (2) (2019) 1–11.
- [262] F. Dawood, R.E. Schaak, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 131 (2) (2009) 424–425.
- [263] S.M. Yang et al., *J. Energy Storage* 44 (2021) 103407–103416.
- [264] J. Gao et al., *Angew. Chem.* 118 (8) (2006) 1242–1245.
- [265] M.A. Hossain et al., *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 513 (2020) 145721.
- [266] H. Tan et al., *J. Phys. Chem. B* 110 (32) (2006) 15812–15816.
- [267] A.K. Guria et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 137 (15) (2015) 5123–5129.
- [268] S.H. Xiao et al., *ACS Nano* 15 (8) (2021) 13307–13318.
- [269] W. Lu et al., *Langmuir* 21 (8) (2005) 3684–3687.
- [270] L. De Trizio et al., *ACS Nano* 6 (1) (2012) 32–41.
- [271] E. Muthuswamy et al., *ACS Nano* 3 (8) (2009) 2383–2393.
- [272] X.L. Guan et al., *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 44 (57) (2019) 30053–30061.
- [273] J.N. Tiwari et al., *Nano Energy* 78 (2020) 105166.
- [274] K. Zhang et al., *Nano Research* 10 (12) (2017) 4337–4350.
- [275] S.S. Yang et al., *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 44 (10) (2019) 4543–4552.
- [276] A.E. Henkes et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 129 (7) (2007) 1896–1897.
- [277] J. Wang et al., *Chem. Mater.* 21 (19) (2009) 4462–4467.
- [278] S. Carencio et al., *Chem. Mater.* 23 (8) (2011) 2270–2277.
- [279] A.R.J. Kucernak et al., *Catal. Today* 262 (2016) 48–56.
- [280] S.S. Luo et al., *Colloid Surf. A* 600 (2020) 124925.
- [281] B.X. Tao et al., *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 44 (2) (2019) 531–539.
- [282] X.P. Zhang et al., *Chemosuschem* 9 (21) (2016) 3049–3053.
- [283] S. Chen, A. Riedinger, *Chem. Commun. (Camb)* 58 (66) (2022) 9246–9249.
- [284] Q. Wu et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 125 (34) (2003) 10176–10177.
- [285] Y. Ma et al., *J. Mater. Chem.* 16 (2006) 27.
- [286] J. Zheng et al., *J. Solid State Chem* 180 (1) (2007) 276–283.
- [287] Q.H. Zhang, L. Gao, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 89 (2) (2006) 415–421.
- [288] R.A. Karaballi et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 58 (10) (2019) 3147–3150.
- [289] R.A. Karaballi et al., *Langmuir* 36 (18) (2020) 5058–5064.
- [290] J. Li et al., *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 84 (12) (2001) 3045–3047.
- [291] Y. Zhu et al., *ACS Catal.* 7 (5) (2017) 3540–3547.
- [292] C. Zhao et al., *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.* 4 (10) (2021) 10735–10742.
- [293] X. Li et al., *Nano Energy* 57 (2019) 57–65.
- [294] M. Su et al., *Mater. Chem. Front.* 5 (12) (2021) 4571–4578.
- [295] K. Woo et al., *Chem. Mater.* 16 (14) (2004) 2814–2818.
- [296] C. Chen et al., *Science* 343 (6177) (2014) 1339–1343.
- [297] Y. Piao et al., *Nat. Mater.* 7 (3) (2008) 242–247.
- [298] S. Jeong et al., *Nano Lett.* 20 (10) (2020) 7263–7271.
- [299] A.C. Johnston-Peck et al., *ACS Nano* 3 (5) (2009) 1077–1084.
- [300] T.-L. Cheng et al., *J. Phys. Chem. C* 118 (2) (2014) 1269–1284.
- [301] R. Peter, M. Petracic, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 125 (45) (2021) 25290–25297.
- [302] A.P. Alivisatos, *Science* 271 (1996) 933–937.
- [303] T. Hyeon, *Chem. Commun. (Camb)* 8 (2003) 927–934.
- [304] S. Sun et al., *Science* 287 (5460) (2000) 1989–1992.
- [305] H.C. Zeng, *J. Mater. Chem.* 16 (7) (2006) 649–662.
- [306] A.H. Latham et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 128 (39) (2006) 12632–12633.
- [307] M. Avrami, *J. Chem. Phys.* 7 (12) (1939) 1103–1112.
- [308] C. Wagner, *Z. Phys. Chem* 21B (1) (1933) 25–41.
- [309] D. Wang, Y. Li, *Inorg. Chem.* 50 (11) (2011) 5196–5202.
- [310] G.A. Devries et al., *Science* 315 (5810) (2007) 358–361.
- [311] R.P. Carney et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 130 (3) (2008) 798–799.
- [312] G.A. DeVries et al., *Adv. Mater.* 20 (22) (2008) 4243–4247.
- [313] K. Nakata et al., *Adv. Mater.* 20 (22) (2008) 4294–4299.
- [314] J.C. Bauer et al., *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 13 (7) (2011) 2571–2581.
- [315] J. Yin et al., *Chem. Mater.* 24 (24) (2012) 4662–4674.
- [316] A.P. Grosvenor et al., *Surf. Sci.* 565 (2–3) (2004) 151–162.
- [317] A.P. Grosvenor et al., *Surf. Sci.* 574 (2–3) (2005) 317–321.
- [318] G.W. Leibbrandt et al., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 68 (12) (1992) 1947–1950.
- [319] R. Nakamura et al., *Acta Mater.* 57 (17) (2009) 5046–5052.
- [320] K.P. Kepp, *Inorg. Chem.* 55 (18) (2016) 9461–9470.
- [321] V. Mehar et al., *ACS Catal.* 10 (23) (2020) 13878–13889.
- [322] W. Luc et al., *ACS Catal.* 8 (10) (2018) 9327–9333.
- [323] F. Weinhold, R. West, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 135 (15) (2013) 5762–5767.
- [324] C.E. Anson et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 47 (7) (2008) 1326–1331.
- [325] R. Ma et al., *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 47 (6) (2013) 2527–2534.
- [326] K. An, T. Hyeon, *Nano Today* 4 (4) (2009) 359–373.
- [327] R.D. Shannon, *Acta Crystallogr. Sect. A* 32 (5) (1976) 751–767.
- [328] C. Stinn, A. Allanore, *Nature* 602 (7895) (2022) 78–83.
- [329] Y. Tan et al., *Adv. Mater.* 28 (15) (2016) 2951–2955.
- [330] J. Liu et al., *J. Mater. Chem. A* 6 (24) (2018) 11453–11462.
- [331] Q. Liu et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 53 (26) (2014) 6710–6714.
- [332] G.F. Chen et al., *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 26 (19) (2016) 3314–3323.
- [333] C. Lv et al., *J. Mater. Chem. A* 4 (4) (2016) 1454–1460.
- [334] Y. Ge et al., *Adv. Energy Mater* 8 (21) (2018) 1–29.
- [335] X. Zhang et al., *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 28 (16) (2018) 1706523.
- [336] C. Qian et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 126 (4) (2004) 1195–1198.
- [337] A.E. Henkes, R.E. Schaak, *Inorg. Chem.* 47 (2) (2008) 671–677.
- [338] S. Carencio et al., *Chem. Mater.* 24 (21) (2012) 4134–4145.
- [339] P.K. Khanna et al., *Mater. Chem. Phys.* 92 (1) (2005) 54–58.
- [340] E. Ye et al., *Chem* 17 (21) (2011) 5982–5988.
- [341] E.J. Popczun et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 53 (21) (2014) 5427–5430.
- [342] E.J. Popczun et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 135 (25) (2013) 9267–9270.
- [343] L. Wu et al., *Chem. Rev.* 116 (18) (2016) 10473–10512.
- [344] N.N. Greenwood, A. Earnshaw, *Chemistry of the Elements*, Elsevier, 2012.
- [345] A.-M. Nguyen et al., *Chem. Mater.* 31 (16) (2019) 6124–6134.
- [346] D.H. Ha et al., *J. Mater. Chem.* 21 (31) (2011) 11498–11510.
- [347] L. Zhang et al., *Science* 349 (6246) (2015) 412–416.
- [348] S. Pedireddy et al., *Nat. Commun.* 5 (2014) 4947.
- [349] X. Huang et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 48 (26) (2009) 4808–4812.
- [350] X. Wang et al., *Nano Lett.* 16 (2) (2016) 1467–1471.
- [351] Y. Hu et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 53 (14) (2014) 3675–3679.
- [352] S. Shen, Q. Wang, *Chem. Mater.* 25 (8) (2012) 1166–1178.
- [353] L. Manna et al., *Acc. Chem. Res.* 54 (7) (2021) 1543–1544.
- [354] S. Ding et al., *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 10 (21) (2018) 17911–17922.
- [355] H.X. Han et al., *Acc. Chem. Res.* 54 (3) (2021) 509–519.
- [356] G. Song et al., *Adv. Mater.* 28 (14) (2016) 2716–2723.
- [357] Z. Jin et al., *Acc. Chem. Res.* 50 (4) (2017) 895–904.
- [358] S. Anantharaj et al., *ACS Catal.* 6 (12) (2016) 8069–8097.
- [359] W. Chen et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 49 (16) (2010) 2917–2921.
- [360] C.L. Bracey et al., *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 38 (8) (2009) 2231–2243.
- [361] T.A. Witten, L.M. Sander, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 47 (19) (1981) 1400–1403.
- [362] E. Benjacob et al., *Physica A* 187 (3–4) (1992) 378–424.
- [363] G. Daccord et al., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 56 (4) (1986) 336–339.
- [364] B. Gerss et al., *Cryst Growth Des* 15 (6) (2015) 3046–3051.
- [365] M. Lattuada, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 116 (1) (2012) 120–129.
- [366] Y.C. Ou et al., *J. Phys. Chem. C* 114 (41) (2010) 17416–17421.
- [367] Y.-C. Hsu et al., *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.* 3 (11) (2020) 11399–11407.
- [368] R.J. Borg, G.J. Dienes, *An Introduction to Solid State Diffusion*, Elsevier, 2012.
- [369] M. Shim, P. Guyot-Sionnest, *J. Chem. Phys.* 111 (15) (1999) 6955–6964.
- [370] K.S. Cho et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 127 (19) (2005) 7140–7147.
- [371] J.G. Li et al., *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 11 (8) (2019) 8106–8114.
- [372] D. Chen et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 57 (28) (2018) 8691–8696.
- [373] P. Zhou et al., *Chem. Commun. (Camb)* 53 (86) (2017) 11778–11781.
- [374] A. Bergqvist et al., *Chem. Educ. Res. Pract.* 14 (4) (2013) 589–606.
- [375] H. Oh et al., *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 10 (43) (2018) 37643–37650.
- [376] J.A. Fauchaux et al., *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* 5 (6) (2014) 976–985.
- [377] W.J. Vining et al., *Inorg. Chem.* 32 (20) (1993) 4214–4217.
- [378] A. Fischer et al., *ACS Nano* 2 (12) (2008) 2489–2496.
- [379] R. Michalsky, P.H. Pfromm, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 116 (44) (2012) 23243–23251.
- [380] W.-S. Jung, S.-K. Ahn, *J. Mater. Chem.* 4 (6) (1994) 949–953.
- [381] G.A. Slack, *J. Phys. Chem. Solids* 34 (2) (1973) 321–335.
- [382] T. Mroz, *Am. Ceram. Soc. Bull.* 70 (5) (1991) 849–850.
- [383] J.-K. Kim, W.-S. Jung, *J. Ceram. Soc. Jpn.* 119 (1389) (2011) 351–354.
- [384] W.-S. Jung, S.-K. Ahn, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 21 (1) (2001) 79–85.
- [385] A. Paseuth, S. Shimada, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 91 (4) (2008) 1129–1134.
- [386] T. Yamakawa et al., *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 89 (1) (2006) 171–175.
- [387] W.-S. Jung, *J. Ceram. Soc. Jpn.* 119 (1396) (2011) 968–971.
- [388] W.-S. Jung, *J. Ceram. Soc. Jpn.* 120 (1403) (2012) 272–275.
- [389] H. Zhao et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 127 (45) (2005) 15722–15723.
- [390] X. Chen et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 127 (22) (2005) 7982–7983.

- [391] S. Sen et al., *Chem. Mater.* 34 (21) (2022) 9329–9343.
- [392] D.K. Harris et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 133 (13) (2011) 4676–4679.
- [393] P.J. Lin-Chung, *Phys. Rev.* 188 (3) (1969) 1272–1280.
- [394] D. Franke et al., *Nat. Commun.* 7 (2016) 12749.
- [395] D. Li et al., *Chem. Mater.* 26 (12) (2014) 3599–3602.
- [396] B.A. Glassy, B.M. Cossairt, *Small* 13 (40) (2017) 1702038.
- [397] V. Srivastava et al., *Chem. Mater.* 28 (18) (2016) 6797–6802.
- [398] A. Das et al., *Chem. Mater.* 28 (11) (2016) 4058–4064.
- [399] D. Xue et al., *Nanoscale* 11 (37) (2019) 17478–17484.
- [400] D. Wang et al., *J. Mater. Chem. A* 1 (5) (2013) 1587–1590.
- [401] L. Yu et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 53 (14) (2014) 3711–3714.
- [402] L. Yu et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 55 (43) (2016) 13422–13426.
- [403] Z. Wang et al., *Chem. Commun. (Camb)* 47 (28) (2011) 8061–8063.
- [404] *Sov. Phys. Semicond* 16(7) (1982) 772–775.
- [405] S. Link, M.A. El-Sayed, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 103 (40) (1999) 8410–8426.
- [406] S. Link, M.A. El-Sayed, *Annu. Rev. Phys. Chem.* 54 (2003) 331–366.
- [407] S. Link, M.A. El-Sayed, *Int. Rev. Phys. Chem.* 19 (3) (2000) 409–453.
- [408] J. Medema, J.P.W. Houtman, *Anal. Chem.* 41 (1) (1969) 209–211.
- [409] T.L. Hill, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 68 (1946) 535–536.
- [410] P.R. Tremaine, D.G. Gray, *Anal. Chem.* 48 (2) (1976) 380–382.
- [411] J. Haussonne et al., *Am. Ceram. Soc. Bull.* 72 (5) (1993) 84–90.
- [412] H.G. Stunnenberg et al., *Science* 347 (6222) (2015) 614–615.
- [413] J. Boles et al., *J. Bus. Ind. Mark.* 15 (2/3) (2000) 141–153.
- [414] R. Wu et al., *J. Mater. Chem. A* 1 (37) (2013) 11126–11129.
- [415] Y. Fu et al., *Rsc Adv.* 5 (106) (2015) 86941–86944.
- [416] C.C. Hou et al., *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* 59 (48) (2020) 21360–21366.
- [417] W.F. Miao et al., *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 556 (2019) 432–440.
- [418] F. Yan et al., *Nanoscale* 10 (6) (2018) 2697–2703.
- [419] R. Bardestani et al., *Can. J. Chem. Eng.* 97 (11) (2019) 2781–2791.
- [420] L.D. Gelb, K.E. Gubbins, *Langmuir* 15 (2) (1998) 305–308.
- [421] I.U. Arachchige et al., *Chem. Mater.* 17 (26) (2005) 6644–6650.
- [422] K. Morishige, Y. Nakamura, *Langmuir* 20 (11) (2004) 4503–4506.
- [423] M. Kruk et al., *J. Phys. Chem. B* 104 (2) (2000) 292–301.
- [424] W.E. Buhro, V.L. Colvin, *Nat. Mater.* 2 (3) (2003) 138–139.
- [425] C. Katan et al., *Chem. Rev.* 119 (5) (2019) 3140–3192.
- [426] A.M. Smith, S. Nie, *Acc. Chem. Res.* 43 (2) (2010) 190–200.
- [427] A.M.S.A.S. Nie, *Acc. Chem. Res.* (2009) 190–200.
- [428] A. Sitt et al., *Nano Today* 8 (5) (2013) 494–513.
- [429] R. Woods-Robinson et al., *Chem. Rev.* 120 (9) (2020) 4007–4055.
- [430] L. Liu et al., *Sol. RRL* 6 (8) (2022) 2200299.
- [431] C. Linderälv et al., *Chem. Mater.* 34 (21) (2022) 9364–9372.
- [432] C. Gong et al., *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 103 (5) (2013) 053513–053517.
- [433] M.H. Chiu et al., *Nat. Commun.* 6 (2015) 7666.
- [434] C.H. Chuang et al., *Nat. Mater.* 13 (8) (2014) 796–801.
- [435] M.R. Buck, R.E. Schaak, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 52 (24) (2013) 6154–6178.
- [436] L.F. Garcia-Herrera et al., *Chem. Mater.* 33 (10) (2021) 3841–3850.
- [437] R. Liu et al., *Small Struct.* 2 (3) (2020) 2000136–2000163.
- [438] W. Du et al., *Rsc Adv.* 4 (14) (2014) 6998–7002.
- [439] H. Chen et al., *Nanoscale* 5 (19) (2013) 8879–8883.
- [440] C. Xia et al., *Chem. Mater.* 27 (19) (2015) 6482–6485.
- [441] H. Cao et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 138 (48) (2016) 15727–15735.
- [442] K.L. Kelly et al., *J. Phys. Chem. B* 107 (3) (2003) 668–677.
- [443] P. Zhang et al., *Adv. Mater.* 27 (36) (2015) 5328–5342.
- [444] S.C. Warren, E. Thimsen, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 5 (1) (2012) 5133–5146.
- [445] K. Manthiram, A.P. Alivisatos, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 134 (9) (2012) 3995–3998.
- [446] S. Unser et al., *Sensors (Basel)* 15 (7) (2015) 15684–15716.
- [447] R. Jiang et al., *Adv. Mater.* 26 (31) (2014) 5274–5309.
- [448] A. Agrawal et al., *Chem. Rev.* 118 (6) (2018) 3121–3207.
- [449] S.A. Maier, *Plasmon.: Fundam. Appl.* (2007) .
- [450] W.L. Bade, *J. Chem. Phys.* 27 (6) (1957) 1280–1284.
- [451] A. Comin, L. Manna, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 43 (11) (2014) 3957–3975.
- [452] H. Tanimoto et al., *J. Phys. Chem. C* 119 (33) (2015) 19318–19325.
- [453] J.M. Bingham et al., *J. Phys. Chem. C Nanomater. Interfaces* 113 (39) (2009) 16839–16842.
- [454] K.M. Mayer, J.H. Hafner, *Chem. Rev.* 111 (6) (2011) 3828–3857.
- [455] P. Zijlstra et al., *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 7 (6) (2012) 379–382.
- [456] Y. Shen et al., *Nat. Commun.* 4 (2013) 2381–2390.
- [457] E. Hutter, J.H. Fendler, *Adv. Mater.* 16 (19) (2004) 1685–1706.
- [458] A. Dahlin et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 127 (14) (2005) 5043–5048.
- [459] J. Son et al., *Nano Lett.* 20 (7) (2020) 4985–4992.
- [460] M.D. Susman et al., *Chem. Mater.* 24 (13) (2012) 2501–2508.
- [461] S.L.A.M.A. El-Sayed, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 103 (1999) 8410–8426.
- [462] D. Kim et al., *Nat. Commun.* 5 (1) (2014) 5948.
- [463] A.K. Sra, R.E. Schaak, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 126 (21) (2004) 6667–6672.
- [464] Y. Zhao et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 131 (12) (2009) 4253–4261.
- [465] J.M. Luther et al., *Nat. Mater.* 10 (5) (2011) 361–366.
- [466] Y. Liu et al., *J. Phys. Chem. C* 121 (25) (2017) 13435–13447.
- [467] S.W. Hsu et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 133 (47) (2011) 19072–19075.
- [468] I. Kriegel et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 134 (3) (2012) 1583–1590.
- [469] I. Kriegel et al., *ACS Nano* 7 (5) (2013) 4367–4377.
- [470] L. Chen et al., *Mater. Adv.* 2 (3) (2021) 907–926.
- [471] W. van der Stam et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 139 (37) (2017) 13208–13217.
- [472] Y. Xie et al., *ACS Nano* 7 (8) (2013) 7352–7369.
- [473] R.M. Cordova-Castro et al., *ACS Nano* 13 (6) (2019) 6550–6560.
- [474] L. Berger et al., *Phys. Rev. B* 77 (10) (2008) 104431–104441.
- [475] D. Lisjak, A. Mertelj, *Prog. Mater. Sci.* 95 (2018) 286–328.
- [476] S.H. Noh et al., *Nano Lett.* 12 (7) (2012) 3716–3721.
- [477] D. Yoo et al., *Acc. Chem. Res.* 44 (10) (2011) 863–874.
- [478] X. Liu et al., *Nano Lett.* 21 (7) (2021) 2699–2708.
- [479] J. Gao et al., *Acc. Chem. Res.* 42 (8) (2009) 1097–1107.
- [480] A.H. Latham, M.E. Williams, *Acc. Chem. Res.* 41 (3) (2008) 411–420.
- [481] S.C. Tang, I.M. Lo, *Water Res.* 47 (8) (2013) 2613–2632.
- [482] A. Akbarzadeh et al., *Nanoscale Res. Lett.* 7 (1) (2012) 144.
- [483] K. McNamara, S.A.M. Tofail, *Adv. Phys.: X* 2 (1) (2016) 54–88.
- [484] G. Mohammadi Ziarani et al., *RSC Adv.* 9 (43) (2019) 25094–25106.
- [485] Z.L. Li et al., *Part. Part. Syst. Char.* 35 (8) (2018) 1800127–1800137.
- [486] J.A. Blackburn, *DC Measurements, in: Modern Instrumentation for Scientists and Engineers*, Springer, 2001, pp. 239–263.
- [487] F. Delahaye, B. Jeckelmann, *Metrologia* 40 (5) (2003) 217–223.
- [488] J.C. Abry et al., *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 61 (6) (2001) 855–864.
- [489] W.H. Meiklejohn, C.P. Bean, *Phys. Rev.* 105 (3) (1957) 904–913.
- [490] S.A. Wolf et al., *Science* 294 (5546) (2001) 1488–1495.
- [491] L. Xiao et al., *Nano Lett.* 8 (12) (2008) 4539–4545.
- [492] B.H. Zhou, J.D. Rinehart, *ACS Cent Sci* 4 (9) (2018) 1222–1227.
- [493] J. Park et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 127 (23) (2005) 8433–8440.
- [494] J.-G. Zhu, C. Park, *Mater. Today* 9 (11) (2006) 36–45.
- [495] G. Scheunert et al., *Appl. Phys. Rev.* 3 (1) (2016) 011301–011345.
- [496] C. Iniotakis et al., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 100 (3) (2008) 037002.
- [497] E.B. Sonin, K.B. Traito, *Phys. Rev. B Condens. Matter* 50 (18) (1994) 13547–13556.
- [498] K.I. Kugel, A.L. Rakhmanov, *Phys. C: Supercond.* 196 (1–2) (1992) 17–26.
- [499] K. Sato et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 133 (46) (2011) 18626–18633.
- [500] H.K. Kim et al., *Nano Lett.* 13 (3) (2013) 884–888.
- [501] I.R. Macdonald et al., *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* 1 (16) (2010) 2488–2492.
- [502] J.T. Batley et al., *Chem. Mater.* 32 (15) (2020) 6494–6506.
- [503] P.V. Lukashev et al., *ACS Nano* 6 (11) (2012) 9745–9750.
- [504] S. Zhu et al., *ACS Nano* 12 (4) (2018) 3442–3448.
- [505] M. Gong et al., *Nano Lett.* 14 (11) (2014) 6493–6498.
- [506] G.S. Chaubey et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 129 (23) (2007) 7214–7215.
- [507] M. Sarno et al., *Ind Eng Chem Res* 55 (11) (2016) 3157–3166.
- [508] G. Bai et al., *ACS Appl. Nano Mater.* 2 (6) (2019) 3570–3576.
- [509] C. Garnerio et al., *Nano Lett.* 19 (2) (2019) 1379–1386.
- [510] B. Mellander, M. Friesel, *Phys. Rev. B Condens. Matter* 35 (15) (1987) 7902–7905.
- [511] D. Xu et al., *Nano Lett.* 5 (4) (2005) 571–577.
- [512] S. Chakraborty, S. Padhy, *ACS Nano* 2 (10) (2008) 2029–2036.
- [513] R.J. Mehta et al., *Nano Lett.* 10 (11) (2010) 4417–4422.
- [514] R.B. McCleskey, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 47 (17) (2013) 9874–9881.
- [515] Y. Wang et al., *Chem. Rev.* 120 (21) (2020) 12217–12314.
- [516] C.H. Kuo et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 133 (4) (2011) 1052–1057.
- [517] G.N. Goltsman et al., *J. Supercond.* 7 (4) (1994) 751–755.
- [518] J. Wang et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 52 (25) (2013) 6417–6420.
- [519] Y. Zhao et al., *Adv. Energy Mater* 6 (8) (2016) 1502175–1502194.
- [520] Y. Wang et al., *J. Power Sources* 298 (2015) 203–208.
- [521] J.B. Goodenough, Y. Kim, *Chem. Mater.* 22 (3) (2009) 587–603.
- [522] A. Manthiram, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* 2 (3) (2011) 176–184.
- [523] M.R. Palacin, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 38 (9) (2009) 2565–2575.
- [524] J.M. Tarascon, *Philos. Trans. A Math. Phys. Eng. Sci.* 368 (1923) (2010) 3227–3241.
- [525] P. Poizot et al., *Nature* 407 (6803) (2000) 496–499.
- [526] G.B.M. Jain, J. Xu, *Chem. Mater.* 18 (2006) 423–434.
- [527] G. Zhang, X.W. Lou, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 53 (34) (2014) 9041–9044.
- [528] Z. Wang et al., *Adv. Mater.* 24 (14) (2012) 1903–1911.
- [529] Z. Wang et al., *Energy Environ. Sci.* 5 (1) (2012) 5252–5256.
- [530] G. Zhang et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 52 (33) (2013) 8643–8647.
- [531] S. Xu et al., *Energy Environ. Sci.* 7 (2) (2014) 632–637.

- [532] Y. You, A. Manthiram, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 8 (2) (2017) 1701785–1701796.
- [533] P.K. Nayak et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 57 (1) (2018) 102–120.
- [534] F. Li, Z. Zhou, *Small* 14 (6) (2018) 1702961.
- [535] B.L. Ellis, L.F. Nazar, *Curr. Opin. Solid St. M* 16 (4) (2012) 168–177.
- [536] H. Che et al., *Energy Environ. Sci.* 10 (5) (2017) 1075–1101.
- [537] Y. Shan et al., *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 30 (23) (2020) 1–31.
- [538] N. Yabuuchi et al., *Chem. Rev.* 114 (23) (2014) 11636–11682.
- [539] X. Xiang et al., *Adv. Mater.* 27 (36) (2015) 5343–5364.
- [540] D. Kundu et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 54 (11) (2015) 3431–3448.
- [541] B.E. Conway, *Electrochemical Supercapacitors: Scientific Fundamentals and Technological Applications*, Springer Science & Business Media, 2013.
- [542] M.R. Gao et al., *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 42 (7) (2013) 2986–3017.
- [543] C. Han et al., *Adv. Sci* 3 (5) (2016) 1500350–1500361.
- [544] A. Huang et al., *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 11 (43) (2019) 39991–39997.
- [545] C. Hu et al., *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 10 (39) (2018) 33124–33134.
- [546] H. Wan et al., *Crystengcomm* 15 (38) (2013) 7649–7651.
- [547] J. Pu et al., *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* 2 (4) (2013) 809–815.
- [548] P. Cai et al., *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 504 (2020) 144501.
- [549] V. Augustyn et al., *Nat. Mater.* 12 (6) (2013) 518–522.
- [550] V. Augustyn et al., *Energy Environ. Sci.* 7 (5) (2014) 1597.
- [551] F. Béguin et al., *Adv. Mater.* 26 (14) (2014) 2219–2251.
- [552] G.D. Moon et al., *ACS Nano* 5 (11) (2011) 8600–8612.
- [553] J. Wang et al., *Nature Energy* 1 (5) (2016) 1–8.
- [554] H. Wu et al., *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 7 (5) (2012) 310–315.
- [555] H. Ren et al., *Nano Lett.* 14 (11) (2014) 6679–6684.
- [556] M. Saruyama et al., *Chem. Sci.* 9 (21) (2018) 4830–4836.
- [557] M. Wang et al., *J. Catal* 371 (2019) 262–269.
- [558] J.-S. Li et al., *J. Mater. Chem. A* 4 (4) (2016) 1202–1207.
- [559] J. Tian et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 136 (21) (2014) 7587–7590.
- [560] J. Yin et al., *Chem-Eur J* 19 (41) (2013) 13979–13986.
- [561] W. Li et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 135 (19) (2013) 7098–7101.
- [562] X. Chen et al., *Sens. Actuators B: Chem.* 280 (2019) 151–161.
- [563] S. Silvi, A. Credi, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 44 (13) (2015) 4275–4289.
- [564] P. Neumann et al., *Nano Lett.* 13 (6) (2013) 2738–2742.
- [565] D. Patil et al., *Talanta* 81 (1–2) (2010) 37–43.
- [566] B. Li et al., *Chem. Mater.* 12 (9) (2000) 2614–2616.
- [567] K. Arshak, I. Gaidan, *Sens. Actuators B: Chem.* 111–112 (2005) 58–62.
- [568] F. Caballero-Briones et al., *Electrochem. Commun.* 10 (11) (2008) 1684–1687.
- [569] D. Koziej et al., *Catal. Today* 126 (1–2) (2007) 211–218.
- [570] R. Toyoshima et al., *J. Phys. Chem. C* 117 (40) (2013) 20617–20624.
- [571] R.J. Baxter, P. Hu, *J. Chem. Phys.* 116 (11) (2002) 4379–4381.
- [572] P. Feng et al., *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 89 (11) (2006) 112114–112117.
- [573] J. Gao, B. Xu, *Nano Today* 4 (1) (2009) 37–51.
- [574] P.M. Takahara et al., *Nature* 377 (6550) (1995) 649–652.
- [575] P.M. Takahara et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 118 (49) (1996) 12309–12321.
- [576] L. Giovagnini et al., *J. Med. Chem.* 48 (5) (2005) 1588–1595.
- [577] J. Shi et al., *Nat Rev Cancer* 17 (1) (2017) 20–37.
- [578] W. Tao et al., *Adv. Mater.* 30 (38) (2018) 1–11.
- [579] W. Tao et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 56 (39) (2017) 11896–11900.
- [580] X. Zhu et al., *ACS Nano* 12 (3) (2018) 2922–2938.
- [581] V. Shanmugam et al., *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 43 (17) (2014) 6254–6287.
- [582] W. Tao et al., *Adv. Mater.* 29 (1) (2017) 1–9.
- [583] Z. Sheng et al., *ACS Nano* 8 (12) (2014) 12310–12322.
- [584] L. Cheng et al., *Chem. Rev.* 114 (21) (2014) 10869–10939.
- [585] J. Huang et al., *Adv. Mater.* 27 (34) (2015) 5049–5056.
- [586] X. Yi et al., *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 25 (29) (2015) 4689–4699.
- [587] P. Huang et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 52 (52) (2013) 13958–13964.
- [588] W. Yang et al., *ACS Nano* 12 (12) (2018) 12169–12180.
- [589] M. Zhou et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 132 (43) (2010) 15351–15358.
- [590] Q. Tian et al., *ACS Nano* 5 (12) (2011) 9761–9771.
- [591] K. Dong et al., *Adv. Mater.* 25 (32) (2013) 4452–4458.
- [592] Y. Chen et al., *Anal. Chem.* 88 (12) (2016) 6115–6119.
- [593] H. Di et al., *Anal. Chem.* 89 (11) (2017) 5874–5881.
- [594] B. Zhou et al., *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 10 (11) (2015) 924–936.
- [595] L. Cheng et al., *Nanoscale* 5 (1) (2013) 23–37.
- [596] M. Chen et al., *Chem. Commun. (Camb)* 48 (71) (2012) 8934–8936.
- [597] C. Zhang et al., *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* 55 (6) (2016) 2101–2106.
- [598] X. Huang et al., *Acc. Chem. Res.* 50 (10) (2017) 2529–2538.
- [599] Y. Ding et al., *Exploration* 2 (3) (2022) 1–18.
- [600] R. Long et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 135 (8) (2013) 3200–3207.